

Graphene and Its Derivatives Based Polymer Nanocomposites for Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Applications: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract:

Over the last two decades, graphene and its derivatives based fascinating materials have been exploited in the synthesis of multifunctional polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) derived from various polymer matrices including elastomers, thermoplastics, thermosets, biopolymers, and conducting polymers. They have been extensively demonstrated. This review provides an in-depth discussion of the recent developments and perspectives of graphene-derived multifunctional PNCs for application in electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding devices. In the first part of the review, the synthesis routes of graphene and its derivatives have been discussed in detail. Later, different processing methods of graphene-derived PNCs have also been discussed. Furthermore, the review discusses the primary EMI shielding mechanism and key parameters that define the EMI shielding effectiveness (SE) of graphene-based PNCs. Besides, the review also highlights key parameters such as the type of polymer matrix, nanofiller type and concentration, sample thickness, and grain size that need to be considered for advancing the EMI shielding properties of PNCs. Finally, the review provides insight into the factors influencing the EMI SE values of PNCs and discusses the challenges and future perspectives for developing a new generation of shielding materials.

Keywords: Graphene and its derivatives; Graphene/polymer nanocomposites; EMI shielding; EMI shielding mechanisms.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction
2. Synthesis Methods of Graphene and Its Derivatives
 - 2.1 Synthesis Methods of Pristine Graphene
 - 2.1.1 Mechanical Exfoliation
 - 2.1.2 Liquid Phase Exfoliation
 - 2.1.3 Epitaxial Growth
 - 2.1.4 Chemical Vapour Deposition
 - 2.1.5 Chemically and Thermally Synthesized Graphene
 - 2.2 Synthesis Methods of Graphene Oxide and Reduced Graphene Oxide
 - 2.2.1 Graphene Oxide: An Overview of Structure, and Surface Chemistry
 - 2.2.2 Synthesis Approaches of Graphene Oxide
 - 2.2.3 Chemical Reduction of Graphene Oxide
 - 2.2.4 Thermal Reduction of Graphene Oxide
3. Processing Methods of Graphene Based Polymer Nanocomposites
 - 3.1 Solution Blending Method
 - 3.2 Melt Blending Method
 - 3.3 In-situ Polymerization Method
4. Electromagnetic Interference Shielding: Definition, Key Parameters, and Shielding Mechanisms
 - 4.1 Reflection
 - 4.2 Absorption
 - 4.3 Multiple Reflections
 - 4.4 Shielding Effectiveness
5. EMI Shielding Applications of Graphene Based Polymer Nanocomposites
 - 5.1 Elastomer Based Graphene Composites
 - 5.2 Thermoplastic Based Graphene Composites
 - 5.3 Thermosets Based Graphene Composites
 - 5.4 Biopolymer Based Graphene Composites
 - 5.5 Conducting Polymer Based Graphene Composites
6. Factors Influencing the EMI Shielding Properties of Polymer Nanocomposites
7. Conclusions and Perspectives
- References

1. Introduction

Carbon, the most fascinating constituent in the periodic table exhibits several allotropic forms such as diamond and graphite which are well-known from primeval times; while nanotubes, fullerenes, etc. were invented in contemporary times. These carbon allotropes have captured a noteworthy position in nanoscience and nanotechnology owing to their remarkable mechanical, chemical, thermal, and electrical properties. The most promising carbon allotropic form among the naturally known and discovered carbon-based materials is graphene which has seized special attention among the research community. Graphene, a fundamental unit of graphite-like material, with a two-dimensional (2D) single atomic layer thick sheet of sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms that exhibit honeycomb or hexagonal structure and entices a keen interest amongst researchers owing to its remarkable mechanical, electrical, thermal, biomedical and optical applications [1-4]. Thus, graphene has attracted extensive interest among scientists and researchers for its exceptional properties as well as prodigious application perspective in recent times. Graphene is composed of either mono- or double or few- layers of sp^2 bonded carbon atoms oriented in a six-member ring arranged in the 2D honeycomb structure.

During the last twenty years, graphene has been sparkling as a rising star in all the sectors of science and technology i.e., material science, nanoelectronics, condensed matter physics, and so on [1]. In 2004, Prof. Sir, Andre. Konstantin Geim and Prof. Sir, Konstantin Sergeevich Novoselov from the University of Manchester (UK) were the first to discover graphene using the scotch tape method i.e., they mechanically exfoliated highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG). Later in 2010, Geim and Novoselov were awarded the prestigious Noble Prize in Physics for their revolutionary breakthrough and pioneering discovery of graphene. Since its discovery, graphene has vastly served as beneficial for physical, analytical, biomedical, and chemical applications. Ideally, graphene is distinguished as the primary building block for fabricating several carbon allotropes and is known to be the thinnest material across the globe possessing huge potential for myriads of applications [5-8]. But in the real sense, graphene has been recognized as the mother of all carbon materials useful in building zero-dimensional (0D) fullerenes or buckyballs via wrapping, one-dimensional (1D) carbon nanotubes (CNTs) via rolling and three-dimensional (3D) graphite via stacking as displayed in Figure 1 [9]. In the true sense, the sp^2 orbitals are hybridized from the three atomic orbitals of carbon atoms i.e., $2s$, $2p_x$ and $2p_y$. Thus, this sp^2 hybridization of the atomic orbitals makes the carbon atoms bind to the neighbouring carbon atoms via covalent sigma (σ) bonds; whose carbon-carbon bond length is 1.42 \AA (0.142 nm), resulting in graphene with honeycomb or

hexagonal planar structure (Figure 2) [10]. In other words, each carbon atom presents in the same plane of a honeycomb-like lattice structure connected through the covalent carbon-carbon bond, whilst the interlayers are attached via feeble Van der Waal forces.

Figure 1: Different isotropic form of carbon obtained from 2D graphene (a) 0D Fullerene, (b) 1D CNTs and (c) 3D graphite [9]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from MDPI.

Figure 2: Structural representation of (a) graphite and (b) graphene [10]. Copyright 2019. Adapted from Scientific Research Publishing Inc.

In comparison to other nanomaterials, graphene reveals significant stability, which may be attributed to the fact that the π -orbital of each carbon atom present in lattice bestows delocalized electron networks. The fourth atomic carbon orbital, i.e., $2p_z$ is positioned vertically to the out-of-plane hexagonal planar structure to produce bonds which from every neighbouring carbon atom can be hybridized jointly to yield an electron cloud above and below the sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms. The σ bonds existing amidst the hybridized sp^2 orbitals of graphene are solely responsible for the mechanical strength of its lattice structure, while the π band accounts for the remarkable electrical conductivity of graphene [3, 11-13]. Furthermore, the ubiquitous usage of this material may be due to the presence of aromatic structure, reactive sites, and free π - π electrons [14-16]. The beneficial properties including high specific surface area, outstanding optical transmittance, exceptional mechanical stability as well as flexibility, permeability to gases, supreme thermal and electronic conductivity, and many other superior properties of graphene promote its application range in every horizon of science and technology [14-17]. Thus, owing to all these attributes and application perspectives, graphene has been termed a miracle material [18].

Over the last two decades, a surge of research activities in graphene has already been carried out owing to the simplicity of its synthesis methods, uniqueness in its properties, and diversity in its high-end applications ranging from optoelectronic and photoconductive devices to tissue engineering, drug delivery, and medical imaging. The literature suggests that graphene is the strongest material having Young's modulus of ≈ 1100 GPa with a fracture strength of ≈ 125 GPa (which is ≈ 100 times greater than steel) [19, 20]. In addition, the thermal conductivity

of graphene is remarkably high i.e., $\approx 5000 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ whereas its specific surface area is also high i.e., $\approx 2630 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ [21, 22]. Owing to its quintessential crystal structure, the low energy electrons migrate relentlessly over the flat surface of graphene acting like Dirac fermions that result in several unique electrical attributes namely superior electrical conductivity of about $\approx 6000 \text{ S/cm}$ with no charge carriers, pseudo spin chirality on the basis of “Berry Phase”, ballistic charge transport phenomena, freaky quantum hall effect, etc., making it a potential futuristic material for the electronic industry [23-25]. Furthermore, graphene owns the fastest electron mobility ($\approx 15,000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1}$; lower than that of silver (Ag)), efficacious Fermi velocity (10^6 ms^{-1} at room temperature; analogous to the speed of light), exceeding high temperature-independent charge carrier mobility ($\approx 200,000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$; 200 times larger than that of silicon (Si)) [26, 27]. In fact, graphene is said to be a zero-band gap semiconductor having a diminutive overlay of the valence and conduction band [28]. These fascinating characteristics of graphene unveil its feasibility for numerous commercial applications including sensors [29], photovoltaic cells [30, 31], electronic and energy devices [1, 12], catalysis [32], graphene-based polymer nanocomposites (GPNCs) [33, 34], transparent and flexible conductive materials [35, 36], etc. However, the scientific community considers graphene to be a wonder and puzzling material and thus, research on this material is still going on and on in every facet of basic, applied, and technological sciences.

2. Synthesis Methods of Graphene and Its Derivatives

2.1 Synthesis Methods of Pristine Graphene

The development of graphene has started to cause great impacts on products manufactured from variegated industrial sectors; that range from transparent, flexible, and wearable electronics to high-end computing and electronics [37]. On the other hand, the production methods must be developed in such a way that they should have a keen focus on factors such as simplicity, quality, cost, and quantity. Graphene can be synthesized using graphite via mainly two methods i.e., “top-down” and “bottom-up” approaches as depicted schematically in Figure 3 [25]. The “top-down” approach comprises processes such as mechanical exfoliation and chemical synthesis i.e., chemical exfoliation succeeded by reduction of graphene derivatives namely graphene oxide (GO), liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) method, etc. and the “bottom-up” approach can be further categorized as epitaxial growth on silicon carbides (SiC) and several diverse types of substrates, and chemical vapour deposition (CVD), etc. [38-40]. Several other synthesis methods of graphene include unzipping CNTs, thermal

annealing, solvothermal, pyrolysis of sodium ethoxide, electrochemical, thermal decomposition, ball milling exfoliation, etc., wherein these methods need an in-depth study for producing a good quality graphene layer [41]. Among the aforementioned methods, the simplest one is the mechanical exfoliation method, the cost-effective method being LPE while the most familiar and potential approach for graphene synthesis is the CVD method by which supreme quality graphene can be obtained in large quantities [42-44]. Generally, the selection of the graphene synthesis method has a significant impact on its quality and application prospects [18]. Figure 4 represents the benefits and drawbacks of the most common synthesis approaches of graphene.

Figure 3: Schematic depiction of various graphene synthesis approaches [25]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 4: Benefits and drawbacks of various synthesis approaches of graphene.

2.1.1 Mechanical exfoliation

Mechanical exfoliation refers to the micromechanical cleavage of graphite flakes or HOPG using scotch tape; a conventional method that is being used for producing single-layer graphene (SLG) films (Figure 5) [32]. The term micromechanical cleavage indicates the process of peeling off graphite layers continuously from the bulk HOPG surface. Mechanical exfoliation is the simplest method which involves the interfacial peeling and interlayer tearing process which can be tuned by virtue of the properties, geometry, and exfoliation kinetics of graphene based materials [45]. This is undoubtedly the cheapest method of preparing premium-quality graphene. Novoselov et. al. [5] was the first research group that successfully adapted the mechanical exfoliation method to prepare SLG, which has eventually, become one of the celebrated methods among the research community. In this method, the scotch tape adhesion characteristics and exfoliation time are the key parameters for producing SLG or few-layer

graphene (FLG). The size of SLG film obtained using this method was up to 10 μm whilst that of the thick multi-layer graphene (MLG) is $\approx 100 \mu\text{m}$ [46]. The external force required for the mechanical cleaving of SLG from graphite is 300 nN/lm^2 [47]. Stacking of graphite sheets results due to the overlapping of partially filled 'p' orbital involving Van der Waal forces in the vertical direction to that of the plane of the sheet. On the contrary, in exfoliation, the huge lattice spacing, and feeble bonding exist in the perpendicular direction and minuscule lattice spacing and stronger bonding exist in the hexagonal plane structure [48]. Using mechanical exfoliation, premium-quality graphene flakes with a large surface area can be achieved with excellent structural and electronic characteristics proving the suitability of this process for basic research only. Nevertheless, the privilege of using this method is that high-quality monocrystalline graphene films can be produced without using any complicated experimental setup. However, this process is labour-intensive and demands a large amount of laborious work. Moreover, scaling up this technique for the commercial scale manufacturing of graphene seems difficult because of the low yield and random distribution of graphene flakes on the substrate. In addition, the thickness variation of exfoliated graphite is another challenge as the multiple layers and the size of the crystal domains are difficult to control [49].

Figure 5: Scotch tape or mechanical exfoliation method of graphene fabrication using HOPG [32]. Copyright 2011. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

2.1.2 Liquid Phase Exfoliation

In the past decade and a half, remarkable advances have been made in the liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) of graphene with tremendous success in the synthesis of graphene using various mediums including organic solvents, surfactants, or polymeric solutions, green dispersants, and/or ionic liquids. LPE is the most reputed method for bulk synthesis of multilayer graphene dispersions. These defect-free multilayer graphene dispersions can be realized in various organic solvents and can be used in coatings, composites, or paints. The three major steps involved in the LPE process are: (1) dispersing graphite in a solvent; (2) ultrasonication for exfoliating the graphite and finally (3) purification as depicted in Figure 6 [50]. In the first step, the graphite is dispersed or dissolved in organic solvents like dimethylformamide (DMF) [51], tetrahydrofuran (THF) [52], N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP) [53], and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) [54, 55]. The second step includes ultrasonication of the graphite/solvent mixture for exfoliation of graphene layers and the maximum time required for ultrasonication is ≈ 60 minutes with a power of 250-500 Watt. The third step is purification which is usually carried out with the help of the ultracentrifugation process for segregating the exfoliated and the unexfoliated graphene flakes. This process is regarded as a cost-effective and efficient one since the energy applied to the graphene/solvent mixture via sonication enables exfoliation. However, two main factors strongly impact the exfoliation of bulk graphite which are: (i) The input energy applied to the bulk graphite in liquid medium using a bath or probe sonicator. The bulk graphite is exfoliated efficiently when exposed to ultrasonic vibrations or waves. The actual structure of the bulk graphite is collapsed with the bubbles in the liquid into SLG or MLG, due to the large amount of energy generated from the cavitation bubbles or the shear forces that are formed from the ultrasonic vibrations. The second factor is the type of liquid media used as organic solvents, aqueous solutions of stabilizers, and ionic liquids [56]. The role of interfacial tension becomes prominent when a solid is dispersed into a liquid media. Ideally, the solvent chosen is expected to reduce the surface tension existing between the liquid and graphene flakes. In other words, it is imperative that the selected solvent must have surface tension equivalent to or greater than the energy of graphene-graphene interactions thereby assisting in the production of high-quality and high-yield graphene. Blake et. al. [51] and Hernandez et. al. [53] designed a facile approach to produce defectless graphene, wherein the NMP was used as an organic solvent to exfoliate graphite. The authors used NMP as its surface energy well - matches that of graphene and hence promotes the exfoliation process effectively. Hou et al. [57], recently reported urea-assisted LPE of graphite to produce FLG. Another study

reported the organic salt-aided LPE of expanded graphite to produce graphene nanosheets [58]. Of late, sodium dodecyl benzene (SDBS) surfactant was used by Lotya et. al. for facilitating the exfoliation of graphite in water [59]. It was noted that the coulomb repulsion occurring between the surfactant-coated sheets creates a huge potential barrier that inhibits the aggregation of graphene monolayers and stabilizes them. All these studies suggest recent advances in graphene synthesis using LPE of graphite demonstrating the utilization of different organic solvents, surfactants, and polymers thereby promoting graphene synthesis by regulating the parameters such as frequency of ultrasonication, and size distribution of cavitation bubbles [60]. The main merits of the LPE approach are that there are humongous solvents available which can be utilized for producing extremely good quality graphene, whereas the high boiling point, high cost, and low yield of graphene are some of the demerits witnessed in this approach.

Figure 6: LPE process of graphite with and without surfactants [50]. Copyright 2014. Reproduced with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

2.1.3 Epitaxial Growth

Graphene nanosheets of uniform wafer size, large area, and low defect density can be synthesized via a simple epitaxial growth method by thermal decomposition of SiC and other transition metal substrates namely platinum (Pt) and ruthenium (Ru), etc. in ultrahigh vacuum and ambient conditions [61, 62]. Epitaxial growth is a process of yielding epitaxial films that are formed from the deposition of a mono-crystalline film on mono-crystalline substrates [61-63]. On the basis of substrate type, epitaxial growth processes are classified as homo and hetero-epitaxial growth. In homo-epitaxial growth, the film deposited over the substrate is made of similar materials whereas; in hetero-epitaxial growth, the deposition of the film over the substrate is done using distinct materials. For example; SiC is a semiconductor material having a wide energy band gap of 3eV. It can be undoubtedly used as a substrate upon which electrical measurements can be carried out with ease [63]. In epitaxial growth on SiC, the substrates are thermally treated in a vacuum at elevated temperatures from 1200 to 1600°C resulting in the sublimation of Si atoms followed by the graphitization of carbon atoms [64]. The graphene obtained from this method is familiarly termed “epitaxial graphene” which displays excellent 2D electron gas performance and superior carrier mobility which is highly desirable for high-performance integrated circuits. Although the obtained graphene is bulk in quantity and very fine in quality, this process necessitates high vacuum as well as very expensive fabrication systems in addition to the strenuous efforts required for the removal of graphene from the substrates. The primary asset of this synthesis technique is that it produces graphene covering the entire substrate surface which allows the fabrication of circuits directly on the substrate. However, a huge difference persists in the properties of graphene obtained from the epitaxial growth and mechanical exfoliation method. This may be because the interfacial effects in epitaxially grown graphene are highly reliant on many factors such as substrates, pressure, temperature, and heating rates [61]. The SiC is commonly chosen as a substrate to grow graphene since it is a well-accepted substrate for light-emitting diodes (LEDs), radiation hard devices, high-frequency electronics, top-gated field effect transistors (FET), etc. [65].

2.1.4 Chemical Vapour Deposition

The most promising and feasible method for synthesizing SLG or MLG has been the CVD method. The procedure of graphene growth on metal substrates using the CVD technique is the same as that of the epitaxial growth on metal-based single crystals. Nevertheless, in CVD growth thin metal foils or films are used as substrates and also the pressure required for the growth of graphene is comparatively higher than epitaxial growth. The fundamental principle

in this approach involves the thermal decomposition of hydrocarbons at elevated temperatures (900-1000°C) on the surfaces of transition metal substrates. In recent times, the CVD process has been used to develop SLG films from hydrocarbon sources grown on different transition metal substrates namely, Iridium (Ir), Nickel (Ni), Palladium (Pd), Ru, Copper (Cu), etc., [62, 66-68]. Figure 7 (a) displays a basic CVD experimental setup generally employed to obtain SLG using Cu or Ni as a catalyst [69]. The CVD setup consists of a high-temperature tube furnace, a vacuum chamber with a vacuum and pressure controller which helps in controlling the growth conditions, and mass flow controllers (MFC) which control the flow of reactant gases and carbon sources. The metal substrates are generally selected based on the etching ability, grain size, cost, and recognition by the semiconductor industry, etc. Polycrystalline Cu and Ni metal substrates are drawing a keen interest on account of their inexpensive, wide availability, and feasibility for mass production of graphene. The CVD process can be elucidated in a simple way, wherein high-quality graphene is grown via the thermal decomposition of the hydrocarbon precursors at high temperatures catalyzed by transition metal substrates followed by nucleation of graphene islands on the substrates and finally the growth of graphene films having distinct lattice orientations as shown in Figure 7 (b-d) [70]. One of the biggest concerns of this process is the difficulties in exfoliating the graphene from the substrate and this can dramatically hamper the structure and properties of graphene. This approach is quite expensive which may be attributed to the utilization of high-energy and, metal substrates which need to be usually renewed during each preparation method [71].

Figure 7: (a) Schematic representation of basic CVD experimental set up used in graphene synthesis [69]. Copyright 2013. Adapted from Intech Open. (b-d) Illustration of the three key

steps of graphene synthesis using CVD method [70]. Copyright 2011. Reproduced with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

In the CVD method, the substrate is subjected to exposure to one or more precursors that react and disintegrate on the surface of the substrate to gradually grow graphene. Nowadays, Cu foils or any other metal substrates can be used on which homogeneous graphene films can be grown, showing its paramount potential for variegated commercial applications [72-75]. The scaled-up CVD approach can overcome vital problems for the homogeneous growth of graphene i.e., grain size, doping, stacking orders, and the number of layers that are commonly witnessed in other approaches of graphene synthesis. CVD also bestows the flexibility for the growth of graphene with several substrates and precursors. For example, substrates can be Cu [73], Pt [76], Ni [77], etc. and precursors chosen can be solid, liquid, and gas. There are various CVD growth approaches namely low-pressure CVD (LP-CVD), atmospheric pressure CVD (AP-CVD) [78], roll-to-roll CVD [79], hot filament CVD (HF-CVD) [80], and plasma-enhanced CVD (PECVD) [81] etc. In fact, there is a requirement to transfer the graphene from the Cu substrate to other substrates via popular approaches like solution-etching, electrical bubbling, etc., which are useful for achieving mass production of graphene [79]. It has been evidenced that the graphene obtained from the CVD approach possesses excellent electron mobility of $\approx 7350 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with enhanced device properties [71].

Graphene produced by the PECVD method [82, 83] relies on several plasma sources including radiofrequency (RF), microwave (MW) frequency, and direct current arc discharge [84-87]. In this process, the deposition of the graphene can be achieved using reactive species formed in the plasma even at low temperatures and low pressure. The Cu and Ni substrates are commonly used for PECVD graphene growth and in addition, several other metal substrates can also be used [84, 88]. Although it is a promising method, yet it requires optimization or controlling the thickness of the graphene layers and, ensuring its feasibility for mass production. The primary factors that regulate a CVD process are precursor, pressure, growth time, temperature, and catalyst. In a true sense, there are mainly two routes for the growth of graphene via the CVD process. In route I, the basic steps involved are: (A) adsorption and degradation of starting materials (B) diffusion and dissolution of different carbon materials (C) separation of carbon-based materials which are already dissolved (D) nucleation and growth of graphene. On the other hand, route II involves steps (A) and (D) of the route I [75]. Optimizing the prime factors to manipulate the entire CVD approach will result in the fabrication of graphene with

coveted properties like controlled thickness, doping, grain size, hybridization with any other 2D materials, and so on. From this approach, it is possible to produce doped graphene [89], SLG [90], bilayer graphene [91], and large single crystals of graphene of desired structure [92].

2.1.5 Chemically and Thermally Synthesized Graphene

The wet chemical synthesis of graphene is another important and unique route to produce a large quantity of colloidal dispersion of graphene and chemically modified graphene at low temperatures. This synthesis approach is scalable and can be extended to facilitate functionalization, solution processing, and bulk production of graphene [10]. Traditionally, graphene has been chemically synthesized mainly using graphene oxide (GO) which is often produced by the oxidization of graphite with the help of strong oxidizing agents (namely sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), nitric acid (HNO_3), potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$), potassium chlorate ($KClO_3$) and sodium chlorite ($NaClO_2$)). Moreover, the reduction of GO using chemical (using reducing agents) and thermal reduction (physical) methods leads to graphene formation with a partially restored sp^2 carbon network [93, 94]. In the chemical reduction of GO, different varieties of reducing agents like hydrazine monohydrate [95], hydroquinone [96], and sodium borohydride [97], have been exploited for obtaining the reduced graphene oxide (RGO). However, RGO cannot be regarded as pristine graphene as it comprises a small amount of oxygen (oxygen-containing functional groups). Moreover, the major limitations of this method are the usage of hazardous and expensive chemicals, complex processes, and structural defects (porosity) in the final product. Yet, the chemical reduction of GO is a favorable route of graphene synthesis by virtue of its high yield and large-scale application. Nowadays, researchers are prompted to use eco-friendly, low cost and highly effective reducing agents including vitamin C [98], reducing sugars [99], and amino acid [100], as a substitute for these hazardous and expensive chemicals. The limited expulsion of the oxygen-bearing functional groups and the re-establishment of conjugation during reduction of GO, renders RGO with improved electrical conductivity. Besides, these oxygen-bearing functional groups of GO and RGO help in the formation of stable dispersion and easy functionalization when incorporated in aqueous organic solvents thereby providing bounteous opportunities for the processing of functionalized graphene [52, 101].

Thermal reduction of GO is an economical, simpler, and safer alternative to other techniques. In the thermal reduction of GO, the dry GO powder is heated rapidly under distinct atmospheric conditions like ammonia (NH_3), nitrogen (N_2), hydrogen (H_2), ultra-high vacuum

(UHV) [102, 103], flashlight [104], and MW-assisted reduction [105] to exfoliate its structure. Further, the dry GO powder is charged in a quartz crucible and subjected to thermal shocks at elevated temperatures (greater than 1000°C) at high heating rates such as 2000°C/min to form thermally reduced GO (TRGO) [106, 107]. The reason for the rapid heating of GO powder is that it causes the evolution of different gas molecules (carbon monoxide (CO) or carbon dioxide (CO₂)), which increases the internal pressure and exfoliates the graphene sheets apart [106]. The advantage of this method is that it is possible to obtain SLG and MLG sheets in large quantities whereas the disadvantage is that the evolution of CO₂ gas causes defects in the graphene structure and hence the approach is said to be a non-promising one [108]. Due to the involvement of thermal reduction, about 30% of GO mass is decomposed or lost, and this leads to lattice defects all over the sheets [109]. Thus, this type of imperfect graphene sheet exhibits electrical conductivity of $\approx 10\text{-}23$ S/cm which is very low when compared to the perfect graphene, displaying a weak influence on the reduction and the recovery of its electronic structure.

Thus, from all the synthesis methods of graphene discussed above, it can be emphasized that each method has its own strengths and weaknesses, and hence, it is vital to design new methods in order to obtain supreme quality graphene in bulk quantity [110]. In a true sense, it can be stated that the top-down approach of graphene synthesis is comparatively more beneficial than the bottom-up approach, attributed to its easy implementation, high yield, and flexibility in solution-based processability. On the contrary, the bottom-up approach initiates very less defects on the surface of graphene but it is not widely appreciated due to the complexity involved in the approach, the use of expensive metal substrates, and limitations in scaling up.

2.2 Synthesis Methods of Graphene Oxide and Reduced Graphene Oxide

2.2.1 Graphene Oxide: An Overview of Structure, and Surface Chemistry

GO is basically, a graphene layer decorated with oxygen functionalities namely hydroxyl (-OH), alkoxy (C-O-C), carbonyl (-C=O-) groups, carboxyl (-COOH), epoxy, diols, etc. In a simple way, GO can be synthesized through the oxidation of pure graphite. GO, regarded as the most propitious derivative of functionalized graphene, comprises sp² and sp³ hybridized carbon atoms forming a 2D hexagonal network with oxygen-bearing functional groups including carbonyl, carboxyl, lactone, phenol, and quinone, etc. attached to its edges and its top while hydroxyl and epoxy groups at the bottom basal planes [111-114]. The availability of oxygen-

bearing functional groups renders GO highly hydrophilic which makes it easily exfoliate into single-layer sheets and forming stable dispersions in water [115, 116]. Moreover, the oxygen-bearing functional groups in GO has a strong effect on its electrical, electronic, electrochemical, and mechanical properties, etc. Moreover, the functional groups in GO own high density that is beneficial in solution processing and also serves as an anchoring site for GO modification via the covalent or non-covalent functionalization wherein several electroactive species can be paralyzed on its surface, for instance; appropriate functional groups namely terminal amides and amines, biomolecules (amino acids, proteins, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, lipids, peptides) etc. can be affixed to the oxygen-bearing functional groups exist at the GO surfaces and edges [117-122].

Surface functionalization of GO ameliorates the solution processability and dispersion of GO in organic solvents and polymer matrices and, tailors the structural and functional characteristics of the nanosheets opening windows for numerous applications in various technological sectors. The homogeneous dispersion of GO sheets is mainly promoted by $\pi - \pi$, electrostatic forces, and Van der Waals interaction occurring with the polymeric matrices and organic solvents [15, 31, 123-127]. Literature reports evidence that it is easy to uniformly disperse GO nanoplatelets in DMF without any chemical functionalization [128, 129]. Paredes et. al. [52] studied the behaviour of GO dispersion in different organic solvents (Figure 8). To date, numerous solvents have been identified that can exfoliate GO into discrete sheets using ultrasonication, which forms long-term stable dispersion in comparison to GO dispersed in water. These reports evidence that the GO can be used for the synthesis of graphene-based polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) from solution processing methods [129, 130] or graphene-based hybrid materials [128], which have a bright future in commercial applications. The prepared stable GO dispersions can be coated on different substrates employing traditional methods like spraying, spin coating, or drop-casting for fabricating thin conductive films [131].

Figure 8: Photograph of GO dispersion in various solvents [52]. Copyright 2008. Reproduced with permission from The American Chemical Society.

GO finds many standalone applications, in spite of being used in graphene synthesis. The hybrid electronic structure of GO possessing conducting π and σ states from respective sp^2 and sp^3 carbon domains makes its properties highly remarkable [132]. In addition, GO reveals extremely high specific surface area along with a high aspect ratio. Nevertheless, GO that contains a huge domain of hybridized carbon atoms affixed with oxygenated functional groups are good insulators having a high sheet resistance ($>10^{12} \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$ or greater) [133]. It is possible to lower the sheet resistance of GO via reduction methods for transforming it from an insulator to a semiconductor (or semi-metallic materials) like graphene [134]. Yet, GO is devoid of charge carriers with a unique photostimulated nature and other condensed matter phenomena. The electronic properties of GO sheets are mainly gauged using electrical conductivity, which strongly relies upon the GO's atomic and chemical structure. In the reduction of GO, the oxygen content largely decreases by virtue of the expulsion of functional groups and thus, the electrical conductivity increases as a result of the sp^2 carbon domain. The electrical conductivity of GO is also reliant upon the temperature and reduction time, i.e., the conductivity increases proportionally with enhanced temperature and reduction time [93].

Besides the intriguing electronic properties of GO, it also displays excellent optical characteristics. The single-layered GO owing to its atomically thin structure owns remarkable optical transmittance and transparency in the visible regime [128]. On the other hand, it is feasible to tailor the optical transmittance of GO films by either altering their thickness or by regulating the order of reduction [135]. The π - π^* transitions in GO represent optical absorption

which can be identified from the presence of an absorption peak ranging between 225 - 275 nm (or 4.5-5.5 eV). In the reduction of GO, the optical absorption strength increases whilst there is a shift in the Plasmon peak to ~270 nm indicating an enhancement in structural ordering as well as π -electron concentration [136]. In addition, there are a lot of proofs that show that the GO is luminescent on continuous exposure to wave irradiation [137], wherein the visible-light excitation reveals a broad photo-luminescence (PL) spectrum ranging from visible light to near-infrared (IR) emission [138], whereas the ultra-violet (UV) excitation gives rise to blue emission [139]. These interesting optical properties of GO allow it to be used for lighting-based applications including light-emitting diodes (LEDs) [140], bio-imaging [138], fluorescence tags, etc., [141]. Furthermore, GO is said to hold non-linear optical (NLO) properties as well as distinct ultrafast optical dynamics, serving suitable material for electro-optic devices. Therefore, GO has been used as a chemically adapted material for optical applications based on its NLO, fluorescence, and fluorescence quenching properties [142, 143].

In recent decades, plenty of studies have been focused on tuning the mechanical properties of GO. The presence of different types of functional groups in the GO mainly aids in tuning its mechanical properties. Dikin et al. [113] described the mechanical characteristics of micrometre (μm) thick GO paper prepared from the slow vaporization of GO dispersion. The Young's modulus of ~ 30 GPa and intrinsic strength of ~ 130 MPa were reported for the GO sheet. Numerous research groups started to investigate the mechanical attributes of GO sheets by varying the water content and sample thickness [144, 145]. The mechanical attributes of GO papers were enhanced by chemical cross-linking of single sheets by introducing divalent ions and poly(ethylene glycol) [146, 147]. In addition, the mechanical properties of GO sheets are mostly subject to the particle size of GO and can further be tailored by composite formation or doping [148, 149].

In the current scenario, the GO has grabbed a major subject of research among the graphene materials owing to its ease in synthesis, solution processability, easy accessibility, and unique properties, making it an appealing material for fundamental research and also, a potential candidate for commercial high-end applications. The ability of GO to be exfoliated as a single layer sheet in water, to be cast as films, and to be reduced further back into graphene, bestows GO for various applications like in electrical energy storage [130, 150], photocatalysis [151], field-effect transistors [152], transparent conducting films [153], PNCs [154], drug delivery [155], solid-state gas sensors [156], as a component in paper like material [113, 147]. Moreover, standalone GO films have been used as ion conductors [157], nano-filtration

membranes [158], and hydrogen storage applications [159]. There has also been humongous literature that has reported the usefulness of GO for biomedical applications because of its biocompatible nature [160].

2.2.2 Synthesis Approaches of Graphene Oxide

The most traditional methods for producing GO include the chemical exfoliation of graphite assisted by highly oxidizing agents and concentrated acids followed by ultrasonication (Figure 9) [161]. The oxidation of graphite causes the intercalation of oxygen-bearing functional groups and thus, increases the interlayer spacing of GO sheets [162]. In 1859, Brodie accomplished pioneering work on the production of GO [163]. The synthesis protocol included mixing one equal weight of graphite flakes with about three equal weights of KClO_3 and then treating this mixture with fuming HNO_3 for four days at 60°C . After forty years (i.e., in 1898), Brodie's synthesis method of GO was further improvised by Staudenmaier. In this method, the Staudenmaier replaced about two-thirds of fumed HNO_3 with that of conc. H_2SO_4 and added KClO_3 in several segments [164]. This slight alteration in Brodie's method by Staudenmaier simplified the synthesis method by enabling the possibility of carrying out the overall reaction in a lone vessel. But the main disadvantage is that this reaction takes four long days to complete. Both the synthesis methods of GO are time-consuming and, hazardous owing to the inception of chlorine dioxide (ClO_2) gas that decomposes into chlorine and oxygen [163, 164]. Hofmann et. al. in the year 1937, prepared GO by utilizing concentrated H_2SO_4 and Conc. HNO_3 and KClO_3 via oxidization of graphite [165-167]. The KClO_3 plays the role of a strong oxidizing agent, thereby oxidizing the graphite in an acid solution and acting as a reactive species since it is an in-situ dioxygen source.

Figure 9: Representation of GO synthesis [161]. Copyright 2019. Adapted from MDPI.

Several attempts have been made to synthesize GO for a variety of applications via the Hofmann method [168, 169]. Later, Hummers and Offeman, in 1958, modified the process by utilizing a mixture containing H_2SO_4 , KMnO_4 , and sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) [170, 171]. Their synthesis protocol involved harsh treatment of one equal weight of graphite powders to undergo oxidation below 35°C with the help of Conc. H_2SO_4 solution containing 0.5 equal weights of NaNO_3 and three equal weights of KMnO_4 . It can imply that the Brodie, Staudenmaier, Hoffmann, and Hummers methods are still regarded as the four vital methods to synthesize GO from graphite powder. Of which, the best suitable approach for mass-scale production of GO includes the chemical exfoliation of graphite via the Hummers method. The three main advantages of the Hummers method are: Firstly, the reaction takes only a few hours to complete, and that too with high efficiency. Secondly, KMnO_4 has been used instead of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in order to ensure a safe reaction and also, to shun the release of explosive gases such as ClO_2 . Thirdly, the NaNO_3 that replaces fuming Conc. HNO_3 evades the acid fog formation. The two major downsides of the Hummers method are: (i) the evolution of toxic gases namely nitrogen dioxide (or NO_2) and dinitrogen tetroxide (or N_2O_4) from the oxidation process and (ii) the difficulty involved in the removal of residual Na^+ and Na_3^- ions from the wastewater produced from the synthesis method and purification of GO [172].

Marcano et. al. [173] in the year 2010 invented an improved approach to synthesizing GO via the Hummers method. In this process, the amount of KMnO_4 was increased two times greater than the amount used in Hummer's reaction. The next change involved in this process was the preparation of a solution containing a mixture with a ratio of one part of phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) to nine parts of H_2SO_4 in order to stimulate the intercalation property of H_2SO_4 further. This improvised synthesis method of Hummer's was coined as an improved Hummer method. The changes adopted in this improved Hummers method led to better graphite oxidation, improved total reaction yield, and reduced release of toxic gases owing to the elimination of NaNO_3 and incorporation of H_3PO_4 in the reaction process. All four aforementioned synthesis methods clearly reveal that the oxidation reaction is highly dependent upon the type of graphite source used, the type of oxidizing agents used, and the reaction time. Also, the improved Hummers method has shown more efficiency than that of the original Hummers method and less under-oxidized material was produced via the improved Hummers method [173].

2.2.3 Chemical Reduction of Graphene Oxide

In the reduction process of GO, the obtained GO partially reverts to its original state and thus leads to improved properties mainly electrical conductivity. This reduction process is a vital step involved in ameliorating or fine-tuning the GO properties and potentially modifying its structure [174-177]. Chemical reduction of GO (CRGO) is an extraordinary approach to fabricate bulk quantities of graphene and RGO simply and effectively [94, 165, 178]. Generally, in this approach, GO is dipped into a chosen reducing agent over a certain period and for a specific temperature range, and thus, the exorbitant functional groups (namely; -COOH and -OH) are removed essentially [176, 178]. Initially, this process is accompanied by ultrasonication of GO in water, to form a uniform dispersion with GO readily soluble in water. Then, the GO was reduced by the appropriate chemical process and the RGO prepared mimics the graphene structure, despite containing structural defects, residual oxygen, and other heteroatoms. In the reduction process, there is the elimination of nearly all the oxygen-bearing functional groups and also there is the partial restoration of π -electron conjugation inside the aromatic graphite system. Lastly, there is the precipitation of RGO from the reaction media owing to the partially restored graphite domains of the chemically transformed graphene sheets possessing enhanced π -stacking interactions as well as improved hydrophobicity. The RGO properties are almost analogous to graphene when fabricated via chemical, thermal, electrochemical, MW, or photo-reduction pathways. Among them, the chemical reduction of GO is the most appreciated approach for synthesizing chemically converted RGO (CRGO). The diverse range of organic and inorganic reducing agents used, including hydrazine hydrate, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, amino acids, urea, strong alkaline solutions, pyrrole, glucose, phenylhydrazine, sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), hydroxylamine, for producing CRGO [165]. This chemical reduction process does not mandate the need for equipment or environments as required in thermal reduction processes such as thermal annealing treatment, making this process cheaper and simpler for bulk manufacturing of graphene when compared to the thermal reduction process.

The GO reduction using hydrazine was prepared well – before the graphene discovery [174]. Stankovich et al. were the first to report the use of hydrazine for synthesizing chemically derived graphene. These reports showed the facile route for large-scale graphene production [115, 124]. Thus, hydrazine has been recognized as the best chemical reagent for GO reduction. The hydrazine derivatives such as hydrazine hydrate and dimethyl hydrazine can help in the reduction of GO by mixing them with an aqueous GO dispersion and as a result, agglomeration

of graphene nanosheets were obtained owing to the improved hydrophobic characteristics of the mixer. On drying, the obtained product was an electrically conducting black powder having a C/O ratio of ~ 10 [115]. With hydrazine reduction, the highest conductivity of RGO film achieved so far is 99.6 S/cm and C/O ~ 12.5 [98]. Several studies have been performed to promote the exertion of graphene, via the GO reduction in the colloidal form in the water itself by the addition of soluble polymers as surfactants or ammonia (NH_3) for modifying the RGO sheet's charge state. The graphene sheets that are dispersed in the colloidal solutions may be utilized for assembling macrostructures via common filtration-type solution processes [179].

Fan et. al. [180] delineated that the strong alkali solutions (potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), etc.) can be used with the exfoliated graphite oxide at mild temperatures ($50 - 90^\circ\text{C}$) to undergo rapid deoxygenation and result in stable graphene aqueous suspensions. Shin et al. [181] carried out the reduction of graphite oxide with different NaBH_4 loadings, and the results showed different reduction orders that were well-corroborated with the XRD patterns. After reduction, it was witnessed that their electrical properties improved, overall. Fernandez-Merino et al. [98] exhibited GO reduction using ascorbic acid (otherwise; vitamin C (VC)) with a C/O ratio of ~ 12.5 and electrical conductivity to that of 77S/cm, which was similar to the experiment performed with hydrazine. The merits of VC include a non-toxic nature than hydrazine and excellent chemical stability with water than NaBH_4 . Additionally, there is no aggregation of RGO sheets in colloidal form during the reduction process, which is witnessed with the use of hydrazine. Of late, Moon et al. [182] and Pei et. al. [183] introduced a new chemical reagent for the reduction of GO called hydroiodic acid (HI), wherein the two individual studies revealed a C/O ratio of ~ 15 and electrical conductivity of ~ 300 S/cm. These values seem greater when compared to a reduction of GO with other chemical reagents. Even at room temperature, HI reagent can be used for the reduction of GO in colloidal, film, or powder form, either in a solution or gas environment [175].

2.2.4 Thermal Reduction of Graphene Oxide

Highly efficient RGO powders can also be obtained from the thermal reduction process of GO. Generally, in this process, the reduction of GO occurs under elevated temperatures ($> 1000^\circ\text{C}$), where the oxygen functionalities as well as the water get burnt and evaporated. The thermal reduction process is an efficient one, but it is not feasible for GO in film form [177, 184, 185]. Thermal reduction of GO (TRGO) is a vital processing approach for fabricating diverse kinds of graphene-derived materials. The reduction of GO via heating is termed thermal

reduction by annealing or in short, thermal annealing reduction. Besides annealing temperature, the annealing atmosphere (such as vacuum, inert, or reducing atmosphere) is also instrumental in GO reduction [186, 187]. GO reduction by heating involves multi-step induction of thermal energy to eliminate intercalated water molecules and oxygen-bearing functional groups ($-OH$, $-COOH$, epoxy, etc.). As discussed earlier, the chemical reduction process of discrete GO sheets in the solution form was conducted with the help of a strong chemical base [188]. In contrast, the thermal reduction process involves heating graphite oxide rapidly at elevated temperatures, followed by exfoliation to form porous carbon materials and then, there is a transformation into graphene having oxygen-bearing functional groups in feeble quantity. When the graphite oxide is heated rapidly, there is a sudden evolution of CO or CO_2 gas from amidst the gaps of graphene sheets, resulting in its exfoliation. Additionally, the rapid heating causes the decomposition of oxygen functionalities clinging to the carbon plane into gaseous form and thus, enormous pressure is created in between the piled-up carbon layers. Based on the state equation, it was observed that $300^\circ C$ annealing temperature generates 40 MPa, whereas $1000^\circ C$ generates a pressure of 130 MPa. Using the Haymaker constant, it has been evaluated that a feeble pressure of ~ 2.5 MPa is ample to cleave the two piled-up GO platelets [106].

The rapid heating at high temperatures, therefore, aids in exfoliating graphite oxide and, helps in removing the oxygen-bearing functional groups by decomposition. This dual effect facilitates the heat expansion of graphite oxide, which was found to be a satisfactory approach for yielding graphene in bulk amounts. On the contrary, this strategy yields only small-sized and wrinkled forms of graphene sheets due to the distortion of the carbon plane wherein decomposition of oxygen-bearing functional groups evades the carbon atoms in the carbon plane, and thus, the graphene sheet is split into tiny pieces [109]. In this type of thermal treatment, the exfoliation creates structural defects and to a notable extent, damage in graphene sheets due to the evolution of CO_2 gasses. At the time of exfoliation, about 30% of the mass loss of graphite oxide occurs and ultimately, leaves lattice defects over the entire graphene sheet [109]. Unfortunately, these structural defects and damages in graphene sheets largely affect its electronic properties, which may be attributed to the reduction in ballistic transport path length and, due to the incorporation of scattering centers. The electrical conductivity of the obtained graphene sheets from this process was in the range of 10 – 23 S/cm; which was comparatively lower than the pure graphene, implying the effect of reduction and weak recovery of the electronic structure of the carbon plane [109].

To overcome the above drawbacks, the best-substituted approach is the exfoliation of graphite oxide in liquid media that permits the graphene sheets to exfoliate in huge lateral sizes [189, 190]. The reduction process, in such a case, can be conducted after the assemblage of macroscopic materials, for instance into film or powder forms, via annealing in reducing or inert atmospheres. The heating temperature strongly influences the extent of oxygen removal from the surface of GO, which in turn affects the GO reduction [109]. Li et. al. [187] closely observed the structural changes in GO with respect to annealing temperature and concluded that there is a requisite of high temperature for achieving better GO reduction. Schniepp et. al. [109] observed the connection between the heating temperature and the C/O ratio. They investigated the C/O ratio at heating temperature $< 500^{\circ}\text{C}$ to be < 7 while the C/O ratio increased to > 13 at the heating temperature of 750°C . Eliminating the oxygen-bearing functional groups in the GO reduction process generally helps to maximize the conductivity. Wang et. al. elucidated that the electrical conductivity of RGO film was 49, 93, 383, and 450 S/cm at annealing temperatures of 550, 700, 900, and 1100°C , respectively. The authors concluded that the electrical conductivity of RGO films increases with annealing temperature [36].

The annealing atmosphere also greatly affects the thermal annealing reduction process. Becerril et. al. [186] performed thermal annealing reduction of GO films at 1000°C and reported that a vacuum atmosphere in the range $< 10^{-5}$ Torr served as the prime factor for the best GO recovery. In the absence of a good-quality vacuum atmosphere, the films might be rapidly lost by reacting with residual oxygen formed within the system. In such a case, a reducing gas like hydrogen (H_2) may be supplied to consume the residual oxygen present in the atmosphere. H_2 is found to have an excellent reducing ability at high temperatures and thus, the GO reduction can be conducted at appreciably low temperatures in the presence of H_2 atmosphere. Wu et. al. [107] prepared graphene from the exfoliation of graphite oxide by the hydrogen arc discharge exfoliation approach. The reduction of GO was achieved at the temperature of 450°C within 2 hrs of annealing in an Argon (Ar)/ H_2 atmosphere with a 1:1 ratio of the gas mixture. This resulted in RGO having a C/O ratio of 14.9 and an electrical conductivity of 1×10^3 S/cm. Another report emphasized that the heat-treating GO in a low-pressure gas atmosphere (2 Torr, 10% NH_3/Ar) can simultaneously result in nitrogen (N_2) doping and reduction of GO [187].

3. Processing Methods of Graphene Based Polymer Nanocomposites

Graphene based polymer nanocomposites (GPNCs) have attracted significant attention owing to their tremendous potential for a plethora of applications [191]. For this purpose, GO,

RGO, or TRGO have been commonly utilized as fillers into the polymer matrix to obtain GPNCs mainly due to the cost-effectiveness and large-scale production of GO and RGO. In recent years, humongous literature reports have been witnessed in which graphene or graphene-based reinforcements have been incorporated into various polymer matrices to produce GPNCs, which are utilized for various commercial applications including lithium-ion batteries [192-194], solar cells [195, 196], water purification [197, 198], sensors [199, 200], supercapacitors [201-203], tissue engineering [204, 205], drug delivery [206-208], and electrochemical applications [209, 210]. The effect of graphene nanofiller on the characteristics of diverse polymer matrices namely polycarbonate (PC), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), polyaniline (PANI), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), Nafion (N), polystyrene (PS), polyimide (PI), polyurethane (PU), etc., has been investigated wherein the obtained GPNCs behold variety of prospective applications [33, 142]. The multifunctional features of the GPNCs may be pertaining to the superiorly high aspect ratio, strength, and high surface area of graphene. However, the undesirable issue witnessed in designing GPNCs is the poor dispersion of single graphene sheets in the polymer matrix. The efficiency of the GPNCs can be enhanced remarkably if graphene and its derivatives can be dispersed uniformly in the polymer matrix. The uniform dispersion of graphene and GO-based fillers in the polymer system warrants a maximum surface area that affects the nearby polymer chains thereby leading to enhancement in the polymer properties. Additionally, the final properties of the PNCs are also governed by the nature of the interfacial bonding interactions occurring between the polymer matrices and the nanofiller [130, 191]. The limiting factors that inhibit strong interfacial interactions are weak Van der Waals forces, $\pi - \pi$, and hydrophobic interactions, posed by the graphene fillers [211]. To strengthen the interactions of graphene with a diverse range of polymer matrices and to increase its reinforcing effect, one of the effective ways is the functionalization of graphene using genuine chemical groups at the edges and surfaces of graphene. The inference drawn is that the GO and other derivatives of graphene as a filler material have been regarded as potential reinforcing agents. The surface functionalization of the graphene and its derivatives yields a rich amount of oxygen-bearing groups on the surfaces, facilitating a wide range of opportunities for strong interfacial interactions with the polymer matrices via covalent bonding, hydrogen bonding, and polar and columbic interactions.

The properties of GPNCs are solely reliant on the processing routes as well as processing conditions. In the recent scenario, there have been diverse ranges of processing routes described in the literature for integrating graphene and its derivatives-based fillers into numerous

polymeric matrices [212, 213]. Despite the significant interfacial interaction between the graphene nanofiller and the polymeric matrices, the extent of dispersion of graphene-based filler in polymer matrices and the nature of the interfacial interaction between the filler and the polymer matrix is instrumental in deciding the quality of the GPNCs. Based on applications of GPNCs, the selection of different types of polymer matrices and graphene-based filler types at various compositions can be carried out. Therefore, numerous approaches have been adopted in order to obtain a uniform dispersion of graphene filler in polymer matrices. Among the several available processing methods of GPNCs, there are five major techniques including solution processing, in situ polymerization, melt processing, latex mixing, and electro-polymerization. Almost every polymer composite as well as PNCs can be prepared via one or more of these aforementioned techniques. Yet, the GPNCs can be easily processed via these techniques [191]. The salient features of the solution processing melt processing and in situ polymerization techniques are discussed below.

3.1 Solution Blending Method

Solution blending (otherwise known as solution processing or colloidal processing) has been a well-established and widely reported method of fabricating GPNCs, attributed to the easy processability of graphene-based fillers in water as well as in organic solvents [214, 215]. In this method, the graphene-based fillers (including GO, RGO, TRGO, etc.) are dispersed in a suitable solvent and the selected polymer (or polymer blends) dissolved in the same miscible solvent as the filler is mixed to form a colloidal dispersion, wherein the homogeneous dispersion of filler into the polymer/solvent is carried out by simple stirring or by shear mixing or agitation or ultrasonication [216, 217]. For proper homogeneous dispersion of graphene-based fillers that hold poor solubility in most organic solvents, ultrasonication is the best method [53]. On the contrary, exposing these fillers for a long time to ultrasonication at high power can develop defective graphene and ultimately, deteriorates the composites properties, as a whole [32]. Thus, functionalization is an effective way to enhance the dispersion degree of graphene in organic solvents. GO derivatives and functionalized graphene disperse readily in organic solvents viz. water, chloroform, acetone, THF, toluene, DMF, etc. [33]. The key factor to achieve homogeneous dispersion is the compatibility of solvents with the polymers and the nanofillers. Once the homogeneous dispersion of filler/polymer/solvent is ready, the GPNCs film are commonly obtained by evaporation, in order to eliminate the entire solvent [218]. Also, there are several other procedures to obtain the GPNCs from the filler/polymer/solvent dispersion such as precipitation, lyophilization, filtration, and so forth [219-221]. Both

thermosetting and thermoplastic PNCs can be produced with the help of this processing technique. The major challenges posed by this method is in reducing the residual solvents and, in achieving a good degree of dispersion of fillers in viscous polymer solution [222]. It has been regarded that the solution processing method aids in better dispersion of particles, although slow solvent evaporation mostly causes re-aggregation of particles. In particular, this method is very useful in dispersing SLG into a polymer matrix. The solution blending approach is far superior to the melt processing method because it yields better particle dispersion. Moreover, the requirement for huge quantities of organic solvents and the related environmental pollution issues hampers the mass production of GPNCs via this technique [223]. This reason impedes the popularity of this approach particularly for industrial applications, in comparison to the melt processing method [224].

3.2 Melt Blending Method

Melt blending (or otherwise melt processing, melt compounding, or melt mixing) is another popular, cost-effective, and multifaceted approach of nanocomposite fabrication, best suited for synthesizing thermoplastic PNCs [225-227]. This method is generally devoid of solvents, in which dried polymer powders are first melted at elevated temperatures, and graphene-based fillers are integrated with the polymer melt under high shear conditions. Among others, this method is more economically viable, eco-friendly, and compatible with the most current industrial settings that bestow large scale production of GPNCs for commercial applications [228, 229]. Generally, traditional equipment like injection moulding, twin-roller mill, internal mixer, tri-roller mill and twin extruder is used for the mechanical mixing of thermoplastic polymer melts with graphene-based fillers at high temperatures [228, 230-235]. The high shear forces in the extruder make the graphene-based fillers intercalate within the polymeric materials. However, the uniform mixing of polymer-graphene-based fillers depends on the extent of polymer degradation at high temperatures [236]. Thus, there is a need to tailor or regulate several blending and moulding parameters such as shear stress, temperature, screw – speed, and residence time to optimize the properties of the GPNCs obtained from this approach [236]. On the other side, melt blending has several disadvantages. One of the drawbacks of this method is that it does not apply to polymer matrices or filler materials that are susceptible to thermal degradation [224]. Another challenge is the non-uniform or heterogeneous dispersion of graphene-based materials which results from the high viscosity of graphene-based polymer dispersions [32, 209, 237]. In addition, the usage of high mechanical stress and temperatures during mixing in the extruder leads to defects and breaking of graphene flakes (buckling,

rolling, shortening), stability, and poor conductivity of the resulting composites owing to the reduced aspect ratio of graphene sheets are also drawbacks of this method. Moreover, the low density of graphene in solid form imposes difficulty feeding onto the extruder leading to poor dispersion degree as compared with solution processing method or in situ polymerization [224]. Notably, the melt mixing method can only be recommended for fabricating graphene in the form of dried powder (such as the TRGO), owing to the thermal instability of chemically modified graphene.

3.3 In Situ Polymerization Method

In situ polymerization is one of the typical and effective synthesis approaches, in which the graphene fillers or GO-derived fillers get uniformly dispersed in the polymer matrix [213, 225, 238]. In this method, the homogeneous dispersion of graphene sheets is blended with monomer (or multiple monomer) and then, the polymerization reaction eventuates via proper control over the processing conditions like time and temperature. Notably, the in-situ polymerization technique is inappropriate when the polymerization happens at the graphene surface or amidst the graphene layers [239]. Thus, a high degree of filler exfoliation is feasible by controlling the polymerization reactions inside and outside of the graphene layers. Similar to the solution processing method, this processing method can also be used for producing thermoplastic and thermosetting PNCs. One of the advantages of this method is that it bestows excellent compatibility as well as strong interactions between the polymeric systems and graphene-based fillers, thereby promoting stress transfer. Moreover, this method facilitates strong covalent bonding between the graphene and the polymer matrix [236]. In this method, the intrinsic dispersion ability is comparatively higher than the other mixing approaches thereby promoting uniform and remarkable dispersion properties. Yet, the main drawback of this method is the enhanced viscosity of graphene/polymer dispersion with a higher degree of polymerization that hampers the ease in processability of the GPNCs [240]. Furthermore, this process in many cases mandates the use of solvents and thus, solvent removal becomes a crucial affair that is analogous to the solution processing approach. This method is least suitable for natural polymers, as it demands the use of monomers and a huge quantity of reagents to carry out the polymerization reaction [238, 241, 242].

4. Electromagnetic Interference Shielding: Definition, Key Parameters, and Shielding Mechanisms

The advent of the recent 5G/6G era has led to the rapid technological growth and proliferation of mobile electronic devices. With the increasing demands for smart, compact and highly integrated wireless communication devices in the military, defence, aerospace and other consumer and commercial industries have resulted in a tremendous increase in electromagnetic (EM) pollution [243, 244]. These EM pollutions are particularly known as electromagnetic interference (EMI) which are undesirable outcome of modern engineering which continuously affects the durability and efficiency of electronic devices [243]. EMI can be driven by a variety of sources, such as electrostatic discharge, radio frequency interference, EM conduction or induction, thus affecting the performance of immensely sensitive devices such as cell phones, computers, Wi-Fi and bluetooth devices, laptops, etc., and adversely affecting their lifespan [244, 245]. Figure 10 displays the range of frequency bands of different electronic gadgets and devices that cause EM pollution in the surroundings [246]. Moreover, these high-frequency EMI radiations adversely affect the human body as well and their prolonged exposure can cause serious health hazards [247]. EM radiation also have adverse effects on the central nervous system of human beings causing sleep disorders, learning/memory impairments and physical abnormality [248]. Figure 11 demonstrates several detrimental effects of EM radiation on human health [249]. Thus, EM radiations are considered a global concern. Knowing the extent of the ill effects of EMI, it is of utmost necessity to effectively diminish the EM radiations. Thus, EMI shielding has been increasingly investigated in recent years as it is the method of preventing EM radiations from reaching a target by constructing shields through the fabrication and designing of various conductive or magnetic materials [245, 250]. However, the main requirements of modern electronic devices and communication technologies are lightweight shielding materials with high flexibility, reliability, low-cost, low thickness, corrosion resistance and higher EMI shielding performance [250].

Figure 10: Schematic illustration of different sources of EM pollutions in our surroundings [246]. Copyright 2019. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

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Figure 11: Detrimental effects of EM radiations on human health [249]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

In general, EM waves are made up of two primary components i.e. magnetic field (H) and electric field (E) that are perpendicular to one another: The plane that consists of both H and E components is at right angles to the propagation direction of EM waves [251-253]. The relative magnitude relies on the waveform and its source. The E to H ratio is called wave impedance. In accordance with the EM theory, E and H are high-frequency EM waves that signify independent radiation strengths; therefore, the shielding of any of them can lead to the vanishing of other [248]. EMI shielding is evaluated by mechanisms such as absorption, reflection and multiple reflections. Impedance mismatching causes the reflection of the incoming EM radiation on the shield's surface, and the interaction of the shield's electric or magnetic dipoles to absorb the un-reflected proportion of the incident EM radiations [248]. Therefore, a thorough understanding of the extrinsic and intrinsic characteristics of shielding material is essential.

Figure 12 indicates several essential properties required in a material to be used for EMI shielding. According to the need of design criteria and to achieve improved EMI shielding effectiveness (EMI SE), the shielding materials primary should have a combination of well-balanced properties such as high electrical conductivity, magnetic permeability, and dielectric constant along with proper structure and physical geometry [254-256].

Figure 12: Different properties affecting EMI shielding performance of a shielding material.

EMI shielding materials made of metal are the traditional choice and widely preferred due to their outstanding EMI SE, but the usage of conventional metal and metallic nanocomposites for EMI shielding is limited due to their drawbacks such as heavyweight, low corrosion resistance, rigidity, processing difficulties, high production costs, and increased reflection of EM wave, which contributes to more secondary EM pollution [244]. To overcome these drawbacks, a typical EMI shielding material possessing superior electrical conductivity, low density and enhanced thermal stability must be developed. Conducting polymer nanocomposites (CPNCs) have been demonstrated to show reduced secondary pollution thereby shielding the EM waves and showing enhanced absorption mechanism [257]. Compared to metal, these composites also have demonstrated advantageous aspects including light-weight, mechanical flexibility, easy processing, and resistance to corrosion in complex environments thereby making them attractive materials for EMI shielding [258, 259]. Thus, the

development of novel EMI shielding materials having properties like easy processing, corrosion resistance, lightweight etc., and that can be operated using absorption and reflection-based mechanisms have been the focus of significant research [260-263].

In general, three main mechanisms contributing to the overall effective attenuation of EMI shielding are reflection, absorption, and multiple reflections [264, 265]. The EM field is created by charged particles or electrons because of their movements which ultimately results in a transport of energy or radiation. Therefore, EMI is caused by the devices that transmit, distribute, or use electrical energy [265]. Typically, in an EMI shielding process, first, incident waves interact with the shield and get reflected partially due to mismatching of the impedance at the interface between air and shield [265]. This is followed by the absorption and dissipation of penetrated radiations by the shield or further reflection on the back surface of the shield as depicted in Figure 13(a) [265]. This process leads to a reduction of the incident power at the interface between air and shield which is called reflection loss (SE_R) and when the power is absorbed by the shield it is regarded as absorption loss (SE_A). Moreover, the penetrated waves can be reflected multiple times within the shield causing multiple reflection loss (SE_M) [265]. These EMI shielding mechanisms are reliant on the characteristics and properties of EM waves and shielding materials respectively [250, 261-265]. As demonstrated in Figure 13(b), the EMI shielding characteristics can be affected by the material properties such as thickness, conductivity, polarizability, and permeability [265]. Moreover, it should be noted that the hybridization of conducting and magnetic materials can give a synergistic response of magnetic and dielectric properties leading to more attenuation of EM waves [265, 266].

Figure 13: (a) EMI shielding mechanism and (b) Material properties that affects the EMI shielding performance [265]. Copyright 2023. Adapted from Elsevier.

4.1 Reflection

Reflection is the primary method of EMI shielding. The reflection minimizes EMI by causing an impedance mismatch at the air-shield interface. The material that reflects EMI by reflection mechanism, must carry free charge carriers i.e. electrons or holes that connect with the EM field radiation resulting in the reflection loss. Thus, superconductive materials work effectively as a shield via reflection of EM radiation, However, high conductivity is specifically not required to get good reflection efficiency [267]. Due to lower conductivity, some EM waves might penetrate through a shielding material [213]. Moreover, increasing the content of conductive nanofillers in the composites can also lead to increased EMI shielding efficiency. Usually, metals such as copper, nickel, silver, gold, etc., demonstrate high EMI shielding efficiency by reflection owing to the presence of a large number of free electrons that conduct electric current [267, 268]. The efficiency of reflection-dominant shielding materials relies on the permeability and conductivity of the shielding material and the frequency of the incident EM wave [262]. The magnitude of reflection is dependent on surface conductivity which can be formulated as [245]:

$$SE_R = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{16\omega\epsilon_0\mu_r} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where σ_T , represents total conductivity and μ_r is the relative permeability of the shielding material. Thus, reflection is directly proportional to the ratio of conductivity and permeability i.e. σ_T/μ_r [269, 270]. Further, with fixed σ_T and μ_r , SE_R diminishes with increment in frequency for a given material.

The reflection loss is not relevant to shield thickness and depends on the ratio of wave impedance to hindrance impedance while the barrier impedance can be expressed as a function of its conductivity, permeability, and frequency [213, 257]. Also, the reflection losses decline with rising frequency for the electric and magnetic fields. For electric fields the frequency of the interference and the shielding material are key factors in reflection loss. The reflection loss as a function of σ_r/μ_r ratio can be expressed as [271]:

$$R_e = 322 + 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sigma_r}{\mu_r f^3 r^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where σ_r is the relative conductivity of the shielding material in Siemens per meter, μ_r is the relative permeability in Henry per meter, f is the frequency of the interference and r denotes the distance from the source of the interference in meters. The reflection loss for magnetic fields also depends on the frequency of the interference and the shielding material which can be expressed as [271]:

$$R_m = 168 + 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sigma_r}{\mu_r f} \right] \quad (3)$$

For plane waves ($r > \lambda/2\pi$), the reflection loss is given by [271]:

$$R_e = 168 + 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sigma_r}{\mu_r f} \right] \quad (4)$$

For plane waves also, the reflection loss reduces as the frequency rises. Moreover, the reflection loss is equal to the reciprocal of the transmission coefficient of interfaces which indicates that it depends only on the impedance values of the medium [272].

4.2 Absorption

Absorption is a secondary mechanism of EMI shielding in which EM waves are dissipated and transformed into heat on the passage of EM waves across a medium. Absorption is thickness dependent mechanism in which shielding efficiency increases in the presence of electric or magnetic dipoles interacting with the EM radiations within the shield [267, 273]. The absorption increases with an increase in the thickness, polarizability and permeability of shielding materials as well as with an increase in the frequency of EM radiation [267].

Moreover, improved surface resistivity, smaller volume, and better absorption loss are predicted in a good shielding material. In traditional EMI shielding materials, the shielding of EM waves is reflection-dominated instead of absorption-dominated resulting in a non-negligible secondary pollution [274, 275]. In contrast, in the absorption-dominated EMI shielding materials, the secondary pollution can be reduced efficiently by initiative consumption resulting in a significantly improved shielding efficiency [275].

Absorption loss is determined by the barrier thickness as well as the skin depth while it is independent of plane wave, as well as electric or magnetic field, in contrast to reflection loss which is dependent on wave impedance. When an EM wave goes through a medium its amplitude diminishes exponentially owing to the generation of Ohmic loss generated by the current produced in the shield [276]. The attributes of the barrier material determine the skin depth in response. For example, steel offers better absorption than copper at the lower frequencies where its relative permeability is high. The absorption which increases exponentially with the square root of the frequency becomes the dominating factor at high frequencies. In this way, the magnitude of (SE_A) can be articulated by the following condition [245, 276-278]:

$$SE_A = -20 \frac{t}{\delta} \log_{10} e = 8.68 (t/\delta) = 8.68 t \left(\frac{\sigma_r \omega \mu_r}{2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Where 't' is the thickness of the shielding material and δ is the skin depth which can be expressed as [279]:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi f \mu_r \sigma_r}} \quad (6)$$

Where f is the frequency, μ_r represents the magnetic permeability and σ_r indicates the electrical conductivity. Skin depth decreases with an increase in σ_r , μ_r and f and therefore absorption loss also increases. The absorption loss can be further expressed as a function of the product $\sigma_r \mu_r$ which can be expressed as [271]:

$$SE_A = 3.34 t \sqrt{\sigma_r \mu_r f} \quad (7)$$

where, t indicates the thickness of the shielding material in inches, σ_r is the electrical conductivity, μ_r is the relative magnetic permeability and f is the frequency in Hertz. Thus, thickness is a critical factor in absorption-based shielding mechanisms thereby increasing EMI SE with an increase in shield thickness. Moreover, dielectric and magnetic loss dominates in the absorption mechanism [280]. Therefore, an appropriate absorbing material should demonstrate excellent conductivity, high permeability, and adequate thickness to accomplish the requisite number of skin depths even at low frequencies [281].

4.3 Multiple-Reflections

Multiple-reflection is the third mechanism of EMI shielding which is attributed to internal multiple reflection and scattering from phase interfaces of various surfaces and inhomogeneous shields [267]. Multiple reflection refers to the repeated reflections of EM waves at the front and back surfaces of the shield to the interior of the shield and also, the dissipation occurring at the phase interfaces within the shield [267]. Good multiple reflection ability can be observed in the materials that display high specific surface area [269]. In an ideal shielding material, these reflections are minimal and the wave is quickly absorbed, reducing its magnitude and minimizing the EMI. However, in practice, imperfections in the shielding material, such as defects or gaps can allow multiple reflections to occur, reducing the effectiveness of the shielding. To reduce the impact of multiple reflections, shielding materials are often designed to have low electrical and magnetic loss and high electrical conductivity. Therefore, creating porous, multilayer, hierarchical, and multiphase structures that can provide more impedance mismatching interfaces in the shields to effectively reduce the internal multiple reflections (SE_M) and scatterings thereby contributing significantly to enhanced wave attenuation [265, 282]. The attenuation corresponding to the SE_M can be mathematically expressed as [271, 272]:

$$SE_M = 20 \log_{10} (1 - e^{-2t/\delta}) = 20 \log_{10} (1 - 10^{-\frac{t}{\delta}}) \quad (8)$$

where δ is the skin depth relative to the thickness at which the incident field is attenuated to $1/e$ of its original value [280].

Multiple reflection losses strongly correlated with absorption and depends on the thickness of material. Therefore, crucial for porous structures and materials with specific geometries [248]. Apart from a rigid structure, a large surface area and significant void space offer greater opportunities for EM waves to scatter and undergo multiple reflections at active sites [213, 248]. Hollow porous structures provide unique properties that can meet the need to improve EMI performance, such as an extensive surface area, customizable internal structure, low density, and favourable permeability [283]. The SE_M can be disregarded when the shielding materials thickness is larger than or close to the value of δ or when SE_A is greater than 10 dB, since in thick shielding materials (high SE_A), the impact of the EM wave at the second interface is of low amplitude [265, 272].

4.4 Shielding Effectiveness

The term "shielding effectiveness" (SE) is an index commonly used to quantify the shielding performance of EMI shielding materials i.e. the degree of reduction in EM energy at

a certain frequency [248, 252]. When selecting shielding material, it is important to consider factors such as weight, because lighter materials are preferred for EM protection applications [213]. Shielding materials are usually made from conductive or magnetic materials like metals, conductive polymers, or metallic fibers and always the goal is to have the lowest possible thickness while still maintaining a strong and practical structure [213, 252, 283]. The effectiveness of EMI shielding materials depends on various factors, such as the frequency of the EM waves and the size and shape of the electronic device [270, 284]. The high value of EMI SE indicates that fewer EM waves are transmitted through the shielding material.

SE is measured as a function of frequency and expressed in decibels (dB). Furthermore, SE is referred as a logarithmic function of the ratio between intensities of power (P), E, and H fields before and after attenuation and can be given as:

$$SE \text{ (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_T}{P_I} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$SE \text{ (dB)} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_T}{E_I} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$SE \text{ (dB)} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{H_T}{H_I} \right) \quad (12)$$

where subscripts T and I indicate transmitted and incident EM waves, P_I , E_I , and H_I indicate the incident electric field, magnetic field and power densities while P_T , E_T , and H_T indicating the transmitted electric field, magnetic field and power densities respectively [213].

The total EMI SE (SE_T) is a sum of three losses, i.e. SE_R , SE_A , and SE_M , and can be referred as given below [213, 252]:

$$SE_T \text{ (dB)} = SE_R + SE_A + SE_M \quad (12)$$

When the EMI SE of a material is ≥ 10 dB, the multiple reflections can be disregarded and the effective absorption (A_{eff}), SE_R and SE_A can be given as [285]:

$$A_{eff} \text{ (dB)} = \frac{1-(T+R)}{(1-R)} \quad (13)$$

$$SE_R \text{ (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{1-R} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$SE_A \text{ (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{1-A_{eff}} \right) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1-R}{T} \right) \quad (15)$$

SE_T can therefore be expressed as:

$$SE_T \text{ (dB)} = SE_R + SE_A \quad (16)$$

Experimentally, EMI SE can be measured via a network analyzer which works on the principle of waveguide technology [286]. Network analysers are of two types; scalar network analyzer (SNA) and vector network analyzer (VNA). Compared to SNA, VNA is most often used to study complex signals that include complex permittivity and permeability. In addition,

it can be used to study the response amplitude of signals and phases of various signals [286]. Generally, a two-port VNA is used for EMI SE measurements (Figure 14) [287]. The block diagram of a VNA instrument is shown in Figure 15 [245]. Using VNA, the incident and transmitted waves are recorded and the complex scattering parameters i.e. S-parameters S_{11} (or S_{22}) and S_{12} (or S_{21}) are measured [245]. These S-parameters can be used to calculate power coefficients of reflection and transmission which eventually gives absorption as shown below [245];

$$R = \left| \frac{E_r}{E_i} \right|^2 = |S_{11}|^2 = |S_{22}|^2 \quad (17)$$

$$T = \left| \frac{E_t}{E_i} \right|^2 = |S_{12}|^2 = |S_{21}|^2 \quad (18)$$

$$A = (1-R-T) \quad (19)$$

The EMI SE in relation to shielding coefficients and S-parameters can be expressed as:

$$SE_T = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{|S_{12}|^2} \right) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{|S_{21}|^2} \right) \quad (20)$$

Where, S_{12} = reverse transmission coefficient, and S_{21} = forward transmission coefficient

$$SE_R = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{1-|S_{11}|^2} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$SE_A = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{1-|S_{21}|^2} \right) \quad (22)$$

Where, S_{11} = forward reflection coefficient

Figure 14: Typical two port VNA set up used for EMI SE measurements [287]. Copyright 2018. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 15: Schematic diagram of two port-VNA used for EMI shielding measurements [245]. Copyright 2022, Adapted from the American Chemical Society.

5. EMI Shielding Applications of Graphene Based Polymer Nanocomposites

5.1 Elastomers Based Graphene Composites

Over the last two decades, the research on EMI shielding materials has primarily focused on polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) as they can be superior to metal sheets owing to their lightweight, low cost, and ease of fabrication [288, 289]. In general, pristine polymeric materials are transparent to EM waves owing to their poor electrical properties. Therefore, conductive nanofillers are added to the polymeric matrices to achieve signal absorption that leads to attenuation of EM waves with restricted surface reflection [288]. This is a modern-day approach to designing highly efficient multifunctional materials with excellent EMI shielding properties. Therefore, a large group of authors have utilized and combined a wide range of polymeric materials and nanofillers to prepare PNCs using various synthesis approaches to achieve enhanced EMI SE [288]. Among various nanofillers, carbon-based nanofillers such as

graphite, graphene, carbon nanofibers, and CNTs have been utilized in the preparation of PNCs for EMI shielding applications owing to their lightweight, superior electrical conductivity and tuneable EMI SE [290, 291]. Among them, graphene with delocalized conjugated π electron structure can provide a quick pathway for electron transport and phonon transfer thereby contributing to an increased in-plane thermal and electrical conductivity [291]. Thus, graphene-based composite materials with dual functionality i.e. desired thermal conductivity and enhanced EMI SE have been explored extensively [292-295].

Elastomers are polymeric materials exhibiting elastic as well as viscous characteristics and consists of long polymeric chains bonded together via weak intermolecular forces. Elastomers can be obtained from natural resources such as natural rubber and therefore they possess rubber-like characteristics such as flexibility and elasticity [241, 296]. Examples of elastomers are natural rubbers, nitrile rubbers, polybutadiene, polyisoprene, PU elastomers, styrene-butadiene block copolymers, fluoroelastomers, silicone elastomers, ethylene propylene diene rubber, and ethylene propylene rubber [297]. Elastomer-based composites have been known as technologically important materials by virtue of their widespread applications [241]. In particular, elastomer-based composites are considered an ideal material for EMI shielding applications owing to their flexibility, easy processing and morphology-controlled properties. Recently, a wide range of graphene based elastomer composites have been explored as EMI shielding materials. For example, Al-Samdi et al. [298] fabricated PNCs based on acrylonitrile butadiene rubber and graphene nanosheets (NBR/GN) using rubber roll-milling method. Figure 16(a, b) depicts the measured and computed values of EMI SE for NBR/GN nanocomposites in the 1–12 GHz frequency range at 2 mm sample thickness. The obtained EMI SE values of all synthesized nanocomposites were dependent on the frequency and GN content. The linear increase in EMI SE vs. frequency indicates the formation of the homogeneous conductive network in the nanocomposites which played a key role in enhancing electrical conductivity and EMI SE value [298]. The EMI SE value of the NBR/GN nanocomposite with 1 wt% GN was found to be in the range of 22–48 dB in the frequency range of 1–12 GHz. When the GN loading was increased to 4 wt%, the EMI SE values varied from 38 to 77 dB indicating an enhancement in the EMI shielding properties of NBR/GN nanocomposites with increasing GN loading. The computed values of EMI SE were very much closer to the measured values for all the nanocomposites. Moreover, the influence of skin depth and the contribution from absorption and reflection mechanisms to the total EMI SE was also investigated as shown in Figure 16(c) [298]. The skin depth decreases with increasing GN content in the nanocomposites owing to

the high aspect ratio of GN and high concentration of charge carriers at the surface. In addition, both reflection and absorption losses were improved with increasing GN content and the shielding via absorption was greater than the shielding via reflection which can be ascribed to the increased conductivity and crosslinking density as a function of GN content in the nanocomposites [298]. The EMI SE values were also dependent on the sample thickness as depicted in Figure 16(d) [298]. The EMI SE values were enhanced with increasing sample thickness attributing to the large dielectric constant and conductivity of NBR/GN nanocomposites with an increase in GN content. The highest EMI SE of ~ 77 dB for the nanocomposite with 4 wt % GN content implies their potential as a very effective, lightweight EMI shielding material for spacecraft, aircraft, and microelectronic applications [298].

Figure 16: (a) EMI SE of NBR/GN composites measured at microwave frequency. (b) EMI SE of the NBR/GN composites computed at microwave frequency. (c) SE_A and SE_R at 10 GHz vs. GN content. (d) Variation in SE with respect to varied sample thicknesses vs. GN content [298]. Copyright 2016. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Song et al. [299], reported flexible EMI shielding composites based on cellulose-derived carbon aerogels (CCA), rGO and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) matrix. The CCA@rGO aerogels were obtained using vacuum impregnation, and freeze drying followed by thermal annealing as shown in Figure 17(a) [299]. The CCA@rGO/PDMS composites formed a 3D conductive network resulting from the skin core structure of CCA@rGO. The prepared CCA/rGO/PDMS composite foam displayed excellent flexibility and the ability to withstand bending deformations (Figure 17(b)). Moreover, the composite foam displayed excellent load-bearing performance as depicted in Figure 17((c-c')) [299]. The CCA@rGO/PDMS composites displayed excellent EMI shielding characteristics with the highest EMI SE values of 51 dB at CCA@rGO loading of 3.05 wt % (Figure 18) [299]. The CCA/PDMS composites displayed an EMI SE value of 40 dB at 2.24 wt % of CCA while the pristine PDMS matrix displayed an EMI SE of 2 dB. The EMI SE value of the CCA/PDMS composite was 27.5% lesser than the EMI SE value of CCA@rGO/PDMS composite, indicating that the EMI shielding properties of CCA@rGO/PDMS composites were improved due to an increase in rGO loading as it provides more carriers for dissipating EM waves [299]. The 3D double-layer conductive network structure of CCA@rGO/PDMS composite with a high conductive network density resulted in an enhanced conductive loss and mismatching of the impedance between the incident EM waves and the prepared composites, thereby enhancing the EMI shielding properties of the composites [299].

Figure 17: (a) Fabrication steps of CCA@rGO/PDMS composites, (b) demonstration of the flexibility and (c-c'') load bearing performance of CCA@rGO aerogels [299]. Copyright 2021. Adapted from Springer.

Preprint

Figure 18: EMI shielding mechanism and performance of CCA@rGO/PDMS composite foam [299]. Copyright 2021. Adapted from Springer.

Yaday et al., [300] prepared PDMS nanocomposites derived from NiFe₂O₄ spinel ferrite nanoparticles (NiFe₂O₄) reinforced with graphite (G), GO and RGO in elastomer matrix for EMI shielding applications. Figure 19 displays the EMI SE of elastomer nanocomposites based on NiFe₂O₄, G, GO and RGO with the sample dimensions of 30 mm x 20 mm x 2 mm in the 5.8 to 8.2 GHz frequency range [300]. Among all the nanocomposites, the maximum value of total EMI SE (SE_{Tot}) achieved was about 28.5 dB for NiFe₂O₄/RGO/elastomer nanocomposite with a sample thickness of 2mm. The developed nanocomposite sheets displayed significant interaction with the EM waves resulting in a considerable loss of EM waves owing to the existence of electric and magnetic dipoles [300]. Moreover, the high EMI SE value of NiFe₂O₄/RGO/elastomer nanocomposite can be attributed to dual NiFe₂O₄ and RGO interfaces. The authors explained the EMI shielding mechanism of RGO and NiFe₂O₄-based elastomer nanocomposite as follows; The incident EM waves interact with the nanocomposite surface; parts of which get reflected and some get penetrated. A portion of the incoming EM waves were

absorbed by NiFe₂O₄ NPs, while the remaining waves passed through the nanocomposite [300]. Finally, the authors concluded that absorption attenuation is the dominant EMI shielding mechanism [300].

Figure 19: EMI SE (SE_{Tot}) for with, \square GO and RGO reinforced NiFe₂O₄/elastomer nanocomposite sheet [300]. Copyright 2014. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Chester et al. [301] prepared the hybrid nanocomposite comprised of CNTs, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs), and poly(styrene-*b*-ethylene-ran-butylene-ran-styrene) (SEBS) via melt compounding and investigated their EMI SE in the 8.2–12.4 GHz frequency range (X-band). The electrical conductivity of SEBS/GNPs/CNT hybrids was 17 orders of magnitude more than that of pure SEBS matrix. The synergistic effect of CNTs and GNPs leads to the enhanced EMI SE in the SEBS/GNPs/CNT hybrid nanocomposite in contrast to SEBS/CNTs and SEBS/GNPs nanocomposites. An average EMI SE of 8.6 dB was reported for SEBS/GNPs nanocomposite at 15 wt % GNPs loading (Figure 20 (a)). The highest EMI SE reported to be 36.47 dB, which signifies the 99.98% reduction of the incident radiation with 5/10 wt.% of GNPs/CNTs loading in the nanocomposite (Figure 20(b)) [301]. This confirms the synergistic effect of CNTs and GNPs on the EMI SE of hybrid nanocomposites. Thus, the preparation of hybrid nanocomposites for EMI shielding application is favourable because of the conductive network

constituted through the combination of carbon nanofillers of varied shapes and sizes which synergistically affect the EMI SE values [302].

Figure 20: The frequency-dependent shielding performance of SEBS/GNPs/CNTs nanocomposite for various GNPs/CNTs loadings [301]. Copyright 2017. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Zhan et al. [303] synthesized composites based on natural rubber/rGO (NRG) and natural rubber/rGO/magnetic iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) (NRMG) using a self-assembly technique in latex. Figure 21 illustrates the synthesis procedure of NRMG composites. The EMI SE of prepared segregated structured composites was investigated in the X-band frequency range [303]. The EMI SE values of all the samples were frequency-independent. With increasing rGO loading, the EMI SE of NRMG and NRG was increased. The excellent EMI shielding characteristics of composites at high rGO content can be attributed to highly conductive networks, ample free charge carriers and large electric dipoles [304, 305]. Furthermore, the heat-treated and untreated NRMG composites with 1.6 mm thickness were analysed for their EMI shielding characteristics. As shown in Figure 22, the EMI SE values of heat-treated composite were found to be 32.1 dB at 10 GHz frequency which was almost 12% greater than the untreated NRMG composite (28.6 dB). Moreover, the effect of specimen thickness on the EMI SE of the prepared composites was evaluated. Figure 23 depicts the correlation of EMI SE of NRMG composites with the film thickness [303]. With the increase of the thickness from 0.8 to 1.8 mm, the EMI SE of NRMG composite increased from 16 to 37 dB. This could be due to the strong interaction of Fe_3O_4 @rGO with the incident EM waves. The study shows that the critical thickness of 1.2 mm or lower of NRMG composite film was sufficient to meet the necessities of commercial applications [303].

Figure 21: Synthesis steps of NRMG composites [303]. Copyright 2018. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 22: EMI SE vs. frequency for (a) untreated and (b) heat treated NRMG composite having 1.6 mm thickness [303]. Copyright 2018. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 23: Film thickness vs. EMI SE of thermally treated NRMG composites [303]. Copyright 2018. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

In another work, Li et. al., [306] prepared rGO@cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) aerogel (rGCA)/ethylene-propylene-diene monomer (EPDM) composites (rGCA/EPDM) with well-defined lamellar structure and interconnected porous network using a chemical reduction and self-assembly processes as shown in Figure 24(a). The interfacial interaction formed between the composite aerogel, and CNCs worked as a reinforcing skeleton while EPDM chains provided an elastic network for crosslinking within the composite aerogel thereby providing rGCA/EPDM with excellent mechanical flexibility, superior compressibility as well as good recoverability (up to 90 % strain) as demonstrated in Figure 24(b). The EMI shielding performance of EPDM, rGA, rGCA, rGA/EPDM, and rGCA/EPDM was evaluated in the X band region as shown in Figure 25(a). The EMI SE values of rGA (24.3 dB) and rGCA (27.3 dB) are higher than 20 dB, satisfying the commercial requirements. In addition, the EMI SE value for rGCA was 10.1 % greater than the EMI SE value of rGA. This indicates that the interconnected 3D network improved the ability of rGCA to reflect and adsorb incident EM waves [306]. In contrast, the EMI SE values of rGA/EPDM and rGCA/EPDM composites were decreased due to the phase interface. Nevertheless, rGCA/EPDM composite displayed EMI SE value of 24.1 dB which is 28.2 % and 9.5 times greater than the EMI SE of rGA/EPDM (18.8 dB) and neat EPDM (2.3 dB) respectively. Figure 25(b) shows the SE_R and SE_A values of EPDM, rGA, rGCA, rGA/EPDM and rGCA/EPDM composites. The SE_R values of aerogels were found to be lower than 2 dB, while the SE_A values are much higher, which contributed significantly to the enhanced EMI SE value. The result suggests that the aerogels effectively adsorb incident EM waves via an absorption shielding mechanism. As compared to rGA and rGA/EPDM composites, the higher values of SE_A of rGCA and rGCA/EPDM are resulted from the interconnected hierarchical structure and crosslinking network of rGCA [306]. Moreover, the well-ordered cellular structure and crosslinking network of rGCA/EPDM have led to multiple interfacial reflections within the internal networks and as a result, most of the incident EM waves were adsorbed by dissipation, and only a few EM waves passed through the aerogels as shown in Figure 25(c) [306].

Figure 24: (a) Steps involved in the preparation of rGCA and rGCA/EPDM composite, (b) Photographs showing different shapes of rGCA/EPDM composites, (c) Photographs showing excellent compressibility of rGCA/EPDM composite [306]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 25: (a) EMI SE_T vs. frequency (b) EMI SE_A and SE_R for EPDM, rGA, rGCA, rGA/EPDM, and rGCA/EPDM composites (c) Schematic diagram showing EMI shielding mechanism for rGCA/EPDM composites [306]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

In another work, Li et al. [307], introduced a facile foaming route to develop the bubble-templated 3D graphene networks encapsulated with PDMS rubber composites for EMI shielding applications. This was used to achieve the assembly of GNPs into a 3D porous network followed by annealing at 1000°C . The composites were prepared after vacuum-assisted infiltration of PDMS liquid. Figure 26 shows the complete process of preparation of 3D rGO-GNP-PDMS composites. The optical microscopy image in Figure 27(a) suggests that the bubbles in the foaming dispersion were closely packed and homogeneously distributed; therefore, a network is formed due to the expulsion of GO and GNPs into a narrow gap. Figure 27(b, c) displays photographs of the prepared hydrogel and the dried 3D rGO-GNP foam, respectively. The SEM micrographs of a fractured surface of 3D rGO-GNP foams with varied graphene loadings (Figure 27(d-f)) suggest the existence of spherical holes caused by the accumulation of air bubbles which are homogeneously distributed within the foam network [307]. With the increase

in graphene content, the pores became more closure to each other. The SEM micrographs with high magnification in [Figure 27\(g-i\)](#) revealed stacking of GO sheets and GNP forming a pore wall consisting of random openings at low graphene loading. The EMI SE values of the 3D porous T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites in the 8 ~ 11 GHz frequency range were evaluated and the results are shown in [Figure 28\(a\)](#). The composites with a thickness of 2 mm displayed enhanced EMI SE values with an increase in graphene loading from 9.7 to 18.1 wt % attributing to enhanced electrical conductivity with an increase in graphene content and also due to low graphene content open air bubbles within the foam network which provided a channel for transmission of EM waves at low graphene content [\[307\]](#). The EMI SE of GNP-PDMS, 3D rGO-GNP-PDMS and 3D T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites with 2 mm thickness and graphene content of 18.1 wt% is depicted in [Figure 28\(b\)](#). The 3D framework substantially enhanced the EMI-shielding properties and with further heat treating the specimens at 100°C the EMI SE was enhanced upto 90 dB. [Figure 28\(c\)](#) displays the influence of specimen thickness on the EMI SE values. With increasing thickness, the EMI SE values were enhanced and a notable improvement in EMI SE was observed when the specimen thickness was increased from 1 mm to 2 mm and with further increase in thickness the EMI SE decreased which may be due to the presence of large-sized bubble voids of several hundreds of microns in size within the foam [\[307\]](#). [Figure 28\(d\)](#) shows a proposed shielding mechanism of 3D T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites. When the incident EM waves reach the composite surface, the discrepancy in the impedance results in the scattering and reflection of a fraction of waves, while some of the waves pass through the composite. The porous network within the composites makes the EM waves reflect at the wall continuously in each closed void. On the other hand, the conducting network significantly promotes electron transport, resulting in the energy loss of the EM waves. Consequently, the bubble-templated 3D structured composites exhibited excellent EMI SE which could be ascribed to the ample number of closed pore structures reflecting and absorbing EM waves as well as high electrical conductivity resulting from interlinked 3D graphene networks [\[307\]](#).

Figure 26: Scheme representing the fabrication methods of 3D rGO-GNP-PDMS composites [307]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 27: (a) Optical microscopy image of the foaming solution. (b) Photos of prepared hydrogel and (c) dried 3D rGO-GNP foam. (d-f) SEM micrographs of fractured surface of 3D rGO-GNP foam with 9.7, 14 and 18.1 wt% graphene loading respectively. (g-i) Magnified SEM images of (d-f) [307]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 28: EMI SE of 3D T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites of 2 mm thickness at varied graphene content. (b) EMI SE of GNP-PDMS, 3D rGO-GNP-PDMS and 3D T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites as a function of frequency. (c) EMI SE of 3D T-rGO-GNP-PDMS composites containing 18.1 wt% graphene at varied thickness. (d) Proposed EMI shielding mechanism [307]. Copyright 2013. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Jinag et al. [308], fabricated lightweight, flexible TPU/RGO composite foam via a supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO₂) foaming technique for EMI shielding application. The synthesis procedure of TPU/RGO composite foam is depicted in Figure 29. The in-situ reduction of GO using L-ascorbic acid led to the hydrogen bonding interaction between the components rendering good interfacial adhesion and excellent flexibility of composite foams. Figure 30(a-f) demonstrates the cellular microstructure of pristine TPU and TPU/RGO composite foams with different RGO content. SEM image of pristine TPU foam (Figure 30(a)) indicates non-homogeneous cell diameters caused by the interfacial interaction between the adjacent TPU particles while some large cellular structures were observed which resulted from

the air bubble trapped in the composite foam during compression molding step [308]. The SEM micrographs of TPU/RGO composite foams with varied RGO loading (Figure 30(b-f)) exhibited high density and small cell diameter owing to the hydrogen bonding interaction between TPU and RGO [308]. Thus, the cellular structure was significantly affected by the distribution of RGO within the TPU/RGO composite foam. Moreover, RGO functioned as a heterogeneous nucleating agent during the foaming process, thereby creating several cells with small dimensions along the TPU interface [308]. These nucleation points improved with increased RGO loading thereby creating a wide boundary of big and small cells. The EMI shielding performance of TPU/RGO composite foams was investigated in the X-band region and frequency-dependent EMI shielding performance was noted in the entire measured frequency range (Figure 31(a, b)). The EMI SE values of prepared composites were enhanced with the increasing RGO content. With 6.5 wt% of RGO in solid TPU/RGO composites, the EMI SE value was observed to be 24.7 dB which is mainly due to the segregated conducting network formed by the composites. For TPU/RGO composite foam, the highest EMI SE of 21.8 dB was noted at 6.5 wt % of RGO loading. Thus, both solid composites and composite foam samples displayed identical EMI shielding properties at the same RGO content. Figure 32 demonstrates the EMI shielding mechanism of the prepared solid composites and composite foam. When the incident EM waves interact with the foam surface, the different impedance of the composite and air is reduced by the cell structure thereby EM waves smoothly enter into the foam interior with limited reflection on the surface. Thus, the cellular morphology of TPU/RGO composites helps in enhancing the absorption of EM waves which is highly important for EMI shielding applications [308].

Figure 29: Fabrication steps of TPU/RGO composite foam [308]. Copyright 2019. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 30: SEM micrographs of TPU/RGO composite foams with varied RGO loading (a) pristine TPU, (b) 0.5 wt %, (c) 1.5 wt%, (d) 2.5 wt %, (e) 3.5 wt %, (f) 4.5 wt% [308]. Copyright 2019. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 31: (a) Frequency dependent EMI SE performance of the TPU/RGO solid composite and (b) TPU/RGO composite foam [308]. Copyright 2019. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 32: Mechanism of EMI shielding of (a) TPU/RGO solid composite and (b) the TPU/RGO composite foam [308]. Copyright 2019. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Liu et al. [309] fabricated leaf-structured foam made of CNTs and RGO (CGF) as an outstanding EMI shielding material. Figure 33(a-c) demonstrates the fabrication procedure, dispersion mechanism and structural diagram of leaf-structured CGF material. The EMI shielding properties of PDMS/CGF composites were investigated and an EMI SE value of 71.1 dB was noted for 2.0C20GF/PDMS composite which remained constant as that of 2.0C20GF because the 3D skeleton structure of 2.0C20GF remained unbroken in spite of PDMS filling as depicted in Figure 34(a). Moreover, PDMS and CGF exhibited excellent interfacial compatibility which is evident from the absence of bubbles in the sample. In addition, the EMI shielding performance of 2.0GF/PDMS and 2.0C20GF/PDMS composites under varied pressure cycles was investigated (Figure 34(b-d)) [309]. A decrease in the EMI SE value was noted for both composites at 8.2 GHz with an increasing number of cycles. After 100 pressure cycles, the EMI SE of 2.0GF/PDMS was reduced from 49.6 dB to 28.1 dB and for 2.0C20GF/PDMS composites, the EMI SE decreased from 71.1 dB to 50.9 dB. Moreover, the

EMI SE conservation rate was 56.7% for 2.0GF/PDMS and 71.6% for 2.0C20GF/PDMS composites [309]. The SE_R of both the composites was reduced by ~ 2 dB, whereas the SE_A values were decreased by 19.2 dB and 17.7 dB, respectively. The possible shielding mechanism of leaf-structured CGF material is presented in Figure 35 which explains that the conductivity expansion in homogeneous CGF materials facilitates the reflection of EM waves on the film sample thereby promoting the absorption of EM waves by increasing the conversion and dissipation of induced current which led to enhanced EMI SE [309]. Table 1 displays a comparison of the EMI shielding performance of various elastomer-based graphene composites which suggest that the EMI shielding performance of elastomer/graphene composites generally improves with higher filler content and higher sample thickness. Overall, it can be ascertained that combining conductive and magnetic nanofillers within porous polymeric matrices offers a promising strategy for fabrication of lightweight, flexible, and broadband EMI shielding materials.

Figure 33: (a) Schematic diagram showing the development of CGF material (b) interaction mechanism of GO and CNTs in the dispersion. (c) structure of synthesized CGF material [309]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 34: (a) Cross-section of the optical microcopy image of 2.0C20GF/PDMS composite (b-d) SE_{tot}, SE_R and SE_A plots of 2.0GF/PDMS and 2.0C20GF/PDMS composites with respect to different pressure cycles [309]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 35: Pictorial diagram of possible shielding mechanism of leaf structured CGF [309]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Table 1. EMI SE values of various elastomer-based graphene nanocomposites.

Elastomer/Graphene Composites	Filler Content (Wt%/Vol%)	Frequency (GHz)	Sample Thickness	EMI SE (dB)	Ref.
Silicone Rubber (SR)/MWCNTs/Graphene	2.774 wt%	18-26	2 mm	42	[290]
RGO@CNC/EPDM	-	8.2–12.4	2 mm	24.1	[306]
RGO/GNP Foam/PDMS	18.1 wt %	8.2–12.4	2 mm	86	[307]
TPU/TRGO	5 vol% TRGO	8.2–12.4	1 mm	5	[310]
SR/Graphene	3 wt%	8.2–12.4	1.70 mm	34.72	[311]
TPU/RGO	20 wt% RGO	5.4-59.6	50 μm	1.98	[312]
Fe ₃ O ₄ /Graphene Foam/PDMS	-	8.2–12.4	1 mm	32.4	[313]
GNSs/melamine foam (MF)/TPU	2.01 vol% GNSs	8.2–12.4	2 mm	35.6	[314]
CNT/Graphene/PDMS	5 wt%	8.2–12.4	2.75 mm	-55	[315]
PDMS/RGO/AgNWs composite (PGAC)	0.1 wt% + 0.33 wt%	8-12	2 mm	34.1	[316]
Graphene Microwires/SR	0.003 vol%	8.2–12.4	2 mm	18	[317]
TPU/graphene aerogel	2 wt %	8.2–12.4	13 mm	34.3	[318]
PC/ethylene-methyl acrylate copolymer (EMA)/RGO	15 phr	8.2–12.4	3 mm	-30	[319]
GNR/TPU	8.2 vol% GNR	12-18	1.3 mm	24.9	[320]
PDMS/graphene foam composites	0.8 wt%	8-12	1 mm	20	[321]
PDMS/graphene	1.5 wt %	8-12	4.8 mm	45	[322]
Poly (ethylene-co-vinyl acetate)/RGO	5 wt%	2-8	1.5 cm	30	[323]
Graphene fibre film (GFF)/PDMS	4 wt %	8.2–12.4	1 mm	50.6	[324]

Graphene foam/CNTs/PDMS	2.7 wt % GF/2 wt % CNTs	8.2–12.4	1.6 mm	75	[325]
Graphene Foam/Fe ₃ O ₄ /PDMS	12 wt % GF/Fe ₃ O ₄	8.2–12.4	2 mm	70.37	[326]
Cellulose nanofibers (NFs)/GO/NBR	30 wt % GO	8.2–12.4	13 mm	25.81	[327]
TPU/rGO/MoS ₂	7 wt % rGO/MoS ₂	8.2–12.4	3 mm	117.2	[328]
PDMS/GNPs/Graphene fluoride (GF)	19.8 wt % GNPs/GF	8.2–12.4	-	51.26	[329]
RGO/MWCNTs/PDMS	0.98	8.2–12.4	2.4 mm	56	[330]

5.2 Thermoplastics Based Graphene Composites

Nowadays, lightweight polymeric composites are replacing heavy metals, particularly in marine, automotive, and aviation industries where both thermosetting and thermoplastics have attracted significant attention for their specific applications [331]. However, thermoplastics offer several benefits in terms of processing and mechanical performance such as recyclability, enhanced fatigue and impact damage resistance, and high shelf life, unlike thermosets [332]. Thermoplastic composites are extremely useful in industrial sectors owing to the possibility of tuning their properties by incorporating various nanofillers. Most thermoplastic polymers are insulating in nature and therefore, for developing efficient EMI shielding materials, the formation of the interconnected conducting network is a pre-requisite which can be achieved by incorporating high aspect ratio conductive nanofillers [333]. In a recent decade, graphene-based thermoplastic composites have been widely studied for EMI shielding. For instance, Zeranska et al. [334], reported multifunctional EMI shielding materials derived from GNPs based acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) composites. The EMI shielding properties were investigated in three different frequency ranges of 0.2–3 THz, 220–320 GHz, and 2–13.5 GHz. The authors observed an extremely high EMI SE value of 80 dB in the terahertz frequency range with a sample thickness of 1 mm. The comparison of EMI SE values of ABS/GNPs composites at three different frequencies i.e. 10 GHz, 300 GHz, and 1.5 THz is shown in Figure 36(a). In all three frequency ranges, the EMI SE values showed an increasing trend with an increase in GNPs loadings. Moreover, the EMI SE increased with an increase in frequency with the lowest value of 20 dB in the microwave region and the highest

value of 80 dB in THZ region. The authors reported absorption as a primary shielding mechanism of ABS/GNPs composites (Figure 36(b)) suggesting their application as EMI absorbers [334].

Figure 36: (a) EMI SE values of ABS/GNPs composites at frequencies of 10 GHz, 300 GHz, and 1.5 THz as a function of GNPs loadings (b) Schematics of EMI shielding mechanism [334]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from American Chemical Society.

In another work, Lu et al. [335], reported PET/graphene transparent multilayer composites with excellent EMI shielding performance. The authors observed a linear improvement in EMI SE values with an increase in PET/graphene layers. The PET/graphene composites with eight layers achieved a maximum EMI SE of 19.14 dB with a microwave

absorbance of 95.82%. Zhang et al. [336], prepared tough and lightweight PMMA/graphene composite foam with cellular structure for EMI shielding application. The composite foam displayed enhanced ductility and tensile toughness as compared with the pristine PMMA foam. Moreover, the graphene addition to PMMA foam led to enhanced electrical conductivity and EMI SE values within the range of 13-19 dB with absorption as the primary EMI shielding mechanism. The main contribution to the enhanced EMI shielding characteristics of the PMMA/graphene composite foam is from the establishment of an interconnected conducting graphene network within the insulating PMMA matrix [336]. Sharif et al. [304], prepared a segregated hybrid comprising PMMA, RGO and magnetite nanoparticles for EMI shielding. The authors noted that the decoration of magnetite nanoparticles on RGO resulted in a substantial rise in EMI SE values. The highest EMI SE value of 25 dB was obtained for PMMA/RGO composites with RGO content of 2.6 vol% and sample thickness of 2.9 mm. The excellent EMI shielding performance of the prepared composites was ascribed to the segregated structure, establishment of the conducting network and magnetic attenuation of magnetite nanoparticles [304]. Recently, Kashi et al. [337] formulated a multifunctional, flexible nanocomposite based on poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) matrix and GNPs. Subsequently, the authors explored the potential of prepared nanocomposites in attenuating EM radiation over a broad microwave frequency range of C (5.85–8.2 GHz), X (8.2–12.4 GHz), and Ku band (12.4–18 GHz). Figure 37 displays EMI SE graphs of PBAT/GNP nanocomposites of 1 mm thickness in three different frequency ranges i.e. 5.85–8.2 GHz, 8.2–12.4 GHz, and 12.4–18 GHz. The total EMI SE of PBAT/GNPs composites increased with increasing GNPs content. The variations in the EMI SE of PBAT/GNPs composites are due to enhanced electrical conductivity and electrical permittivity of PBAT as the GNPs loading was increased [337].

Figure 37: EMI SE of PBAT/GNP composites in (a) C, (b) X, and (c) Ku band regions and (d) with respect to GNP content at mid frequency range [337]. Copyright 2018. Adapted from MDPI.

Abalkar et al. [338] examined the electrical properties and EMI shielding characteristics of PC-graphite nanoplatelets nanocomposites fabricated by a simple solution technique and subsequent hot pressing. The graphite nanoplatelets content was varied from 0 to 6 wt%. The EMI SE of PC-graphite nanoplatelets nanocomposites was investigated in the X-band frequency range and subsequently correlated with the conductivity of the nanocomposites. The highest EMI SE of 35 dB was obtained for the PC nanocomposites containing 6 wt% graphite nanoplatelets. As the content of graphite nanoplatelets increases in the nanocomposites, a greater number of reflection sites were created which resulted in a larger attenuation of EM radiation. Furthermore, the authors evaluated the contributions of SE_R and SE_A with increasing graphite nanoplatelet content at 8.2 GHz. The absorption mechanism prevails over the reflection mechanism in the nanocomposite containing more than 2 wt% of graphite nanoplatelets. Moreover, the higher content of graphite nanoplatelets causes this effect

to become more pronounced, most likely as a result of multiple EM wave reflections from a large number of graphite nanoplatelets present in the nanocomposite. As the content of graphite nanoplatelets increases, more sites for EM wave reflection become attainable by virtue of their extraordinarily high specific surface area [339]. In addition, the authors further investigated the effect of sample thickness on the EMI SE of PC nanocomposites. The EMI SE values were enhanced with an increase in the thickness of the samples because of the enhanced interactions of EM waves with nanocomposites. The PC nanocomposite containing 6 wt % graphite nanoplatelets and 0.5 mm thickness displayed an EMI SE of 31.7 dB, while the nanocomposite sample with 2 mm thickness displayed an EMI SE of about 47.2 dB at the same frequency. Thus, EMI SE values were enhanced with an increase in the thickness of the PC nanocomposites owing to the large surface area and aspect ratio of graphite nanoplatelets as a result of multiple reflections of EM waves and electric loss increases in the nanocomposites [338]. Ling et al. [340], produced lightweight, microcellular polyetherimide (PEI)/graphene composite foams using the phase separation method. The EMI shielding studies of PEI/graphene composites were performed in the X-band region. It was observed that the foaming processes significantly affected the EMI shielding performance of PEI/graphene composites. The total EMI SE of PEI/graphene composite foam was 36.1 dB and 44.1 dB for 7 wt % and 1 wt % graphene content which was about 2.2 and 2.5 fold greater than non-foamed samples. These outcomes indicate the role of the foaming process in significantly improving the EMI SE of PEI/graphene composites. Moreover, it was observed that the microcellular structure significantly increased the absorbing ability of the PEI/graphene composites thereby absorbing about 90.6– 98.9% of EM waves. Thus, the authors conclude that the microcellular foaming technique is an impressive approach to enhancing the EM absorbing ability of shielding materials [340].

Vu et al. [341] used a scalable manufacturing technique to produce multifunctional nanocomposites based on PMMA, MXene and rGO with improved EMI shielding performance. In order to fabricate a 3-D structure of the MXene/rGO in PMMA nanocomposites (MXrGO@PMMA) under heat compression, a hybrid MXene shell (MX) and rGO were congregated on the PMMA surface. Figure 38 displays the preparation procedure of the MXrGO@PMMA nanocomposites [341]. The electrical conductivity of MXrGO@PMMA nanocomposite showed a sharp increase with only 2 vol% of the total filler content as depicted in Figure 39(a). The conductivity of PMMA nanocomposites is about 12 orders of magnitude greater than the conductivity of pristine PMMA. The low percolation threshold of electrical conductivity can be ascribed to the 3D conductive segregated network of MXene and rGO in the PMMA nanocomposites [341]. The higher electrical conductivity of MXrGO@PMMA

nanocomposites renders them acceptable for EMI shielding applications. An excellent EMI SE of ~ 51 dB was accomplished for nanocomposites with 2 vol% filler content in the frequency range of 8–12 GHz (Figure 39(b)). Moreover, the EMI SE of the MXrGO2@PMMA nanocomposites is dependent on the volume fraction ratio between MXene and rGO fillers. While the MX2@PMMA (1:0) nanocomposite exhibited a maximum EMI SE of nearly 61 dB (Figure 39(c)). Additionally, the nanocomposite having a 2 mm thickness showed a 51 dB EMI SE value (Figure 39(d)). Also, from Figure 39(e) the propagation of EM waves and possible mechanisms can be seen. The absorption is primarily responsible for the major shielding mechanism in the MXrGO2@PMMA nanocomposite. It is shown that the absorption effectiveness contributes more to overall SE than the reflection effectiveness. The increased contribution of absorption was clearly caused by the larger filler content and thicker samples.

Figure 38: Preparation procedure of the MXrGO@PMMA nanocomposites [341]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 39: (a) Electrical conductivity of MXrGO@PMMA nanocomposites as a function of total filler content, (b) Total EMI SE for (1:1) volume fraction of fillers, (c) Total EMI SE with different volume fraction ratios, (d, e) Total EMI SE with different thicknesses and possible mechanism for EMI attenuation in the MXrGO@PMMA nanocomposites [341]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Shahzad et al. [342], reported rGO/PS composites with enhanced EMI shielding properties. Sulfur-doped rGO (SrGO) was synthesized via simple heat treatment of GO and sulfur powder and used for the preparation of SrGO/PS composites. Figure 40(a) displays the EMI SE values of rGO/PS and SrGO/PS composites. The EMI SE values of SrGO/PS composites were larger than the values of rGO/PS composites. The EMI SE values of composites were enhanced with increasing filler content over the full frequency range. The maximum EMI SE of 24.5 dB was obtained for SrGO/PS composites with 7.5 wt % SrGO content. The primary shielding mechanism was absorption for both the composite samples i.e. rGO/PS and SrGO/PS with 7.5 wt % of rGO and SrGO content as evident from the SE_A and SE_R results shown in Figure 40(b). An enhanced absorption was noted in SrGO/PS composites which resulted from the existence of S heteroatoms in SrGO that create excess polarization centers and enhanced electrical conductivity due to doping [342].

Figure 40: (a) EMI SE of rGO and SrGO/PS composites and (b) SE_A and SE_R of rGO7.5/PS and SrGO7.5/PS composites [342]. Copyright 2015. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Li et al. [343], prepared PI/rGO composite foam using a three-step method comprising *in situ* polymerization, nonsolvent-induced phase separation and thermal imidization. The EMI shielding characteristics of the prepared nanocomposites were investigated in the X-band region. The maximum EMI SE value of 21 dB was obtained for PI/rGO composite with 16 wt % rGO loading, a sample thickness of 0.8 mm and with absorption as a dominant EMI shielding mechanism. Hamidinejad et al. [344], reported high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and GNPs-based composite foam with electrically and thermally graded microcellular structure for EMI shielding. Yan et al. [345], reported functionalized graphene sheets (FGS) and PS-based porous nanocomposites as efficient and lightweight EMI shielding materials with an average EMI SE

value of 29 dB for a 2.5 mm thick specimen. Sushmita et al. [346], reported doped graphene-based PC nanocomposites for EMI shielding applications. Graphene was doped with ferrite (Fe_3O_4) and Gadolinium oxide (Gd_2O_3) to maximize the EMI shielding performance of PC nanocomposites. A total EMI SE value of -28 and -33 dB was obtained for specific concentrations of Fe_3O_4 and Gd_2O_3 at 18 GHz. Pavlou et al. [347], constructed thin PMMA/graphene composite laminates via CVD technique and studied their EMI shielding properties. An average electrical conductivity of 250 S/cm was reported for PMMA/graphene laminates with 1 vol% graphene content. Figure 41(a) displays EMI SE graphs of PMMA/graphene laminates with varied graphene content. An EMI SE value of 25 dB was achieved at 1 TB for the PMMA/graphene laminate with 0.5 vol% graphene. In addition, the thickness of the composite laminate with 0.33 vol% graphene was varied from 6 μm to 33 μm to measure the effect of augmented involvement of absorption in the total EMI shielding (Figure 41(b)). Consequently, EMI SE values were enhanced with increasing frequency and a maximum of 60 dB was achieved at 2 THz for the sample with the thickness of 33 μm . Moreover, absolute EMI SE values of composite laminates with respect to the volume fraction of graphene as depicted in Figure 41(c), indicate that the material has the potential to achieve high values of absolute EMI SE close to $3 \times 10^5 \text{ dB cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ [347].

Figure: 41: (a) EMI SE of the composite laminates with respect to frequency, (b) EMI SE of composite laminates with 0.33 vol% of graphene in the same frequency range as (a), (c) Absolute EMI SE values of composite laminates with respect to volume fraction of graphene [347]. Copyright 2021. Adapted from Springer Nature.

Ahmed et. al., [348], used a solution casting technique to prepare hybrid PNCs based on few-layer graphene (FLG), nickel spinal ferrites (NSF) and PVDF. The NSF loading was varied from 15–30 wt% and the FLG content was kept constant at 3 wt% in the PVDF matrix. The EMI shielding properties were investigated in the 1-12 GHz frequency range and EMI SE values in the range of 25-45 dB were obtained for PVDF/FLG composites. Moreover, adding 15 wt % of NSF led to an increment of EMI SE in the range of 30-50 dB owing to the interaction and network formation between FLG, NSF and PVDF matrix. The maximum EMI SE of 53 dB was achieved for PVDF/FLG/NSF composites with 3 wt% FLG and 15 wt% NSF with the absorption as dominant shielding mechanism. Jing et. al. [349], constructed a 3D printed porous, lightweight, linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE)/graphene nanocomposite using the fused deposition modelling (FDM) technique (Figure 42). FDM-based 3D printing creates unique structural designs with high flexibility producing suitable materials for various applications. The FDM-printed parts of LLDPE/GNP nanocomposites exhibited unique porous lamellar structures which is beneficial for achieving high EMI shielding efficiency. Printing was done by using three varied filling patterns including $0 \times 60 \times 60$ and $-60 \times 0 \times 60$ and the influence of filling patterns on total EMI SE of printed parts of LLDPE/10 GNPs nanocomposites was investigated. The digital photographs of three (LG₁₋₆₀, LG₂₋₆₀ and LG₃₋₆₀) printed parts are displayed in Figure 43a-i, b-i and c-i. The corresponding SEM micrographs represented in Figures 43a-ii, b-ii and c-ii as well as the super-depth-of-field images displayed in Figures 43a-iii, b-iii and c-iii clearly indicates the porous structures of deposition filaments [349]. Moreover, after MW irradiation, close bonding with the filaments with excellent interfacial strength was observed. Figure 44(a) displays the EMI SE graphs of the three printed parts of LLDPE/10 GNPs composites with infill density of 60% and 100%. It was observed that the filling pattern was less effective in terms of EMI SE values for all the samples which were in the range of 30-32 dB with an infill density of 100%. The EMI SE values changed significantly when the infill density was 60% with the optimum value of 32.4 dB for the LG₃₋₆₀ part at 10 GHz. Figure 44(b) compares the SE_T, SE_A, and SE_R plots of printed parts of LLDPE/10 GNPs composites at 10 GHz with different filling patterns and infill densities. A

little variation in the SE_R values was observed under different conditions while both SE_R and SE_A contributed to SE_T values. Figure 44(c) demonstrates the effect of infill density on the SE_T of printed parts of LLDPE/10 GNPs composites I in the X-band. The EMI SE of all the samples decreased with a decrease in infill density in the order; $LG_{3-100} > LG_{3-80} > LG_{3-60} > LG_{3-40}$ and the EMI SE values were decreased from 32.4 dB to 29 dB. Moreover, the printed part with lower infill density exhibited extremely high thickness normalized EMI SE values (Figure 44(d)). Finally, the authors concluded that the FDM printed composites with lamellar structure are certainly beneficial over other techniques reported in the literature [349].

Figure 44. (a) Scheme depicting the method used to construct LLDPE/GNPs composites (b) FDM 3D printing technique, and (c) Microwave irradiation process used after fabrication process [349]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 44: (a) SE_T of the printed parts of LLDP/GNP composite with varied filling patterns (1–3) and varied infill density (60% and 100%) at 10 GHz, (b) Correlation of SE_T , SE_A and SE_R plots with filling patterns and infill density at 10 GHz, (c, d) Influence of infill density on the SE_T and the SSE/t of the printed parts of LLDP/GNP composite in X-band region [349]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Li et al. [350], synthesized polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) composites based on GNPs and carbonized kenaf fiber (CLF) using compression moulding. The introduction of GNPs/CLF hybrid nanofillers into the PEEK matrix led to an improvement in the EMI shielding capability of composites in the X-band region. The maximum EMI SE of PEEK/GNPs/CLF composite was reported to be 27.1 dB at 9 wt% CLF loading. The incident waves entering the composites were attenuated through reflection scattering and adsorption mechanisms as shown in Figure 45(a). Moreover, a synergistic effect of CLF and GNPs was observed by authors in the attenuation of EM waves. The effect of the thickness of the PEEK/GNPs/CLF composite on the EMI SE is illustrated in Figure 45(b). With the increase in the sample thickness from 1 mm to 2.5 mm, the EMI SE increased from 13.4 dB to 27.1 dB. The authors stated that CLF

formed an interconnected skeleton of the 3D network, while GNPs were dispersed within the skeleton of the composites [350]. The EM waves interact with the 3D conductive network when they are incident inside the composites. The composites with larger thickness had more 3D conductive network and therefore, the greater the interaction of EM wave with the nanofillers, greater will be the consumption of energy [350]. In addition, the SE_A and SE_R values were also obtained for PEEK/GNPs/CLF composite with varied thickness and 9 wt % CLF loading at 12.4 GHz. A negligible change in SE_R and a steady increase in SE_A with increased thickness was noted. This indicates that microwave absorption was the primary shielding mechanism of the composites [350]. Table 2 summarizes the EMI shielding performances of various thermoplastic-based graphene nanocomposites which displaying a wide range of EMI SE values which are strongly influenced by filler composition and structure. In particular, incorporating hybrid fillers such as CNTs, and Ni, Co/Fe based oxides together with graphene based nanofillers significantly improved EMI shielding performance with absorption-dominant shielding mechanism while thin or foam-like structures further improved the shielding performance, making these lightweight, and flexible materials as promising candidates for EMI shielding applications.

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Figure 45: (a) EMI shielding mechanism of the GNP-CLF/PEEK composites; (b) SE_T plot of the GNP-CLF/PEEK composite at varied thickness, and (c) SE_A and SE_R values at 12.4 GHz [350]. Copyright 2020. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Table 2: EMI SE values of various thermoplastic based graphene nanocomposites.

Thermoplastics/Graphene Composites	Filler Content (Wt/Vol%)	Frequency (GHz)	Sample Thickness	EMI SE (dB)	Ref.
PS/Functionalized graphene sheets (FGS)	30 wt% FGS	8.2–12.4	2.5 mm	29	[345]
Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE)/TRGO	0.66 vol% TRGO	8.2–12.4	2.5 mm	31.6	[351]

PC/SAN/Graphene nanosheets decorated with Ni NPs (G-Ni)	3 wt% G-Ni NPs	8–18	1.5 mm	29.4	[352]
UHMWPE/GNPs	15 wt% GNPs	8.2–12.4	1 mm	33	[353]
Polyamide (PA)/Graphene	2.5 wt %	8–12	1.5 mm	33.72	[354]
PMMA/Ni NPs decorated GNPs (Ni@GNPs)	40 wt% Ni@GNP	8.2–12.4	1.75 mm	38	[355]
PMMA/Graphene	4.23 vol% Graphene	8.8–12	3.4 mm	30	[356]
Polyether-ketone (PEK)/GNPs	5 vol% GNPs	8.2–12.4	1 mm	30	[357]
PVDF-CNT-Graphene-NiCo	6 wt % CNTs + 8 wt % Graphene + 8 wt% NiCo	18-26	0.5 mm	33	[358]
PI/Nanocarbon Grafted Carbon Fiber (NCF)/RGO	30 wt % NCF + 3.5 wt % RGO	8.2–12.4	0.5 mm	45	[359]
PVDF/RGO/ ZnNiFe	1 wt% RGO + 1 wt % ZnNiFe	8.2–12.4	1.8 mm	29.05	[360]
ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA)/Ethylene octadecene copolymer (EOC)/ exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (GnP)	30 wt % xGnP	7.5 – 8	13 mm	-67.63	[361]
PVDF/GNP	25 wt% GNPs	2-13.5	1 mm	40	[362]
PS/TRGO	10 wt% TRGO	8.2–12.4	2.8 mm	18	[363]
PVDF/RGO/BaZrFe ₁₁ O ₁₉	10 wt % RGO + 10 wt% BaZrFe ₁₁ O ₁₉	8.2–12.4	0.2 mm	48.59	[364]

PMMA/CNTs/GNPs	8 wt % CNTs + 4 wt% GNPs	8-12	2 mm	36	[365]
PVC/Graphene	20 wt% Graphene	8.2–12.4	2 mm	31	[366]
PVC/Graphene	40 wt% Graphene	10-15	2 mm	26	[367]
Polypropylene (PP)/RGO	1.83 wt % RGO	8.2–12.4	0.7 mm	29.3	[368]
PP/PET/Graphene	2 vol% Graphene	8.2–12.4	5 mm	60	[369]
PTFE/GNs	50 wt % GNs	8.2–12.4	1 mm	50,85	[370]

5.3 Thermosets Based Graphene Nanocomposites

In recent years, thermosetting polymers have become very popular owing to their superior properties and high-temperature applications. Unlike thermoplastics, thermosetting polymers can neither be melted upon heating nor be reformed in a solvent, which makes it difficult to recycle [371]. Examples of thermosetting polymers are PU, bakelite, epoxies, silicones, vulcanized rubber, polyesters, phenolics, non-isocyanate PU, and melamine-formaldehyde polymers [372]. Thermosetting polymer forms stable and robust chemical crosslinking during curing which results in several desirable properties including good solvent, and chemical resistance, good thermal stability, excellent hardness and mechanical strength [371]. Curing process is very crucial and influences the durability, morphology, polymerization, crosslinking extent, and stability of the thermosetting polymer [373]. Moreover, the properties of thermosetting polymers can be further enhanced by the introduction of fillers, such as nanoclays, CNTs, and graphene-based materials [374]. Therefore, thermosetting PNCs are known as revolutionary materials by virtue of their advantageous physico-chemical properties and extensive applications in commercial products [375]. Thermoset/graphene composites are a subject of tremendous interest for a wide range of applications by virtue of their low density, excellent corrosion resistance and improved mechanical, thermal and electrical properties [374, 376]. Moreover, graphene-based thermosetting PNCs are recognized as ideal materials for EMI shielding applications as together they form an electrically conductive network and exhibit high EMI SE [220]. For example; Shen et al. developed polyetherimide (PEI)/graphene@Fe₃O₄

(G@Fe₃O₄) composite foams having microcellular structure and low density ranging from ~0.28-0.4 g/cm³ using phase separation technique [377]. The EMI SE value of prepared nanocomposite foam was increased with increasing G@Fe₃O₄ loading and for nanocomposite foam with 10 wt% G@Fe₃O₄ content EMI SE values achieved in the range of 14.3 -18.2 dB in the X- band. Moreover, most of the EM waves were adsorbed by the composite foam due to the presence of multiple reflections, enhanced impedance mismatch and EM attenuation caused by Fe₃O₄ NPs [377].

Tahalyani et al. [244], reported solution-processed PU/GNPs composites for EMI shielding applications. The PU/GNPs composites exhibited the highest EMI SE of 40.9 dB and 70.5 dB at 6 wt% GNPs loading for 1 mm and 2 mm thick samples respectively. Based on the microstructure of the synthesized composites which revealed the homogeneous distribution of graphene nanoplatets within the PU matrix and the interaction of the composites with the EM waves, the authors proposed an EMI shielding mechanism as shown in Figure 46 [244]. The PU dipoles get excited when an EM wave interacts with the prepared composite giving rise to dipolar polarization. In addition, the PU/GNPs interface results in interfacial polarization leading to the formation of a heterogeneous system. Upon interaction with EM wave, these heterogeneous systems help in charge accumulation at the interface causing enhanced space charge polarization. The charge accumulation further distorts the incident EM waves. The authors further stated that the nanocapacitors are formed within the nanocomposites where GNPs act as nanoelectrodes and PU matrix acts as dielectrics [244]. Because of the conducting nature of GNPs, the charges were passed inside the nanocomposites via migration and electron hopping, thereby intensifying the conduction loss and improving the EMI SE via multiple internal reflections which subsequently resulted in an absorption and thermal dissipation of EM energy within the PU/GNPs composites (Figure 46) [244].

Figure 46: EMI shielding mechanism of PU/rGOs composites [244]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Hsaio, et al. [220] examined the impact of the covalent functionalization of graphene nanosheets on the EMI shielding properties of water-borne PU (WPU) nanocomposites. The functionalized graphene nanosheets were homogeneously dispersed in the WPU matrix enabling the establishment of an electrically conductive network. The prepared functionalized graphene/WPU composites displayed an EMI SE value of 38 dB in the X-band region at 5 vol% content of graphene in the WPU matrix. In another work, Hsiao et al., [378] produced lightweight WPU/rGO composites using layer-by-layer (L-b-L) assembly for EMI shielding application. The electrospun WPU fibers were rapped with the GO bilayer showing good adhesion between them. Later, GO was reduced using hydroiodic acid (HI) to obtain rGO/WPU composites. The overall electrical conductivity was enhanced to 16.8 S/m along with layer increment resulting from the enhanced connectivity of RGO, forming the conducting channels within the composites. The highest EMI SE of 34 dB was obtained in the X-band frequency range for a 1 mm thick rGO/WPU-15 composite containing 7.5 wt % of rGO as depicted in Figure 47(a) [378]. Furthermore, the mechanism of shielding was realized by obtaining SE_{total} , SE_A , and SE_R values at 9 GHz with respect to cycles of L-b-L-assembly and the maximum

values of SE_{total} , SE_A , and SE_R were 34, 31, and 3 dB, respectively for rGO/WPU-15 (Figure 47(b)) [378]. Moreover, the dominant shielding mechanism was absorption and likewise SE_{total} also progressed which justifies the greater SE_A values than SE_R values at different cycles of L-b-L assembly. The conductive dissipation of shielding materials leads to the decay of an incident EM wave. The efficiency of composite materials in EMI shielding relies greatly on their high electrical conductivity and the complexity of their electrical conduction networks [378]. The EM waves could not escape through the rGO/WPU composites and therefore the EM waves were absorbed and converted into heat as a result of the establishment of a progressive rGO network. Thus, the prepared composites displayed absorption-dominated EMI shielding. The same group of authors reported covalent modification of graphene nanosheets to improve the EMI shielding characteristics of WPU nanocomposites and achieved a maximum EMI SE value of 32 dB at 5 vol% of functionalized graphene [379].

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Figure 47: (a) EMI SE vs. frequency in X band frequency of RGO/WPU composites with varied L-b-L assembly cycles, (b) Comparison of SE_{total} , SE_A , and SE_R at 9 GHz as a function of L - b-L assembly cycles of RGO/WPU composites [378]. Copyright 2014. Reproduced with permission from The American Chemical Society.

Ahmed et al. fabricated rGO-reinforced epoxy composites with varied concentrations of rGO from 0 to 5 wt% and examined the dielectric behaviour of the rGO/cured epoxy composites which was significantly influenced by the applied frequency and the rGO content [380]. The author further confirmed that the integration of rGO NPs in the epoxy resin matrix

led to linear enhancement in the dielectric properties of the composites. Moreover, the EMI SE of rGO/cured epoxy composites was investigated and a substantial improvement in the EMI SE value of nanocomposites was observed in comparison to pristine epoxy resin. The highest EMI SE of 25.748 dB was observed at 12 GHz for rGO/cured epoxy composite at 5 wt % rGO content and a sample thickness of 6 mm. The authors further confirmed that the reinforcement of rGO to the cured epoxy matrix led to an improvement in the EMI SE values of the composites. Based on the results, it was found that absorption was the dominant shielding mechanism [380]. In another work, Ren et al. [381], successfully developed a novel laminated cyanate ester (CE)-based nanocomposites via a facile method involving mechanical mixing and hot-pressing techniques with exceptional EMI SE and reduced reflection properties. The laminate-structured nanocomposites with an optimized concentration of nanofillers (5 wt % graphene nanosheets and 15 wt % Fe_3O_4) with a thickness of ~ 2 mm display extraordinary EMI SE with the highest value of 45.7 dB in the X-band (Figure 48(a-d)). It was also noted that mention that layer-structured nanocomposites with a thickness of ~ 2 mm displayed higher EMI SE values than homogeneous-structured nanocomposites. In addition, from Figure 48(c) it can be confirmed that layer-structured nanocomposites have lower SE_R values than homogeneous structured nanocomposites with the same nanofiller content. Additionally, Figure 48(d) represented the comparison of SE_T , SE_A , and SE_R for both types of nanocomposites and indicated the higher SE_T was mostly due to better absorption rather than EM wave reflection which can be attributed to the “absorb-reflect-reabsorb” process of EM waves [381].

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Figure 48: EMI SE of CE-based polymer nanocomposite; (a) SE_T (b) SE_A and (c) SE_R in the 8-12 GHz frequency range (d) Comparison of SE_T, SE_A, and SE_R with various filler loadings at 12 GHz [381]. Copyright © 2018. Adapted from MDPI.

Han et al. [382], reported in-situ grafting of vertical edge rich graphene (VG) on to CNT sponge to construct covalently bonded 3D hybridized carbon skeleton followed by fabrication of CNT-VG/epoxy composites for EMI shielding applications. The prepared CNT-VG/epoxy composites displayed an enhanced EMI SE value of 46.9 dB with a thickness of 1 mm which is mainly attributed to the interconnected 3D structured CNT sponge, interface conductivity, and the defect-rich structure of VG. Moreover, these composites displayed the thermal conductivity value of $2.23 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ which indicates their excellent thermal management ability. These multifunctional composites displayed excellent application potential in next generation electronic devices. In another work, Li et al., [383] fabricated epoxy (EP)/RGO and EP/RGO/MWCNT composite foams via a physical foaming method with scCO₂ (Figure 49). The EMI SE values of EP/RGO solid composites with 1 wt % RGO was 4.4 dB and with 5 wt% RGO content, it was 11.5 dB. The composite foam exhibited EMI SE values of 4.6 dB and

15.2 dB with 1 wt% and 5 wt% of RGO respectively. On the other hand, the EMI SE value of EP/RGO/MWCNT solid composite with 1 wt% RGO/CNT was 6 dB and with 5 wt% RGO/CNT it was 15.7 dB. The composite foam exhibited EMI SE of 7.6 dB and 22.6 dB respectively at 1 wt% and 5 wt% RGO/CNT content (Figure 50). Thus, the microcellular structure of the composites with reduced density, exhibited excellent EMI shielding properties. Nevertheless, the EMI shielding performance of the EP/RGO/MWCNT composite foam was significantly higher compared to the EP/RGO or EP/MWCNT composite foams at similar filler loading. The alignment or the orientation of RGO and MWCNT post-foaming process, enhanced the establishment of conductive network in the composites which generated local current under the EM field, thereby converting the EM energy into heat dissipation in the composites. As a result, the EMI SE of EP/RGO/MWCNT composites was improved. The SE_A , SE_R and SE_T graphs are displayed in Figure 50(e, f). For the solid and foamed EP/RGO composites, the SE_A values were obtained in the range from 2.5-6.9 dB with the RGO/MWCNT loading of 1–5 wt% while the SE_A to SE_T contributed upto 56–60%. Post foaming, the SE_A to SE_T contributed up to 61–63%. For the solid and foamed EP/RGO/MWCNT composites with filler loading of 1–5 wt%, the SE_A values reached in the range 3.7-9.0 dB. The SE_A to SE_T contributed up to 57–62%, and post-foaming the SE_A contributed upto 64–68% (Figure 50 (f)). It was further ascertained that apart from the synergistic effect of RGO and MWCNT primarily on the absorption of EM wave, the microcellular structure also played a key role in enhancing the EMI shielding properties of composite foam. The EM wave dissipation in the EP/RGO/MWCNT composite foam is schematically shown in Figure 51. The incident microwaves were reflected several times within the cells and then absorbed and converted to heat as a result of the microcellular structure and conductive fillers present [383]. The internal multiple scattering and reflection in the nanocomposite are made possible by the 3D conductive network, which is in accordance with the EMI shielding characteristics of porous conducting materials. The inclusion of sheets like 2D materials also increased the surfaces for reflection and prolonged the transmission path of EM waves inside composites.

Figure 49: Preparation method of RGO/MWCNT and EP/GO/MWCNT composites [383].
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Figure 50: (a, b) MI of solid and foamed EP/RGO composites (c, d), EMI SE of solid and foamed EP/RGO/MWCNT composites, (e) SE_R, SE_A and SE_T plots of solid and foamed EP/RGO composites, (f) SE_R, SE_A and SE_T plots of solid and foamed EP/RGO/MWCNT composites [383]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 51: Schematic illustration of EM wave dissipation in EP/rGO/MWCNT foam representing (a) orientation of RGO and MWCNT in EP/rGO/MWCNT composite foam (b) black lines representing MWCNTs, grey sheets representing rGO and arrows indicating growth directions of bubbles formed through foaming [383]. Copyright © 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Fan et al., [384] fabricated nanocomposites comprising high loading of rGO in a modified epoxy (m-EP/rGO) matrix using the scCO₂ foaming method. The foam composites exhibited several interfaces and tunable microcellular structures. Besides, nanofiller rearrangement during the foaming process led to the growth of a more intensive conductive network, which enhances the attenuation of EM waves through repeated reflections and absorptions. The epoxy resin was modified using a plasticizer (KM) and the hyperbranched epoxy (E102), which enabled a successful foaming process. As shown in Figure 52(a), an irregular and non-uniform cell morphology was observed for neat epoxy resin owing to its high crosslink density as shown in Figure 52(b), which restricts the foaming process. In contrast, the modified epoxy matrix during the foaming process, exhibited improved gas absorption and the bubble nucleation and growth thereby producing foam with relatively homogeneous cell morphology and very low foam density (Figure 52(c, d)). Furthermore, the EMI shielding efficiency of m-EP/rGO nanocomposites was investigated in the X band. Figure 53 displays the EMI SE values of m-EP/rGO nanocomposite foams and solid samples. As shown in Figure 53(a, b), the EMI SE values of m-EP/rGO nanocomposite foam were greater than the solid samples at the same rGO loading. Moreover, the EMI SE values of foam and solid samples were increased with increasing rGO loading as shown in Figure 53(c). Also, it was noted that the foaming process has led to a higher thickness of the foam which resulted in higher SE_T values for m-

EP/rGO nanocomposite foams in comparison with the solid composites. Moreover, the SE_T value of the foamed sample was higher (86.6 dB) than the solid sample (83.5 dB) at higher rGO loading (32.26 wt%). Figure 54 depicts the possible shielding mechanism of m-EP/rGO nanocomposite, with incident waves interacting with the material and reflecting in part due to impedance mismatch, resulting in the difference in EM performance between the shielding material and ambient air [384]. Furthermore, the high loading of rGO in the epoxy resin provided an efficient pathway to carry free charges leading to the formation of eddy current. Moreover, the interfacial polarization generated at the rGO/m-EP interface has benefited the EM wave dissipation [384].

Figure 52: (a) Micrographs showing fractured surface of pristine epoxy foam, (c) Microstructure of m-EP foam obtained within 20s at 120°C (b, d) Schematic illustration of CO₂ transfer and foaming process in neat epoxy and m-EP [384]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 53: The EMI SE of m-EP/rGO composites in X-band as (a) m-EP/rGO solids, (b) foams, (c) individual contribution from absorption (SE_A), reflection (SE_R), and specific total SE (SSE_T) [384]. Copyright 2021 reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 54: Pictorial diagram of EMI shielding mechanisms showing attenuation and reflection in solids and foamed specimens [384]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Yao et al [385], prepared porous and highly flexible fire-retardant graphene/PU composites for EMI shielding applications. Figure 55 illustrates the synthesis process, EMI shielding, and fire retardant mechanism of graphene/PU composite. The presence of graphene and the porous structure made the composite conducive to EMI shielding. The EMI shielding performance of graphene/PU composite at a low-frequency range and the related mechanism is shown in Figure 56 [385]. The EMI SE values in the range of 8-45 dB were achieved at a low frequency range (0-2500 MHz). Initially, the EMI SE values were improved with an enhanced graphene loading and then decreased with optimum values at 0.5% graphene content. The porous graphene/PU composites with polygonal structure exhibited multiple reflection of the incident EM waves and attenuated the EM waves to a large extent. Yang et al [386], successfully fabricated Fe_3O_4 and anisotropic rGO aerogel (AGA) reinforced epoxy composites ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$) via freeze drying, annealing, infiltration and curing process with excellent EMI shielding properties. The EMI shielding characteristics of the prepared composites were investigated in axial and radial directions. Figure 57(a, b) represents the EMI SE values of the AGA/EP and $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composites in the X band which exhibited higher EMI SE values along the radial direction as compared to the axial direction. In addition, $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composites exhibited higher EMI SE values in both directions (32.3 dB axial, 37.6 dB radial) compared with the AGA/EP composites (8.3 dB axial, 14.3 dB radial). Furthermore, the authors evaluated the power coefficients of R, T and A of the prepared composites for understanding the EMI shielding mechanism and to evaluate the power balance of microwave interaction with the shielding materials [386]. The prepared composites exhibited larger A values than R and T in both directions except for $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composites in the radial direction (Figure 57(c)). It was noted that $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composites were absorption-dominated which exhibited desired characteristics for reducing the secondary pollution of EM waves. Figure 57(d), illustrates the shielding mechanism of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composites. The incident EM waves were partially reflected at the composite interface by virtue of the impedance difference between the $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA/EP$ composite and the air while the remaining EM waves entered into the composites. The interconnected conducting network of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@AGA$ absorbed the EM waves and displayed enhanced dissipation of EM waves [386].

Figure 55: Scheme describing the synthesis process, EMI shielding and fire retardant mechanism of porous graphene/PU composites [385]. Copyright 2020. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

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Figure 56: (a) EMI SE, (b) Schematic representation of shielding mechanism (c) SE_A and (d) SE_R of graphene/PU composites [385]. Copyright 2020. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 57: (a, b) EMI SE_T, (c) power coefficients of the AGA/EP and Fe₃O₄@AGA/EP composites in the axial and radial directions, and (d) representative diagram of EMI shielding mechanism of Fe₃O₄@AGA/EP composites [386]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Recently, Lee et al. [387], used single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs)/rGO hybrid fillers to prepare conductive ink utilized on polyester fabrics (PFs) substrate for the preparation of flexible epoxy composites for EMI-shielding applications. The step-by-step preparation procedure of SWCNTs/rGO/PF/epoxy composites is displayed in Figure 58. The EMI-shielding properties of the SWCNTs/rGO/PF/epoxy composites were investigated in the X-band frequency and the results are shown in Figure 59(a). The EMI SE of composites was increased with increasing SWCNTs loading. However, EMI SE values further decreased for S-4/G/PF/Ep composites (4 wt % SWCNTs loading) because of the SWCNTs agglomeration within the hybrids. The maximum EMI SE of 40.1 dB was achieved for 0.6 mm thick S-2/G/PF/Ep composites (2 wt % SWCNTs loading) which is about 185% higher than the EMI SE of composites without SWCNTs (G/PF/Ep) [387]. From Figure 59(b), it was evident that

SE_A values were improved with the increasing SWCNTs content up to 2wt% and then further decreased slightly. On the other hand, the SE_R displayed a decreasing trend indicating the predominance of absorption behaviors with increasing SWCNTs content in the composites. The transmission was negligible in SWCNTs/rGO/PF/epoxy composites and the majority of the incident EM waves were suppressed via absorption and reflection (Figure 59(c)). On the other hand, the obtained values of A and R for G/PF/EP composites were 0.37 and 0.64 respectively signifying reflection as the dominant shielding mechanism. The authors ascertained that introducing SWCNTs played a key role in the formation of a percolation network thereby enhancing the interfacial interaction between the SWCNTs/rGO and the EP matrix. The hierarchical architectures of SWCNTs/rGO hybrid helped in creating multiple interfaces that resulted in the absorption-dominant EMI shielding. The shielding mechanism of the SWCNTs/rGO/PF/EP composite is shown in Figure 60 which indicates the attenuation of incident waves entering the composites by virtue of absorption and reflection [387]. Moreover, the shielding in the prepared composites was mostly by virtue of enhanced conductivity of the layer resulting from the presence of SWCNTs/rGO hybrid fillers. These findings were ascribed to the hierarchical structure of the PF skeleton and nanometre scale SWCNT/rGO network, which led to exceptional EMI-shielding properties of the composites [387].

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Figure 58: Schematic illustration of the synthesis method of SWCNTs/rGO hybrid ink loaded PF/EP composites [387]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from Springer Nature.

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Figure 59: EMI SE of SWCNTs/rGO/PF/EP composite with respect to SWCNTs loading in the X-band frequency (a) EMI SE, (b) SE_R , SE_A , and SE_{Total} at 8.2 GHz, (c) EMI shielding coefficient at 8.2 GHz [387]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from Springer Nature.

Figure 60: Representation of the EMI shielding mechanism of carbon ink-based PF/EP composite, (a) incoming wave dissipation by S-x/G/PF/Ep, (b) absorption based mechanism in the hierarchical porous PF structures, and (c) different scatterings of the EM waves at the SWCNTs/rGO and EP interfaces [387]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from Springer Nature.

Wang et al. [388], reported graphene/WPU composites based flexible film comprising dense layered structure for EMI shielding application. The surface modification of graphene nanosheets using polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) in a simple liquid phase ball-milling method led to efficient dispersion into the WPU matrix. The dense structure of graphene and low defects helped in yielding G/WPU film with high electrical conductivity (1,004.5 S/m). Consequently, it helped in achieving enhanced EMI SE with a maximum value of 73.4 dB for a 0.9 mm thick sample with a low density of 1.4 g/cm³, resulting in a shielding of 99.99999% incident EM waves. Han et al., [389], reported heterogeneous stacking strategy to modify epoxy resin and to develop carbon aerogels with excellent EMI shielding and thermal management performance. For this, the authors prepared covalently bonded rGO-CNT-VG based 3D hybrid structures via CVD technique. The prepared hierarchical 3D rGO-CNT-VG composites exhibited heterogeneous interfaces within the components which promoted charge polarization,

interfacial polarization and dielectric relation thereby significantly enhancing attenuation of EM waves to achieve ideal EMI shielding performance. The prepared composites exhibited excellent thermal conductivity value of $2.46 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and EMI SE value of 56.65 dB which are 5.1 and 1.9 times greater than rGO/epoxy composites respectively. Thus, this study suggests that designing heterogeneously stacked all carbon 3D structures can be helpful in controlling the performance of carbon based composites. Barani et al., [390], reported multifunctional epoxy/graphene composites for EMI shielding. The prepared composites exhibited excellent EMI shielding performance in the X-band region with a total EMI SE value of 65 dB for the sample with a thickness of 1 mm. Moreover, the EMI SE values improved with an increase in temperature by virtue of electronic band-type and hopping conduction within and between the fillers respectively [390]. The excellent EMI shielding characteristics and heat conduction properties of epoxy/graphene composite at high temperatures make them a prospective candidate for electronic packaging where EMI shielding and thermal management are key aspects of designing an electronic device.

In another interesting work, Li et al., [391] reported novel composites comprising of highly conducting 3D porous network of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, rGO and hybrid aerogel (MRG) with excellent flexibility and self-healing properties. The hybrid aerogel was prepared via freeze drying, followed by chemical reduction and subsequently vacuum-assisted impregnation method was used to introduce cross-linked PU containing Diels–Alder bonds (PUDA) into MRG. Figure 61 displays the Schematic diagram showing the synthesis process of MXene/rGO/PUDA (MRGP) composites [391]. Figure 62(a) shows electrical conductivity graphs of the MRGP composites with respect to MXene loading. In particular, by increasing the MXene content in the composite, an excellent conductive network was established and enhanced conductivity was achieved. Further, the EMI shielding ability was investigated and it was noted that the EMI SE values were enhanced with increasing MXene content in the composite (Figure 62(b)). The 3D MRGP composites exhibited EMI SE of 39.1 dB at 0.46 vol% of MXene and 0.65 vol% loading of rGO in the X-band. The SE_T , SE_A and SE_R graphs of MRGP composites are shown in Figure 62(c). It was noted that for all the samples, the trend of SE_T , SE_A and SE_R values were improved with increasing MXene content in the MRGP composites. Also, all the samples displayed significantly higher SE_A values than SE_R . As shown in Figure 62(d), the transmission coefficient (T) values were reduced with increasing MXene loading, signifying enhanced EMI shielding potential of the composite. In contrast, the reflection coefficient (R) values were increased with an increase in MXene content which can

be attributed mainly to the impedance mismatch at the interface due to the enhanced conductivity of the composites. The R values were significantly larger than the A values indicating reflection-dominant shielding mechanism in the MRGP composites. Besides, the authors investigated the influence of specimen thickness on the EMI shielding properties of MRGP composites (Figure 62(e)) and it was noted that with enhanced specimen thickness, the EM waves pathway gradually increased as a result an enhanced EM wave loss was observed. The specimen having a thickness of 1 mm exhibited an EMI SE of 23 dB and in the entire frequency range, the EMI SE values of >20 dB were obtained. Moreover, the proportion of SE_R and SE_A in SE_T does not change with respect to sample thickness showing higher SE_A values than SE_R (Figure 62(f)) [391]. Table 3 summarizes EMI SE values of various thermosets based graphene composites which exhibit excellent EMI shielding performance, achieving high SE values even at low filler loadings in some cases. In addition, incorporating hybrid nanofillers such as CNTs, MXene, or metal nanoparticles together with graphene in thermosetting polymers and creating hierarchical or porous structures significantly enhances EMI SE values with absorption-dominant shielding mechanism. Overall, thermoset-based graphene composites are ideal choice as a high performance EMI shielding materials because of their structural tunability, high-efficiency and mechanical stability.

Figure 61: Schematic diagram showing synthesis process of MRGP composites [391]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 62: (a) Conductivity of MRGP composites, (b) EMI SE plots of the MRGP composites in the X-band region. (c) SE_A, SE_R, and SE_T curves, (d) Average values of T, A and R of MRGP composite with 3 mm thickness, (e) Influence of specimen thickness on the EMI SE of MRGP composite and (f) Plots depicting average contribution of SE_T, SE_A and SE_R [391]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Table 3. EMI SE values of various thermoset based graphene composites.

Thermosets/Graphene Composites	Filler Content (Wt %/Vol%)	Frequency (GHz)	Sample Thickness	EMI SE (dB)	Ref.
Fe ₃ O ₄ @anisotropic RGO aerogel/epoxy (Fe ₃ O ₄ @AGA/EP)	0.36 wt%	8.2-12.4	4 mm	40.4	[386]
Graphene/WPU	30 wt%	8.2-12.4	0.9 mm	73.4	[388]
Epoxy/Graphene	18.8 vol%	8.2-12.4	2 mm	105	[390]
PU/3D MXene/RGO	0.46 vol% MXene + 0.65 vol% RGO	8.2-12.4	3 mm	39.1	[391]
PU/GNP	10 wt%	8-12	3 mm	41	[392]
PI/WPU-Ni/Fe ₃ O ₄ @RGO	6.2 wt% Ni + 8.53 wt% Fe ₃ O ₄ @RGO	8.2-12.4	3 mm	36.8	[393]
Poly(esterimide) (PEI)/Graphene	5 wt%	8.2-12.4	2.3 mm	62.2	[394]
WPU/Silver-nanoparticle-decorated functional RGO (Ag@FRGO)	5 wt% FRGO	8.2-12.4	2 mm	35	[395]
PU/Graphene (G)	2.5-4.2 wt %	8.2-12.4	0.9-1.5 mm	30-61	[396]
Epoxy/RGO/Ni	9.76 wt% RGO/Ni	8.2-12.4	2 mm	41.11	[397]
Epoxy/RGO/Carbon Fiber (CF)	0.5 wt%	8-12	6 mm	37.6	[398]
RGO-Edge rich Graphene (ERG)Epoxy	3.98 wt %	8.2-12.4	1 mm	45.9	[399]
Epoxy/Graphene	50 wt%	8.2-12.4	1 mm	45	[400]
PI/Graphene/CF	20 wt%	8.2-12.4	2 mm	73	[401]
PI/CNTs/RGO	CNTs/RGO ratio of 2:1	8.2-12.4	15 mm	28.2	[402]

PI/polydopamine-modified expanded graphite (EG-PDA)	60 wt%	8.2-12.4	0.5 mm	101	[403]
Carbonized spent coffee grounds (C-SCG)/GNs/Cyanate ester (CE)	C-SCG 9 wt % + GNs 3 wt %	8.2-12.4	2 mm	31.09	[404]
Carbonized loofah (CL)/GNs/CNTs/CE	7 wt% GNs + 1 wt % CNTs	8.2-12.4	2 mm	35.57	[405]

5.4 Biopolymers Based Graphene Composites

In recent years, biopolymers have received significant attention from researchers and professionals across various disciplines because of their advantages such as non-toxicity, eco-friendliness and biodegradability [406, 407]. Biopolymers are produced from renewable natural resources such as plants, animals and microorganisms and they are considered as a potential replacement for synthetic or petroleum-based polymeric systems [407]. Moreover, biopolymers have fascinating physical, chemical, and biological characteristics including renewability, eco-friendliness, biocompatibility, biodegradability and antibacterial properties which make them useful in various industries such as food, pharmaceutical, medicinal, and environmental fields [407, 408]. Biopolymers are promising materials for numerous applications, such as emulsions, edible films, sensing, food packaging, drug delivery, medical implants, wound healing, tissue scaffolds, and wound dressing [406]. Over the years, biopolymer nanocomposites (BPNCs) integrated with graphene and its derivatives have been broadly explored and excellent performances have been achieved in the fields of gas sensors, biosensors, drug delivery, tissue engineering, antibacterial activity and energy storage and conversion etc. [409, 410]. Besides, graphene-incorporated BPNCs have also demonstrated excellent EMI shielding performances. For example; Choi et al. [411], reported ultrathin graphene/cellulose composites prepared via a simple spray deposition technique (Figure 63(a)) for EMI shielding applications. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyacrylic acid (PAA) were used to improve graphene adhesion on the cellulose substrate. The prepared composites were respectively named GVC (with PVA) and GAC (with PAA). The prepared graphene/cellulose composites displayed excellent flexibility (Figure 63(b)). The high orientation and firm stacking of graphene nan platelets on cellulose substrates forming an interconnected network is evident from Figure 63(c). The observed

changes in the EMI SE and electrical resistivity of the graphene/cellulose composites at 10 GHz frequency are shown in Figure 64(a, b) [411]. It was noted that EMI SE for GVC and GAC composites increased gradually while the electrical resistivity decreased. After the first deposition layer, the EMI SE values were 3.3 and 5 dB for GVC and GAC respectively and after the tenth deposition layer, the EMI SE values were respectively increased to 26.1 and 28.3 dB for GVC-10 and GAC-10. It was evident that the low electrical resistivity was the key factor which generated enhanced EMI SE performance of graphene/cellulose composites through the formation of continuous conductive paths by densely stacked graphene platelets while cellulose helped in improving the impedance mismatch against external free space [411]. Figure 64(c) depicts the main EMI shielding mechanism of prepared composites which can be explained as the reflection of incident EM waves that were propagated through the composites was caused by low electrical resistivity while the dissipation of the part of the EM wave was mostly due to conductive network formation of the graphene/cellulose composite [411].

Figure 63: (a) Scheme showing the fabrication technique of the graphene/cellulose composite. (b) Flexibility demonstration of the graphene/cellulose composite and (c) SEM image revealing the firm stacking of graphene platelets on the cellulose substrates [411]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 64: Variation in the EMI SE values and the electrical resistivity at 10 GHz frequency for (a) GVC-X and (b) GAC-X. (c) Schematic diagram showing EMI shielding mechanism of GVC and GAC [411]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Wan et al. [412] prepared hybrid aerogels combining GO with cellulose using a facile solution mixing and subsequent regeneration–freeze-drying method. The introduction of GO influenced the micromorphology of the prepared aerogels. In addition, when GO was reduced by L-ascorbic acid, followed by the aerogels pyrolysis, the resulting hybrid aerogel exhibited superior electrical conductivity ($\sim 19.1 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) and outstanding EMI shielding properties with highest EMI SE value of 58.4 dB. The dominant shielding mechanism was absorption which is beneficial to attenuating secondary radiation thereby providing an attractive option for developing efficient EM radiation protective shields for electronic devices. Yang et al. [413] developed highly aligned composites derived from reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) using vacuum-assisted filtration and subsequent reduction using hydroiodic acid (HI). The rGO/CNF composite film having rGO content of 50 wt% and thickness of $\sim 23 \mu\text{m}$ exhibited outstanding electrical conductivity of $\sim 4057.3 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ and excellent EMI SE of $\sim 26.2 \text{ dB}$ because of the homogeneous dispersion and self-aligned layered rGO structure. In

another study, Kashi et al. prepared graphene nanoplatelet incorporated polylactic acid (PLA) and PBAT composites via melt mixing [414]. The EMI shielding characteristics of GNPs-reinforced PLA and PBT composites were investigated and in the X-band region. The efficient absorbance of 68% and 43% were obtained for PLA and PBAT composites respectively with 15 wt % GNPs content and sample thickness of 1 mm. when the addition of GNPs is close to ~ 15 wt%. In another work, the same group of authors [415], reported the EMI shielding characteristics of GNPs reinforced PLA composites. The prepared composites displayed higher EMI SE values which were increased with enhanced GNPs loading in the PLA matrix. In addition, the EMI SE values were frequency dependent at higher loading of GNPs and showed the opposite trend when lower content of GNPs was used. Moreover, the primary shielding mechanism was reflection and the effective absorbance of over 80% was noted for PLA composites with a thickness of 1.5 mm in the entire X-band frequency range [415].

Bai et al., [416], developed bacterial cellulose (BC) and RGO-based multifunctional aerogels with unidirectional cellular structures using freeze-drying and pyrolysis techniques for EMI shielding applications. Here, BC worked as a carbon source and GO worked as the reinforcing filler. Typically, the prepared aerogel displayed the filler loading compression loading dependent EM wave absorption properties. A significant enhancement in EM wave absorption capacity was observed with negligible reflection loss of -46.11 dB and maximum absorption bandwidth of 9.12 GHz for the 2.70 mm thick sample at 10 wt% loading of reduced graphene oxide at applied compression strain of 70%. The study paves the way for developing novel, multifunctional EM wave absorption materials. In another work, Huo et al. [417], prepared flexible, lightweight Janus films comprising graphene nanosheets and BC via a vacuum-assisted filtration technique. The prepared graphene nanosheet incorporated BC Janus films exhibited excellent EMI shielding characteristics in the X-band region. Figure 65(a) depicts the electrical conductivity of graphene nanosheet incorporated BC Janus films with respect to graphene nanosheet content. The electrical conductivity was improved with enhanced graphene nanosheet content and highest conductivity of 1261 S cm^{-1} was reached when the graphene nanosheet content was 44 mg in the graphene nanosheets/BC Janus film. The inset images in Figure 65(a) of small bulbs lighting up upon application of 3V input voltage further confirms the outstanding electrical conductivity of the prepared films. The enhanced electrical conductivity played a vital role in enhancing the EMI shielding property of graphene nanosheets/BC Janus films as depicted in Figure 65(b, c). In addition, the EMI SE values were improved with increasing graphene nanosheet loading and the highest value of 70 dB was

achieved when the graphene nanosheet content was 44 mg (GNs/BCs-4) [417]. In addition, the primary shielding mechanism was reflection while the absorption helped in varying the EMI SE values of graphene nanosheets/BC Janus films with varying electrical conductivity. The EMI shielding mechanism of graphene nanosheets/BC Janus films is presented schematically in Figure 65(d) which explains that the majority of the incident EM waves were reflected back in the air upon interaction with the surface of the graphene nanosheets/BC Janus films by virtue of high conductivity of graphene nanosheets. Some of the EM waves were entered into the film and some were transmitted through the film. Moreover, due to electrical polarization and electrical conductivity loss, EM waves were absorbed and turned into heat energy [417].

Figure 65: (a-c) Electrical conductivity (inset: images of small bulbs showing electrical conductivity test), EMI SE in the X-band and SE_R, SE_A and SE graphs of GNs/BCs Janus films at 12.4 GHz. (d) Illustration of EMI shielding mechanism [417]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Yang et al. [418], reported graphene/nanocellulose (NC) films as sustainable EMI shielding material which were prepared using in-situ exfoliation and NC-assisted ball milling process as depicted in Figure 66. Using this process, a series of composite films with different thicknesses (5, 10, 20, 40, 80, and 160 μm) were prepared. A cationic crosslinking strategy was

exercised to maximize the electrical conductivity and EMI shielding characteristics of graphene/NC composite films via cation- π interaction between the metal and graphene. For this, the prepared graphene/NC composite films were dipped into 0.05 M metal salt solutions (NaCl, CaCl₂, CuCl₂, FeCl₃, AlCl₃, ZnCl₂) followed by rinsing and vacuum-drying at 60°C to get graphene/NC composite films which were used for EMI shielding measurement. Figure 67 (a) depicts the EMI shielding performance of graphene/NC films of varied thickness without metal cation crosslinking. It was evident that EMI SE values were improved with enhanced film thickness and the highest EMI SE of 30.9 dB was achieved for 160 μ m thick film. On the other hand, the conductivity initially increased for the films with thickness 10, 20 and 40 μ m and with further increase in thickness (80 and 160 μ m), the conductivity decreased as shown in Figure 67(b). This could be due to increased conductive paths of graphene and increased amount of NC with an increase in film thickness. The electron transport in graphene is restricted by NC thereby decreasing the conductivity of thicker films [418]. The average SE_A and SE_R of graphene/NC films with varied thicknesses are shown in Figure 67(c). Both SE_A and SE_R values were increased with increased thickness. In particular, SE_A and SE_R values of 11.2, 20.9, 20.0, and 7.3, 6.8, and 12.2 dB were respectively obtained for 40, 80, and 160 μ m thick films. The A, R, and T coefficients of the films with varied thickness is shown in Figure 67(d). The values of T coefficients were gradually decreased, and the values of R coefficients were increased with an increase in film thickness indicating improved EMI shielding performance of the composites. In particular, the A values of 0.17 and 0.06, and the R values of 0.81 and 0.94 were obtained for 40 and 160 μ m thick films. The effect of metal cation crosslinking on EMI SE values of 40 μ m thick graphene/NC films is shown in Figure 68. A notable increase in the conductivity and EMI shielding properties of graphene/NC films was achieved due to crosslinking by metal cations. Figure 68(a) shows SE_T values of mechanically exfoliated and metal cation cross-linked films. For comparison, uncross-linked samples using the traditional blending method and uncross-linked mechanically exfoliated films were also prepared. The SE_T values of mechanically exfoliated films were greater than the values of uncross-linked traditional blend samples as well as uncross-linked mechanically exfoliated samples. The SE_T values increased to 18.1 dB for the uncross-linked mechanically exfoliated film as compared to the traditional blend sample (1.0 dB). Figure 68(b) presents the electrical conductivity of metal cation cross-linked films. For uncross-linked samples, the electrical conductivity increased from 67 S/m for the traditional blend sample to 1286 S/m for the mechanically exfoliated film (1819% increase). For cross-linked samples, the conductivity was further increased with the

values of 3172, 2617, 1786, 2159, 1547 and 1533 S/m obtained for the GCF-Cu, GCF-Fe, GCF-Ca, GCF-Na, GCF-Zn and GCF-Al, samples respectively. [Figure 68\(c\)](#) shows the SE_A and SE_R values of cross-linked samples. In particular, for all the samples, the SE_R values were higher and the values were 16.8, 11.7, 12.6, 15.2, 11.4, and 11.5 dB for the GCF-Cu, GCF-Fe, GCF-Ca, GCF-Na, GCF-Zn and GCF-Al, respectively [\[418\]](#). The A, R, and T coefficients of the cross-linked films are shown in [Figure 68\(d\)](#). High T values were obtained for conventional blend samples with weak EMI shielding properties. The presence of metal ions causes an increase in conductivity of GCF which subsequently increases the reflection attenuation and interfacial polarization. The values of R coefficients were found to be 0.98, 0.93, 0.95, 0.97, 0.93 and 0.93 for the GCF-Cu, GCF-Fe, GCF-Ca, GCF-Na, GCF-Zn and GCF-Al, respectively. Thus, the reflection attenuation was the dominant shielding mechanism of cross-linked films. [Figure 68\(e\)](#) presents the EMI shielding and metal cations crosslinking mechanism of GCFs. The NC particles were absorbed on the graphene surface while the metal cations helped in crosslinking NC particles and creating cation- π interaction with the metal cations and graphene. The overall mechanism was helpful in enhancing the conductivity and EMI shielding ability of the thin graphene/NC composite films [\[418\]](#).

Figure: 66: Schematic diagram showing synthesis process of cation cross-linked graphene/NC films [\[418\]](#). Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 67: (a) EMI SE_T , (b) electrical conductivity, (c, d) Average SE_A , SE_R , A, R, and T coefficients for uncross-linked graphene/NC composites films of varied thickness [418]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 68: (a) EMI SE_T , (b) electrical conductivity, (c, d) Average SE_A , SE_R , A, R, and T coefficients for uncross-linked traditional graphite/NC blend films, uncross-linked and cross-linked GCF with different cations. (e) EMI shielding and crosslinking mechanism of GCFs [418]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Hu et al. [419], reported a very simple sol-gel-compression film-forming technology to develop highly conductive and flexible film derived from expanded graphite (EG), silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and sodium alginate (SA) based aerogels. Figure 69 demonstrates the synthesis steps of EG/AgNPs/SA composites. The compression molding was used to effectively promote the conductive network formation considering the material's thickness and flexibility. The synthesized 0.16 mm thick EG/AgNPs/SA composite exhibited a maximum conductivity of 12,600 S/m, and an excellent EMI SE value of 40.1 dB. Figure 70(a) depicts the conductivity graphs of EG/AgNPs/SA composites. It was noted that at 10 mg/mL silver nitrate (AgNO_3) concentration and with different EG/SA mass ratios of 0, 0.2, 0.6, 1.0, 1.4, and 1.8, the conductivity values were 2.3×10^{-4} , 0.0016, 480, 4400, 10,600, 12,600 S/m, respectively. The 1.8-EG/SA composite exhibited conductivity of 10^9 orders of magnitude greater as compared with 0-EG/SA composite. This may be due to the deterioration of the network of SA molecular chains by reduced AgNPs which further improved the interaction and helped in the development of the EG/AgNPs conductive network [419]. Figure 70 (b-d) presents the EMI SE values of the EG/AgNPs/SA composite films with varied AgNO_3 concentrations in the X-band region. The EMI SE values were increased with increasing AgNO_3 concentrations and the highest EMI SE value was reached up to 41.8 dB at an AgNO_3 concentration of 20 mg/mL. In addition, at 10 mg/mL concentration of AgNO_3 , the EMI SE values were increased with increasing EG/SA mass ratio and the average values reached up to 40.2 dB for 1.8-EG/SA, which was forty times more as compared to 0-EG/SA (Figure 70 (c)). Moreover, the average EMI SE value for 1.0-EG/SA was 27.8 dB, which is also sufficient for the general requirement (20 dB) of commercial applications [419]. Figure 71 shows the EMI shielding mechanism of EG/AgNPs/SA composite film. As depicted in Figure 71(a), when the EM waves are passed through the EG/AgNPs/SA composite surface, some portion of it was reflected owing to the different impedance resulting from the ample mobile electrons present on the film surface. Secondly, the defects such as doping of oxygen atom and destruction of chemical bond on the EG surface created uneven distribution or assembly of electron cloud causing polarization loss, which absorbs energy of the EM waves (Figure 71(b)). Besides, a layered conductive network was established via several conducting EG/AgNPs interfaces and insulating interfaces of SA. When the remaining EM waves are passed through the EG/AgNPs/SA composite film a conductive network was formed through EG/AgNPs interaction which is shown in Figure 71(c). The charges were gathered at the two-phase interface due to different electrical properties, resulting in interface polarization loss [419].

Figure 69: Synthesis steps of EG/AgNPs/SA composite film [419]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 70: (a) Electrical conductivity, (b–d) EMI SE values of EG/AgNPs/SA composites at varied AgNO_3 concentrations [419]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 71: EMI shielding mechanism of EG/AgNPs/SA composite film [419]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Li et al., [420], developed multi-layered composites using porous aerogels based on CNF and rGO as potential EMI shielding material and obtained a maximum EMI SE value of 32 dB. Han et al., [421], fabricated CNF and Ni-anchored graphene-based magnetic film for EMI shielding application. First, Ni(OH)₂ nanoparticles were synthesized using a hydrothermal reaction as shown in Figure 72(a). Later, the *in-situ* thermal reduction method was used to prepare Ni nanoribbons anchored magnetic graphene hybrids (TRGO@Ni) (Figure 72(b)). In addition, the ultrathin CNF/TRGO@Ni hybrid films with high flexibility and nacre-like structure were obtained using a simple vacuum filtration technique (Figure 72(c)). From the DC electrical conductivity studies of the CNF/TRGO@Ni hybrid films, it was noted that the incorporation of a small quantity of Ni nanoparticles led to significant enhancement in the conductivity of the hybrids owing to the interaction between the Ni nanoparticles and stacked graphene sheets [421]. The fabricated CNF/TRGO@Ni film exhibited a maximum electrical conductivity of 262.7 S/m while that of CNF/TRGO composite was 21.1 S/m. Furthermore, the EMI SE values of CNF/TRGO and CNF/TRGO@Ni hybrids at 50 wt% filler content in the X and K-band regions were obtained. All the hybrid films exhibited stable EMI SE values in both frequency ranges. In particular, CNF/TRGO composite film exhibited low EMI SE values ranging from 10–14 dB in the X and K band regions due to poor or low electrical conductivity. In contrast, CNF/TRGO@Ni 2-1 and 1-1 hybrid films exhibited EMI SE values greater than 20 dB with average SE_T values of 25.1 and 32.2 dB respectively in the X band region, owing to enhanced conductivity and magnetic loss endowed by Ni nanoparticles [421]. The average

SE_T , SE_R and SE_A values were also calculated. All the samples displayed higher SE_A values in both the regions investigated. For instance; CNF/TRGO@Ni 1-1 hybrid film exhibited average SE_A values of 20.8 and 23.8 dB in both the X and K band as compared to SE_R values (11.4 and 11.3 dB respectively) indicating the absorption dominant shielding mechanism of both CNF/TRGO and CNF/TRGO@Ni hybrid films. Moreover, a negligible change in the SE_T values was observed with respect to the increase in the nanofiller loading and the trend of SE_A was similar to SE_T values which further confirms at higher content of TRGO@Ni filler. The authors further demonstrated the lightening of the LED bulb during the bending process to further confirm the flexibility of the CNF/TRGO@Ni 1-1 hybrid film at higher filler loading (50 wt%). As depicted in Figure 73, the authors further explained a three-step shielding mechanism based on macroscopic reflection and absorption, multiple reflection and synergistic loss of CNF/TRGO@Ni composite films [421].

Figure 72 (a): Diagrammatic representation of the preparation method of TRGO@Ni hybrid. (b) Photographs showing magnetic effect of TRGO and TRGO@Ni. (c) Illustration of the filtration process used to fabricate CNF/TRGO@Ni film. (d) Photos of the prepared CNF/TRGO@Ni films showing bending and folding ability [421]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 73: Pictorial representation of EMI shielding mechanisms: (a) Macroscopic reflection and absorption, (b) Multi-reflection and (c) Synergetic loss [421]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Zhang et al. [422], reported nano composite films based on CNFs/FLG as EMI shielding material. The EMI SE was investigated in the frequency range of 300 MHz-1.5 GHz for a 13 mm thick sample. All CNF/FLG (CG) composite films displayed frequency-independent EMI SE properties; however, the EMI SE values decreased with increasing passing time. The maximum EMI SE value of 36 dB was obtained after the first passing cycle and it further decreased to 32 dB after 5 passing cycles due to disturbance in the conduction of electrons caused by non-homogeneously dispersed FLG [422]. Li et al. [423], studied multi-layered CNF/graphene film with excellent flexibility and EMI shielding ability. The highest EMI SE value of 27.4 dB was obtained attributing to the large difference in impedance and multiple reflections caused by the unique multi-layered structure [423]. Luo et al. [424], studied GNPs reinforced poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) composite foams for EMI shielding applications. The composite foams were prepared using ScCO_2 and the ball milling was used to create the network structure of GNPs. The highest EMI SE values of composite foam reached up to 27.4 dB cm^3/g at 6 wt % loading of GNPs. Wan et al. [425], studied graphene-incorporated cellulose fiber aerogels as outstanding EMI shielding materials. The ultralight and superelastic CF/TRGO composite aerogels were prepared using lyophilisation and carbonization process keeping the mass ratio of CF and GO as 2:1. The prepared aerogels

were thermally treated under 5% Hydrogen-Argon conditions. The samples designated as CF2G1-1000H indicate the CF/GO weight ratio as 2:1 and the annealing temperature of 1000 °C. Figure 74(a, b) depicts the synthesis process and the microstructure of the prepared CF/TRGO aerogel. The SEM analysis of the aerogel revealed a sponge like cellular structure with a 3D interconnected network which benefitted in enhancing the electrical conductivity and EMI shielding characteristics of the prepared aerogels. The 5 mm thick CF/TRGO aerogel annealed at 1000°C exhibited excellent EMI SE value (47.8 dB) as depicted in Figure 74(c, d). The excellent EMI SE values of the prepared aerogel were mostly ascribed to the cellular structure and enhanced conductivity. The compressive behaviour of CF/TRGO aerogels was also evaluated using an in-plane compression test. As shown in Figure 74(e), the compressive stress of CF2G1 aerogel annealed at 1000°C didn't change much after 10 cycles which indicates good deformation of cell-wall structure, excellent elastic properties and cycling stability of the prepared aerogels [425].

Figure 74: (a) Pictorial representation of synthesis process of CF/graphene aerogel (b) SEM micrograph of prepared aerogel, (c, d) Total EMI SE of 5 mm thick CF2G1 aerogel in 8.2-18 GHz frequency range after different treatments, and (e) Compressive stress of CF2G1 at 1000°C under 5% H₂-Ar mixture [425]. Copyright 2017. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Shi et al. [426], reported 3D printed PLA/graphene composites with superior EMI shielding properties. Using this approach, a homogeneous dispersion of graphene nanosheets was achieved in the PLA matrix even at higher loading of graphene nanosheets (9.08 vol%). The 3D printed composites exhibited excellent EMI shielding characteristics with a maximal EMI SE value of 35.8 dB at 2.4 GHz frequency. Lai et al. [427], studied graphene-incorporated self-healing hydrogels based on chitosan (CS), polyacrylic acid (PAA), and amorphous calcium carbonate (ACC). The prepared hydrogels exhibited remarkable stretching, shape adaptability, adhesiveness, durability and self-healing characteristics. Furthermore, the hydrogels exhibited an exceptional EMI SE value of 90.6 dB at 4.76 wt % of RGO content in the polymer matrix and the excellent EMI shielding performance was maintained even after several stretching and self-healing cycles under harsh conditions. The authors concluded that the synergic effect of conducting RGO network, water content and the porous structure played a key role in enhancing the EMI shielding characteristics of the hydrogels [427]. Yang et al. [428], reported a cost-efficient method for the synthesis of graphene-incorporated NC composites. The prepared NC/graphene composite displayed outstanding EMI shielding properties and the maximal EMI SE value of 43 dB was obtained for 13 μm thick film. In another work, a facile, green co-precipitation method was used by Chen et al. [429], to develop cellulose/RGO/Fe₃O₄ based aerogels for EMI shielding applications. The EMI SE values of 0.5 mm thick cellulose/RGO/Fe₃O₄ aerogel were noted in the range of 32.4–40.1 dB in the X-band region when RGO and Fe₃O₄ loading was 8 and 15 wt % respectively. Moreover, with the increase in the aerogel thickness from 0.5 to 2 mm, the EMI SE values were improved significantly and the maximum values in the range of 49.4–52.4 dB were obtained for 2 mm thick aerogel. The shielding mechanism was absorption-dominant. Another study based on lightweight compressible CNF/RGO aerogels for EMI shielding application was reported by Li et al. [430]. The prepared unidirectional aerogels exhibited excellent EMI shielding properties in the X band with a maximal value of 33 dB demonstrating the potential of becoming a promising EMI shielding material. Table 4 summarizes EMI SE values of graphene-based various BPNCs which exhibited diverse range of EMI SE values depending on filler type, structure, and thickness. For example; cellulose and CNF-based graphene composites displayed EMI SE values between 25–40 dB, while PLA-based composites exhibited moderate (15–36 dB) EMI SE values. In addition, incorporating magnetic particles such as Fe₃O₄, Ni, or metal nanoparticles such as Ag, Fe, or aerogel/porous architectures along with graphene based nanofiller, substantially enhances EMI SE values through absorption-dominant shielding mechanism

because of the multiple scattering and conductive pathways in BPNCs. Thus, graphene based BPNCs are effective as lightweight, flexible, and sustainable EMI shielding materials.

Table 4: EMI SE values of graphene based various BPNCs.

Biopolymer/graphene composite	Filler content (Wt%/Vol%)	Frequency (GHz)	Sample Thickness	EMI SE (dB)	Ref.
CNF/RGO/NR	30 wt% RGO	8.2–12.4	0.1 mm	25.81	[327]
Graphene/cellulose	-	8.2–12.4	43 μ m	28.3	[411]
PLA/GNP nanocomposites	15 wt % GNP	8.2–12.4	1.5 mm	15.5	[415]
BC/Graphene	-	8.2–12.4	60 μ m	76	[417]
Nanocellulose/graphene	Mass ratio of 1:1	8.2–12.4	40 μ m	27.7	[418]
EG/AgNPs/SA	EG/SA mass ratio of 1:8	8.2–12.4	16 mm	40.1	[419]
CNF/rGO aerogels	-	8.2–12.4	3 mm	32	[420]
CNF/TRGO@Ni film	50 wt% TRGO@Ni	8.2–26.5	1 mm	32.2	[421]
CNF/graphene	5 % GNS	8.2–12.4	35 μ m	27.4	[423]
CF/RGO aerogel	-	8.2–18	5 mm	47.8	[425]
PLA/GNs nanocomposites	0.08 wt% GNS	8.2–12.4	2 mm	35.8	[426]
RGO/PAA/CS/ACC hydrogel	4.76 wt %	8.2–12.4	9.71 mm	125	[427]
Nanocellulose/graphene nanosheets	90 wt % graphene nanosheets	8.2–12.4	13 μ m	43	[428]
Cellulose/RGO/Fe ₃ O ₄ aerogels	8 wt% RGO/15 wt% Fe ₃ O ₄	8.2–12.4	2 mm	49.4–52.4	[429]
CNF/RGO aerogels	Mass ratio of 1:1	8.2–12.4	3-5 mm	33	[430]
CNF/GO/PMMA aerogels	20 %	8.2–12.4	4 mm	36.75	[431]
RGO/iron pentacarbonyl (IP)/CS composites	-	8.2–59.6	0.3 mm	>38	[432]
RGO/CNF composite	Ni/RGO to CNF ratio of 3:1	8.2–12.4	105 μ m	22.6	[433]
Waste wood cellulose fiber (WWCF)/GNP composites	15 wt%	8.2–12.4	0.66 mm	72.5	[434]

PLA/Oil palm empty fruit bunch (OPEFB)/RGO composites	8 wt % RGO	8–12	6 mm	31.2	[435]
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5.5 Conducting Polymers Based Graphene Composites

Conducting polymers have been extensively studied and found to be the right choice for EMI shielding applications by virtue of their easy synthesis, lightweight, adaptability and corrosion-resistant properties. In addition, the properties of conducting polymers can be tuned through functionalization or surface modification during the synthesis process and by incorporating suitable nanofillers [436, 437]. Several studies have demonstrated the utilization of conducting polymers integrated with graphene and its derivatives as a promising candidate for EMI shielding applications by virtue of their high electrical conductivity, lightweight and high aspect ratio. Further, it was demonstrated that at higher graphene content in the polymer matrix, the dielectric loss increases by virtue of the high electrical conductivity of graphene [436-438]. Moreover, graphene facilitates enhanced electron transport in conducting polymers thereby increasing the overall electrical conductivity and as a result, the EMI SE of the composites also increases through absorption or reflection mechanisms [439, 440]. For instance; Pal et al [436], reported a chemical synthesis approach to prepare graphene/PANI composites for EMI shielding applications. Graphene loading in the PANI matrix was varied as 2, 4, 6 and 8 wt % and the samples were designated as G1, G2, G3 and G4. Figure 75(a-c) shows the obtained plots of SE_A , SE_R and SE_T of PANI/graphene composites revealing that the EMI SE values were dependent on both frequency as well as graphene loading. As indicated in Figure 75(a), the SE_A increased with increasing graphene content. The minimum SE_A value of 16 dB was obtained for pristine PANI (G0 sample) while PANI/graphene composite with 8 wt % graphene (G4 sample) exhibited a maximum SE_A value of 49 dB at 8.2 GHz. The enhanced SE_A values with increasing graphene content in the PANI matrix were ascribed to improved electrical conductivity, high aspect ratio, multiple internal reflections and skin depth [436]. The SE_R plots of PANI/graphene composites are depicted in Figure 75(b). It was noted that for all the samples, the SE_R values were constant and the lowest value of 9 dB was obtained for pristine PANI (G0 sample) while a maximum value of 13 dB was obtained for the G4 sample at 8.2 GHz. The SE_T plots for samples G0 to G4 with respect to graphene loading and frequency are depicted in Figure 75(c). The SE_T values were increased with increasing graphene loading and the maximum value of 61 dB was obtained at 8.2 GHz for composite with 8 wt % graphene

loading in PANI matrix (G4 sample). Moreover, the SE_T values of all the PANI/graphene composites were more than 30 dB, which satisfies the requirements of industrial/commercial applications. For comparison, authors also investigated the SE_T values of G0, G1 and G4 samples of thickness 1 mm and 2 mm as depicted in [Figure 75\(d\)](#). The SE_T values were persistent even after the thickness was decreased. Nevertheless, the SE_T value of G4 sample decreased from 64 dB to 49 dB when the thickness was decreased from 2 mm to 1 mm. [Figure 75\(e\)](#) shows the dependence of EMI SE on the graphene loading and it was evident that the EMI shielding performance of PANI/graphene was increased with an increased graphene loading. [Figure 76](#) demonstrates the contribution of absorption, reflection and multiple internal reflections in attenuating EM waves using PANI/graphene composites [436].

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Figure 75: (a, b) EMI SE values obtained through absorption and reflection, (c) Total EMI SE v/s. frequency, (d) Total EMI SE v/s frequency for 1 mm and 2 mm thick samples and (e) Variation in EMI SE with respect to graphene loading in PANI matrix [436]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 76: EMI shielding mechanism of PANI/graphene composites [436]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Kumari et al. [437], prepared graphene-reinforced poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) and PANI composite films via in-situ chemical polymerization technique (Figure 77) and studied their EMI shielding properties in the 12.4-18 GHz (microwave frequency range). The authors stated that the *in situ* chemical polymerization approach rendered controllable growth of the PEDOT and PANI layers on graphene surface. The prepared composite samples were designated as PG (PEDOT/graphene), PANIG (PANI/graphene), and PPG (PEDOT/PANI/graphene). The synergistic interaction between PEDOT and PANI at the composite interfaces led to enhanced EMI shielding performance. Figure 78(a-c) depicts SE_A , SE_R and SE_T plots of all the prepared samples. The EMI SE values were influenced by material composition as well as frequency. As shown in Figure 78(a), the SE_A values were increased with the addition of graphene in the polymer matrices. The SE_A values of 20.9, 26.33, 27.56, 39.19, and 36.17 dB were obtained at 18 GHz for PANI, PEDOT, PANIG, PG, and PPG composites. The improved SE_A values with varying sample compositions were attributed to high surface-to-volume ratio, increased electrical conductivity, skin depth effect and various internal reflections occurred at the graphene surface [436, 437]. The SE_R plots of the composites are depicted in Figure 78(b) which indicates the lowest SE_R value (4.1 dB) for PANIG and a higher SE_R value (7.5 dB) for PG at 18 GHz. The influence of both absorption and reflection

on the EMI SE was obvious and both the parameters were increased due to increased conductivity of the composites. The lowest SE_T value of 25.08 was observed for PANI and the maximal SE_T value of 42.93 dB was achieved for PPG at 18 GHz (Figure 78(c)). These results further indicate that SE_T values of all the specimens are larger than 20 dB which is required to fulfill the minimum EMI SE criteria to neglect the multiple internal reflections present in the specimen while absorption being the primary shielding mechanism [437]. In addition, the effect of sample thickness on the EMI shielding properties of PPG was investigated (Fig. 78(d)). It was noted that with the increase in sample thickness from 1.45 mm to 3.48 mm, the total EMI SE increased from 32.61 dB to 54.60 dB for PPG samples. Figure 79 depicts the overall shielding mechanisms that influence the attenuation of EM waves through prepared composites [437].

Figure 77: Pictorial representation of synthesis process of graphene reinforced PEDOT and PANI composites [437]. Copyright 2024. Adapted from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Figure 78: (a) SE_A, (b) SE_R, and (c) SE_T plots of all specimens with respect to frequency, (d) SE_T plot of PPG v/s sample thickness (t) [437]. Copyright 2024. Adapted from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Figure 79: Schematic illustration of possible EMI shielding mechanism in PPG samples [437]. Copyright 2024. Adapted from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Mohan et al. [439], prepared freestanding PANI/graphene composites using solution intercalation for EMI shielding. The EMI SE values for the prepared composites were obtained in the C and X band region i.e. 4-12 GHz frequency range. The maximal EMI SE value of 42 dB was achieved in the 4-8 GHz frequency range while in the X-band region (8-12 GHz) the EMI SE value obtained was 32 dB which corresponds to over 99.99% attenuation of microwaves. Moreover, a significant contribution from reflection was noted in the entire frequency range investigated as compared to absorption. Thus, the authors concluded that these hybrid films can be utilized as reflection-dominated EMI shielding materials in a wide range of EM spectrum. Wu et al. [440], produced composites based on graphene foam (GF) and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS) exhibiting ultralow density ($18.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3$) and high porosity (98.8%) for superior EMI shielding performance by drop coating of PEDOT: PSS on independent GF which exhibited circular morphology. The superior electrical conductivity, porous and lightweight structure, and efficient charge delocalization, the composites displayed tremendous improvement in EMI shielding properties with a maximum EMI SE of 91.9 dB and a specific SE (SSE) of 3124 $\text{dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$. Figure 80 shows the EMI SE values of GF/PEDOT: PSS composites with varied mass ratios in the X-band region. With an increase in mass ratio of GF/PEDOT: PSS from 1 to 4.6, the SE_A values were increased consistently while negligible change in the SE_R values ranging between 9 to 13 dB was observed (Figure 80(a)). The GF/PEDOT: PSS-1 composite exhibited low electrical conductivity of 22.3 S/cm and an average SE_T value of 69.1 dB, while the GF/PEDOT: PSS-4.6 composite exhibited high electrical conductivity of 55.2 S/cm with a high average SE_T value of 91.9 dB (Figure 80(b, c)). Moreover, for all the composites, it was observed that the contribution of SE_A was over 80% of the total EMI SE and that of SE_R was insignificant. This indicates the dominant attenuation of microwaves into thermal energy. As shown in Figure 80(c), GF/PEDOT: PSS composites exhibited high SSE values with a maximum SSE of 3124 $\text{dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$ was obtained for GF/PEDOT: PSS-1 and the lower SSE value of 1206 $\text{dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$ was observed for GF/PEDOT: PSS-4.6 [440].

Figure 80: EMI SE of GF/PEDOT: PSS composite of various compositions vs. frequency (a, b) SE_A and SE_R , and SE_T vs mass ratio (c) SEs, SSEs and SSEs [440]. Copyright 2017. Reproduced with permission from The American Chemical Society.

Ignihor et al. [441], synthesized graphite nanoplatelets reinforced PEDOT:PSS composites and evaluated their EMI shielding properties in the X-band frequency region. It was noted that adding 0.5 wt % graphite nanoplatelets to PEDOT:PSS led to an EMI SE value of 30 dB and for 25 wt % graphite nanoplatelet content in the composite, the EMI SE value up to 70 dB was attained with a sample thickness of 0.8 mm. The absorption was the primary shielding mechanism. Khasim et al., [442] prepared composites based on *para*-toluene sulphonic acid (p-TSA) doped PANI and GNPs via in situ polymerization technique. The thickness of the prepared composite film was 1.5 mm. The EMI shielding properties of GNPs-reinforced PANI composites were investigated in the X-band frequency range. It was noted that EMI SE values of the prepared composites were strongly dependent on the content of PANI and GNPs. The in-situ polymerization of aniline in presence of GNPs resulted in an improved interfacial polarization through charge transfer between PANI and GNPs causing high microwave

absorption. It was noted that 10 wt % of GNPs in the PANI matrix led to attenuation of about 95% EM waves in the X-band frequency range with absorption as the primary EMI shielding mechanism. Wu et al. [443], reported a two-step procedure to prepare sponge-like PPy/RGO (S-PPy/RGO) aerogel composites for EMI shielding. The reduction of GO was carried out using a hydrothermal process. The total EMI shielding displayed typical filler loading-dependent characteristics. For the composite with 15 wt % of S-PPy/RGO the SE_T values were over 10 dB thereby reaching effective EMI SE. The maximum reflection coefficient observed was -54.4 dB at 12.76 GHz. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of lightweight aerogel composites as outstanding EMI shielding material.

Cheng et al. [444], prepared flexible graphene/PANI/PI composite films via in situ polymerization and investigated their EMI shielding properties. In this work, graphene and PANI have been used as fillers and PI has been as a matrix. Figure 81(a, b) displays the SE_T values of prepared composites with varied content of graphene and PANI. The SE_T values of graphene/PI and graphene/PANI/PI composites were increased when the graphene/PANI content was increased to 30 to 40 % which may be due to an enhanced electrical conductivity of the composites [444]. The SE_T value of graphene/PANI/PI composite at 40% content of graphene/PANI was found to be ~ 21.3 dB while that of graphene/PI composite was ~ 17.1 dB which is about 125% less than the SE_T values of graphene/PANI/PI composite (Figure 81 (c)). The higher EMI SE values of graphene/PANI/PI composite than that of graphene/PI composites were ascribed to the conductive network establishment between graphene and PANI. Moreover, the uniform dispersion of graphene in graphene/PANI/PI composite helped in the easy attenuation of EM waves via reflection and scattering while the incident EM waves were absorbed and converted to heat. The EMI shielding mechanism of graphene/PANI/PI composite is depicted in Figure 81(d) which indicate that part of the EM waves were reflected at the interface of the composite film due to conductive network formation and accumulation of charge carriers while the remaining EM waves penetrated through the surfaces were reflected or absorbed by graphene layers. Thus, the establishment of a conducting network between graphene and PANI in the PI matrix resulted in an improved EMI shielding properties of the resulting composites [444].

Figure 81: (a) SE_T of Gr@PI; (b) SE_T of Gr-PANI_{10:1}@PI; (c) Average SE_T of Gr@PI and Gr-PANI_{10:1}@PI with different contents; (d) EMI shielding mechanism of Gr-PANI_{10:1}@PI composite where P_I , P_R and P_T represent incident, reflected and transmitted waves [444]. Copyright 2020. Adapted from the Royal Society of Chemistry.

et al. [445], synthesized novel composites based on PPy nanotube and ferrocene-modified GO by *in-situ* chemical oxidative polymerization. The EMI shielding properties of the synthesized composites were investigated in the frequency range of 1 to 4.5 GHz. The maximum EMI SE value of 28.73 dB was achieved for the composite with a thickness of 3.00 mm at 1.0175 GHz frequency. Xie et al. [446], studied graphene/CNTs/PPy composite films for EMI shielding applications. A 3D networked structure of graphene/CNTs/PPy was developed by electrochemical deposition to ascertain the enhanced EMI shielding performance of the composite. In this work, a skeleton was formed by graphene/CNTs substrate while PPy created a bridge between graphene and CNTs, forming a percolation network within the multiphase composite. An average EMI SE value of 59.6 dB was obtained in the X-band region for 249 μm thick composite film. Manna et al. [447], used the hydrothermal process to synthesize ternary composites based on RGO, Fe₃O₄ and PANI to be applied in the shielding

of EM pollutions. The prepared 0.5 mm thick RGO/Fe₃O₄/PANI composite exhibited a maximal EMI SE value of ~28 dB and the absorption is the primary shielding mechanism. Lin et al. [448], used GNPs, multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and PPy as hybrid fillers to produce PU composites via in situ chemical oxidation polymerization in the presence of hexadecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide as a cationic surfactant. The EMI shielding characteristics of GNPs/MWCNTs/PPy/PU hybrids were investigated. The authors noted that the EMI shielding performance of the prepared hybrid was substantially enhanced due to interfacial polarization between GNPs, MWCNTs, PPy and PU. The EMI SE values of hybrids within the range of 35-40 dB in the 30-1800 MHz frequency range were found to be sufficient for efficiently eliminating the 99.9% of EM waves. Taj et al. [449], prepared PEDOT/GNPs composites using in situ chemical oxidation polymerization with varied concentrations of GNPs (1, 5, 10 and 15 wt %) and studied their EMI shielding performance in the X-band region. The maximum EMI SE of about 17.6 dB was noted for PEDOT/GNPs composites with GNPs content of 15 wt % (PG15) indicating the attenuation of about 90% of incident waves with major contribution from the absorption mechanism. Using a similar synthesis approach, Gill et al. [450], produced a PPy/graphene composite with varied content of graphene from 0 to 0.2 wt % and investigated their EMI shielding performance in the X-band region. The maximum EMI SE of ~ 33 dB was noted for PPy/graphene composites with 0.2 wt % of graphene loading (PG2) mostly due to the absorption dominated mechanism. Moreover, the PG2 composite exhibited a very low value of skin depth (~250 μm) and enhanced attenuation constant. Thus, the improved microwave absorption properties of PG2 composite can be ascribed to improved dielectric loss resulting from conductive pathways, interfacial polarization and multiple relaxation [450]. In another study, Joshi et al. [451], prepared graphene nanoribbon (GNR) incorporated PANI/epoxy composites for EMI shielding applications. The EMI shielding performance of the PANI/epoxy/GNR composite was investigated in the X-band region by varying GNR content and the film thickness. With an increase in GNR/PANI content from 2.5 wt % to 5 wt %, the EMI SE increased from -34 dB to -44 dB for the film with a thickness of 3.4 mm. The authors further concluded based on the findings that the absorption was the main shielding mechanism of the prepared composites.

Dalal et al. [452], prepared PEDOT/RGO composites via in-situ chemical oxidative polymerization in the presence of dodecyl benzene sulfonic acid (DBSA) which served as a surfactant. The EDOT monomer was emulsified using an emulsion polymerization technique in the presence of RGO and DBSA with a continuous water phase leading to the formation of

micelles having a hydrophobic tail at the centre and hydrophilic head along the continuous phase. The polymerization was initiated after adding ammonium peroxydisulphate (APS) followed by in-situ growth of PEDOT on the RGO layers as depicted in Figure 82 [452]. Using this procedure, varied compositions of PEDOT/RGO composites were prepared using different weight ratios of monomer to RGO as 1:0.025 (PG1), 1:0.05 (PG2), 1:0.1 (PG3) and 1:0.2 (PG4). The EMI shielding properties of PEDOT/RGO composites were investigated in the Ku band region. As shown in Figure 83, the maximum EMI SE due to absorption (SE_A) was found to be 34.9 dB for PG4 composites at 15 GHz while PG1, PG2, PG3 and PEDOT exhibited SE_A values of 34.7, 31.4, 34 and 28.4 dB respectively at 15 GHz. The enhanced EMI SE values were achieved for PEDOT/RGO composites owing to the high aspect ratio and enhanced impedance matching [452]. In addition, the SE_R values were found to be 8.0, 4.2, 4.2 and 1.5 dB for PG4, PG3, PG2, PG1 and PEDOT respectively at 15 GHz which confirms the absorption as a primary shielding mechanism of the composites. Moreover, the authors further investigated the effect of film thickness on the EMI SE. From Figure 84 it can be seen that SE_A increases from ~20 dB to ~35 dB when the thickness was improved from 1.5 mm to 2.5 mm and with further increase in thickness the SE_A values decrease. These results confirmed that the prepared composites can be implemented as a commercial material for EMI shielding applications [452]. Table 5 summarizes EMI SE values of graphene-based various CPNCs which showed varied EMI shielding performances resulted from the use of varied type of fillers, preparation of hybrids, and samples with varied thickness. This indicates that EMI shielding results of graphene based conducting polymer composites are strongly dependent on filler loading, dispersion state, and the sample thickness. Overall, combining graphene based materials together with magnetic or metal oxide nanoparticles into conducting polymer matrices resulted in an enhanced EMI shielding performance in a broad band frequency range with absorption-dominant shielding mechanism.

Figure 82: Schematic diagram showing synthesis procedure of PEDOT: RGO composites [452]. Copyright 2016. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

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Figure 83: SE_A and SE_R plots of PEDOT, PG1, PG2, PG3, and PG4 composites of 2.5 mm thickness with respect to frequency. Inset: $SE_A + SE_R$ plots vs. frequency [452]. Copyright 2016. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

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Figure 84: Variation in SE_A and SE_R values of PG4 composite with varied sample thickness [452]. Copyright 2016. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

Table 5: EMI SE values of graphene based various CPNCs.

Conducting Polymer-Graphene Composites	Filler content	Frequency (GHz)	Sample Thickness	EMI SE (dB)	Ref.
PEDOT/RGO/PbTiO ₃	0.5 wt% RGO + 4 wt % PbTiO ₃	12–18	2.5 mm	51.93	[287]
PANI/Graphene	8 wt % graphene	8.2-12.4	2 mm	~64	[436]
PVDF/PEDOT-block-PEG/GNPs/CuO	2 wt % GNP+20 wt% CuO	12-18	> 1 mm	17	[438]
S-PPy/RGO/Paraffin	15 wt % RGO	2-18	1.5-5 mm	~10	[443]
PEDOT/Graphene	15 wt %	8.2-12.4	-	17.6	[449]
PPy/Graphene	0.2 wt %	8.2-12.4	250 μ m	33	[450]

	graphene				
GNR/PANI/Epoxy	5 wt% GNR/PANI	8.2-12.4	3.4 mm	-44	[451]
PPy/BST/RGO/Fe ₃ O ₄	RGO/BST (1:2 wt ratio w.r.t. Fe ₃ O ₄)	8.2-12.4	2.5 mm	48	[453]
PANI/Ag@graphene	5 wt% Ag/graphene	0.45-1.5	1 mm	29.33	[454]
PVC/PANI/TRGO	5 wt% TRGO	11-20	> 1 mm	56	[455]
PANI/S-RGO/Paraffin	10 wt% S-RGO	1-20	5 mm	-22.5	[456]
PANI/BaFe ₁₂ O ₁₉ /MWCNT/RGO	5 wt% RGO	8.2-12.4	1 mm		[457]
PANI/MWCNT/thermally annealed graphene aerogel (TAGA)/epoxy	2.58 wt% PANI + 0.83 wt% MWCNT + 1.20 wt% TAGA	8.2-12.4	3 mm	42	[458]
PANI/RGO/Strontium ferrite	10 wt%	2-8	1.5 mm	-45.00	[459]
RGO/Fe ₃ O ₄ /PANI		2-8	0.5 mm	28	[460]
PEDOT/RGO/SrFe ₁₂ O ₁₉	0.5 wt% RGO + 2 wt % SrFe ₁₂ O ₁₉	8.2-12.4	2.5 mm	42.2	[461]

6. Factors Influencing the EMI Shielding Properties of Polymer Nanocomposites

PNCs are regularly being used for EMI shielding applications with controlled mechanical properties and varied EM behaviour. The EMI shielding phenomenon in PNCs depends on varied parameters such as frequency range, specimen weight, specimen thickness, filler type, intrinsic conductivity of filler, filler content, loading level of the filler, particle distribution, size and shape, environmental resistance and mechanical strength [462, 463]. The key influential parameters that significantly affect the EMI SE of PNCs are briefly discussed below [464-466].

6.1 Nature and Type of Polymer Matrix

Generally, different types of polymeric matrices i.e., polar and non-polar have been traditionally considered as excellent carriers for nanofillers. The polymer matrix plays a crucial

role in reducing nanofiller aggregations within the PNCs and enforces the upper limit of inorganic particle size [467]. The interfacial energy between the nanofiller and the polymer changes according to the polarity of the polymer matrix. Therefore, the nature of nanofiller dispersion will also be different for polar and non-polar polymers. For example, polar exhibits higher interfacial energy than non-polar polymers and thereby produces a homogeneous filler dispersion within the polymer matrix [465]. Therefore, the EMI SE values will differ for polar and non-polar polymers reinforced with the same nanofiller. Moreover, the higher values of EMI SE of PNCs are also governed by various other characteristics such as viscosity, crystallinity, and molecular weight of the polymer matrix. With low-viscosity polymer, an efficient nanofiller dispersion can be realized. In contrast, owing to high shear force, high viscosity polymer causes nanofiller breakdown during composite processing, which has a negative effect on the connectivity between the filler and the polymeric matrices [465]. It has been revealed that the EMI SE values were enhanced for low viscosity thermoplastic composites as compared with the high-viscosity one, compared at the same filler loading [468]. Besides, the EMI SE of crystalline polymer can be higher or lower than the amorphous polymer based on the crystallinity percentage (%) of the polymer and the interaction of the nanofiller particles with the polymer matrix [465]. Highly crystalline PNCs exhibit higher electrical conductivity with a low electrical percolation threshold at similar filler content. On the contrary, the connectivity of the filler particles is better in the amorphous region than in the crystalline region which leads to absorption and dissipation of EM radiations. However, some part of EM radiations is transmitted through the crystalline region owing to poor connectivity of filler particles. Furthermore, the molecular weight of the polymer also affects the EMI SE values of PNCs. Polymers having high molecular weight generally exhibit higher viscosity than low molecular weight polymer matrices [465]. Other than this, PNCs based on conducting polymers have also been utilized as an efficient EMI shielding material owing to their easy production, high conductivity, and remarkable electric and dielectric properties [469-471]. On the other hand, electrically insulating polymers are transparent to EM waves and hence they exhibit extremely low EMI SE values (0-3 dB) influenced by their type and nature. Therefore, insulating polymers must be reinforced with suitable conducting filler for effectively enhancing their EMI SE [464]. Thus, in a nutshell, the nature of the polymer matrix affects the EMI SE of PNCs.

6.2 Type, Geometry and Loading Level of Nanofiller

The EMI SE of PNCs varies according to the type and geometry of the nanofiller integrated into the polymer matrix. Nanofillers generally improve the EMI SE of PNCs and influence properties such as conductivity, permeability, permittivity, absorption, and mechanical strength [464]. The nanofillers could be metallic, carbon-based materials such as carbon black, carbon fibres, CNTs, graphene, GO, RGO, GQDs, conducting polymers, etc. Generally, dielectric, conducting, or ferromagnetic nanofillers are incorporated in insulating polymer matrices. The integration of dielectric or magnetic nanofillers in the polymer matrix leads to improvement in the EM properties of PNCs resulting in a maximum absorption of EM energy [472, 473]. The EMI SE of PNCs also relies on the conductivity of the nanofiller and its network within the polymer matrix. Both conductivity and the network of the nanofiller with the polymer matrix depend on the type and the nature of the nanofiller. The conductivity and the connectivity of nanofillers enhance the EMI SE of PNCs by absorbing EM radiations [465]. Furthermore, the conductivity and the nanofiller interactions are also greatly influenced by the geometry of the nanofiller. For example, nanofillers having different geometries like granular, spherical, rod-like, or flat surfaces, etc., with different shapes and sizes exhibit different conductivity as well as respective nanofiller connectivity [465]. Spherical particles are aggregates of different sizes, rod or tube-like fillers exhibit different diameters and lengths i.e. length/diameter (aspect ratio of filler), while graphene exhibits single-layer thick planar geometry with a flat surface. With the aspect ratio of nanofillers is high, the bulk conductivity of PNCs increases, thereby increasing the EMI SE values [465]. Moreover, the EMI SE of PNCs can be effectively tuned by simply varying the filler contents in the polymer. Thus, by controlling the filler loadings of PNCs, the microwave absorption can be effectively tuned in a broad frequency range with strong absorption and wide absorption bandwidth. In particular, the variation in the filler loading leads to minimum reflection loss either at low frequency or at high frequency. High filler loadings are generally required to achieve adequate shielding capabilities (< 20 dB) which adversely affects the mechanical performance of PNCs [474]. Therefore, optimizing the filler loading without compromising the electrical conductivity and EMI SE of PNCs is still a challenge.

6.3 Frequency of Incident Electromagnetic Waves

The EMI shielding ability of PNCs also depends upon the frequency of the incoming EM field. Typically, with increasing frequency, the reflection loss decreases due to an increase

in shield impedance, and the absorption loss increases due to a decrease in skin depth with respect to frequency [466]. Significantly higher EMI SE values were observed for some PNCs in the X band region while lower values were obtained in the S band region [475]. In particular, the conductivity increases with an increase in frequency, and thus the EMI SE values increase comparatively with increased conductivity.

6.4 Sample Thickness

The EMI shielding capabilities of PNCs not only depend on the shielding materials and the frequency of incoming EM field but also the thickness of the test specimen [476]. Ideally, an increase in the specimen thickness leads to higher absorption while thinner specimens result in a lower absorption. A very thick specimen is not suitable for EMI shielding application [464]. In particular, with increased sample thickness, the absorption loss gets increased while the reflection loss does not change with respect to sample thickness. This leads to an overall increase in the EMI SE of PNCs which increases linearly with the sample thickness [466]. As the sample thickness increases, more conducting dipoles are being produced at the interface between the polymer matrix and the nanofiller which leads to absorption and internal reflection; hence EMI SE of PNCs increases with thickness [477, 478]. The relation between thickness, permeability, and frequency of minimum reflection can be given as: $f_m = \frac{c}{2\pi\mu''d}$, where f_m is the matching frequency with minimum reflection loss, c is the velocity of light, d is the sample thickness and μ'' is the imaginary part of the permeability [464]. The above equation demonstrates that upon increasing the sample thickness, the f_m shifts towards a lower frequency [479]. Also, in several studies, it has been shown that upon increasing the sample thickness, the resonance frequency decreases [476, 480]. Thus, specimen thickness is a critical parameter for the EMI shielding application of PNCs.

6.5 Processing Methods and Parameters

The EMI shielding capabilities of PNCs greatly depend on the processing/synthesis methods by which the composites are being produced. The nanofiller dispersion within the polymer matrix and the polymer-filler interaction varies depending on the synthesis methods of PNCs. For example; PNCs prepared via melt mixing or solvent casting exhibit different electrical, mechanical, thermal, and EMI shielding characteristics [465]. In melt-mixed PNCs, the shear force exerted on the filler particles is comparatively higher than that of the solvent casting technique. Furthermore, the higher shearing force during the mixing process results in

a higher breakage of filler particles in the PNCs. Therefore, PNCs prepared via solvent casting would result in a higher EMI SE than the composites prepared via melt mixing. Moreover, the synthesis of PNCs depends on several processing parameters. For example, the synthesis of PNCs using a melt mixing process via a twin screw extruder depends on mixing temperature and duration, rotor speed, molding pressure, sequence of adding ingredients, and the capacity (volume) of the barrel, etc., [465]. In two-roll milling or dry mixing of polymer composite ingredients, the processing parameters such as mixing time, mixing temperature, roller speed (rpm), and the ratio of their speed play a central role. In contrast, the EMI shielding characteristics of PNCs prepared via the solution casting process are controlled by the type and quantity of solution, mixing time, mixing temperature, speed of magnetic/mechanical stirrer, type of ultra-sonication technique used, pulse rate and frequency of sonication, etc., [465].

7. Conclusions and Perspectives

PNCs have shown tremendous potential as advanced functional material and are highly desirable for numerous applications, for example; energy storage and conversion, EMI shielding, gas sensing, separation technologies, biomedical fields, etc., given their tailored mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties. As a multidisciplinary field, PNCs are a superior alternative to traditional metal and ceramic-based EMI shielding materials. The high flexibility provided by the PNCs make them promising materials for EMI shielding applications which further creates a possibility to cater them as per industrial requirements. The simple and easy fabrication process, lightweight, high corrosion resistance, and low cost of PNCs are also advantageous for EMI shielding applications.

PNCs can be synthesized in different structures such as bulk form, layered structures, or foam. These varied structures can have a substantial effect on the EMI SE values of PNCs and such types of materials could serve as lightweight and low-cost EMI shielding materials to protect highly sensitive electronic devices, public health, and the environment from the challenges of unwanted EM pollution. Graphene and its derivatives-based PNCs are one of the auspicious developments in the field of materials science. In this review, the state-of-the-art recent advancements in the EMI shielding applications of graphene and its derivatives-based multifunctional PNCs have been broadly discussed. In particular, EMI shielding characteristics of graphene-integrated various polymeric systems such as elastomers, thermoplastics, thermosets, biopolymers, and conducting polymers have been thoroughly discussed. The

synthesis methods of graphene and its counterparts have been briefly discussed. Furthermore, the factors that cause EMI shielding, the need for the shielding material, and the fundamentals of the dominant shielding mechanisms that govern the EMI attenuation in PNCs have also been concisely discussed in this review.

In recent years, GPNCs have shown promising growth in technology as well as applications. The strategies and advanced synthesis techniques of GPNCs result in an alteration of their final properties making them technologically more sustainable. Furthermore, graphene also exhibits extraordinary electrical, optical, thermal, and mechanical properties along with a high aspect ratio making it an ideal replacement for traditional nanofillers integrated in polymeric systems. In these GPNCs, graphene has been utilized in the form of, nanosheets, nanoplatelets, nanoribbons, nanowires, and other forms of nanoparticle arrays. Graphene nanosheets consisting of single or few layers of sp² bonded carbon atoms have shown tremendous potential as an outstanding EMI shielding material. Furthermore, GPNCs have been actively documented for EMI shielding applications demonstrating enhanced EMI shielding performances by virtue of their excellent thermal and electrical conductivities, processing advantages, corrosion resistance, high specific surface area, as well as exceptional chemical, thermal, and mechanical stability. The electron transfer characteristic of graphene is advantageous for enhancing the EMI shielding capability of PNCs where the main aim is to achieve high electrical conductivity at low graphene content. However, achieving high electrical conductivity and high EMI shielding performance of GPNCs is still a challenge as it is a complex process. Furthermore, the adequate dispersion level of graphene and its counterparts along with the intensified interfacial adhesion with the polymer matrix is the critical factor for obtaining a conducting network at a lower percolation threshold thereby upgrading the electrical conductivity and EMI shielding characteristics of GPNCs.

Until now, enormous research has already been performed on the GPNCs as EMI shielding materials and different methods have been employed to fabricate more efficient, low cost and lightweight composites with enhanced electrical properties and EMI shielding performances. Regardless of remarkable achievement in this field, there is a demand for explosive growth of thinner, lighter and highly efficient next-generation EMI shielding materials. Compared with metal or ceramic-based EMI shielding materials, GPNCs are highly attractive materials with features like lightweight, easy processability, low thickness, broad bandwidth, and high absorption which demonstrate their prospective in EMI shielding applications. Also, it has been realized that the electrical conductivity, dielectric constant,

permeability, and microstructure of PNCs take a leading role in attaining high EMI SE and high absorption, thus, the equal distribution of these properties is the most crucial. Other factors that govern the EMI SE of GPNCs are the compounding and/or processing conditions such as mixing period, temperature and rotor speed in melt-mixed PNCs. Generally, the solution processing method is more efficient as compared with melt mixing where high shear forces destroy the filler lengths. Another aspect is the efficient absorption bandwidth and specimen thickness. Most of the reported EMI shielding materials exhibit small absorption bandwidth and large thickness while PNCs generally exhibit absorption-dominated mechanisms with substantial absorption bandwidth. The global trend is to take advantage of nanofiller properties to develop, novel and multifunctional PNCs. Therefore, the main aim is to make maximum use of the intrinsic properties of graphene to improve the synergistic effect between other components of PNCs. Nowadays more and more research interest is devoted towards designing new types of GPNCs to obtain outstanding EMI shielding properties. Nevertheless, the excellent EMI shielding performance of novel GPNCs needs to be further explored with continuous innovation and development. The present EMI shielding and microwave absorption mechanism also need to be examined in more detail and inventions are immediately required for practical applications. Thus, while developing EMI shielding materials, the factors influencing the EMI wave absorption should be considered for obtaining stronger absorption and better EMI shielding performance over a broad frequency range.

In order to efficiently design and tailor the EMI shielding performance of GPNCs, future work should focus on the development of composite materials with superior dielectric and magnetic losses these properties play a significant role in the shielding mechanism of the material. Furthermore, it is also important for the material to exhibit excellent dielectric as well as magnetic properties to pursue higher EMI SE values. If the material exhibits only excellent dielectric properties and poor magnetic properties, then it will show low EMI SE values. Moreover, many of the studies have been focused on developing high EMI SE GPNCs, while less focus is devoted to investigating the mechanical and fire-retardant characteristics. As the PNCs used for EMI shielding applications need to bear mechanical load; hence the mechanical properties of GPNCs should be examined. Also, the polymers are known to be flammable, therefore, the thermal and fire-retardant properties of GPNCs need to be studied. Besides, in the future focus should also be given to the development of highly efficient eco-friendly GPNCs for EMI shielding applications as limited literature is available on graphene-based sustainable PNCs. Recently, materials with multilayer nanostructure and 3D architectures, for

example; foams, hydrogel, and aerogel have enticed significant interest in EMI shielding applications. Foaming can enhance the functionalities of GPNCs and increase the electrical conductivity thereby influencing their EMI shielding performance. Therefore, graphene-reinforced polymer composite foams should be investigated in detail to ascertain their potential as an EMI shielding material. Attempts should also be made to further optimize the EMI shielding characteristics of graphene-derived PNCs by altering the chemical structure of graphene and its derivatives via functionalization or encapsulation techniques at the production level. This type of approach in the future can give new insight into developing novel EMI shielding materials.

The current trend is more focused on fabricating graphene-based hybrid composites. For example, graphene and one or more conducting nanofillers are incorporated into the polymer matrix. Graphene-based hybrid PNCs with suitable microstructure and pore size are required for optimizing their EMI shielding performance. Porous structures with suitable pore sizes are bound to amplify internal reflections and total absorption. There has been more interest in developing heterogeneous PNCs reinforced with graphene combined with magnetic or dielectric metal NPs, ferrites-based materials, or ceramics for enhancing the EMI shielding properties resulting from the synergic effect of graphene and the inorganic additives. The inclusion of multiple nanofillers in the composites is found to be efficient in enhancing the EMI SE of PNCs by absorption and multiple reflections of EM waves. Therefore, a combination of graphene with other suitable conducting nanofillers can efficiently create an excellent conducting network which is needed to generate enhanced EMI SE in the PNCs. Thus, ternary and quaternary GPNCs are becoming a standard approach for obtaining highly efficient EMI shielding materials, whereas the selection of the polymer matrix and nanofillers can be tailored as per their content and the interaction. Moreover, the fundamental understanding of the structure and electronic properties of hybrids is essential to optimize SE values. Another aspect that has not been explored extensively is the temperature effect on the EMI SE of GPNCs. Most of the EMI shielding studies documented have been carried out at room temperature. Therefore, EMI shielding properties at elevated temperatures should be explored for GPNCs. Moreover, it is believed that novel GPNCs with well-defined compositions, optimized microstructure, good mechanical characteristics, and high thermal stability will have a bright future in the realization of an ideal and highly efficient material for EMI shielding applications. In summary, this review article highlights current trends in this

interesting and innovative research field that achieved considerable progress toward obtaining efficient EMI shielding materials for high-end applications.

Data Availability Statement:

The preprint copy of this article is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484843>, and the dataset is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17544206>

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